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QAYUM VA ACHCHIQDONA ANOR MEVA PO‘STINING TURLI ERITUVCHILAR YORDAMIDA OLINGAN EKSTRAKT LARI HAMDA TARKIBIDAN UGLEVOD MODDALARINING XROMATOGRAFIK TAHLILI

UO‘T 634.64

Niyozov Xasan Niyoz o‘g‘li¹*Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya instituti, Biotexnologiya kafedrasida katta o‘qituvchi**E-mail: niyozovxasan8@gmail.com (0000-0002-0732-4409)¹***Nazarov G‘olib Abdishukur o‘g‘li²***Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya instituti, Biotexnologiya kafedrasida mudiri, b.f.f.d.PhD.**E-mail: nazarovgolib05@gmail.com (0000-0002-0732-4409)***Otajonov Asadjon Shonazar o‘g‘li***Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya instituti, Biotexnologiya kafedrasida katta o‘qituvchi***Maxkamova Diyora Madaminjon qizi***Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya instituti Biotexnologiya kafedrasida magistranti***Matchanova Durdona Shapurovna***Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya instituti, Biotexnologiya kafedrasida katta o‘qituvchi***Aripov Mirolim Mirazim o‘g‘li***Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya instituti Biotexnologiya kafedrasida dotsenti*

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda anor po‘stlog‘i turli xil organik erituvchilar yordamida 2 xil mahalliy anor navlaridan: Achchiqdona, Qayumdan ajratib olindi va eritmalarning tarkibi xromatografiya (HPLC) yordamida tahlil qilindi va anor po‘stlog‘idan olingan namunalarning erituvchilaridagi uglevodlar fruktoza, glyukoza, saxaroza va maltoza antioksidant faol moddalar miqdori taqqoslandi. Anor po‘stlog‘ini ajratib olish uchun erituvchi sifatida suv, etil asetat va etil spirt ishlatilgan. Erituvchilar tarkibini tahlil qilish uchun 254,4 nm to‘lqin uzunliklari ishlatilgan.

Kalit so‘z: Achchiqdona, Qayum, glyukoza, fruktoza, saxaroza, maltoza, xromatografiya (HPLC), tubi tekis kolba, Sellyuloza va gemisellyuloza.

Kirish. Hozirgi kunda jahonda kuzatilayotgan oziq-ovqat va boshqa istemol tovarlari yetishmovchiligini yechimi sifatida qishloq xo‘jaligi sohasini jadal rivojlantirish dolzarb muammolarning yechimi sifatida ko‘rsatiladi. Jahon miqiyosida bog‘dorchilik sohasi bilan birga, ulardan olinadigan mahsulotlarni qayta ishlash va ikkilamchi mahsulotlardan unumli foydalanish o‘zining muhim ahamiyatini saqlab qolmoqda. Dunyo olimlari tomonidan olib borilayotgan tadqiqotlar orasida, bunday muammolarning yechimini izlashga doir chora tadbirlarni tashkil qilish imkoniyatini beruvchi, ilmiy asoslangan hamda ishlab chiqarishga joriy etilgan ishlanmalar ko‘plab uchraydi.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasini rivojlantirishning 2030-yilgacha belgilangan chora tadbirlari doirasida bog‘dorchilik, uzumchilik va boshqa ko‘plab qishloq xo‘jalik mahsulotlarini yetishtirishning samarali usullarini ishlab chiqish borasida vazifalar aniq belgilab berilgan. Yurtimiz xududida yetishtiriladigan anor navlarining hosildorligi hamda tuproq va iqlim shartiga moslab yetishtirishga oid ko‘plab tajribaviy ishlar amalga oshirib kelinmoqda.

Hududlarda yetishtirilishi mumkin bo‘lgan anor navlarini o‘rganish hamda tahlil etish orqali ushbu rejalarning istiqboldagi natijalariga salmoqli hissa qo‘shish mumkin. Shu o‘rinda O‘zbekiston hududlari kesimida olib qaraladigan bo‘lsa Farg‘ona vodiysi, Qashqadaryo va Surxondaryo viloyatlaridagi rejalar, shuningdek, mamlakatning boshqa mintaqalaridagi mavjud anor bog‘larining hisobga olinsa, yaqin o‘n yillikda Respublika qishloq xo‘jaligida anor yetishtirish va hosildorlik ko‘rsatkichini oshirish, ishlab chiqarish hajmini yillik 600 ming tonnaga oshirish maqsad qilingan.

Adabiyotlar sharxi. Hozirgi kunda inson tanasi uchun zarur bo‘lgan, shifobaxsh xususiyatga ega, biologik faol birikmalarning qiymati alohida ahamiyatga ega. Biologik faol

moddalarga oqsillar, uglevodlar, lipidlar, fermentlar, vitaminlar, gormonlar, makro-mikro elementlar va boshqa ko‘plab birlamchi va ikkilamchi metabolitlarni misol qilish mumkin. Bu asosiy biologik faol birikmalardan tanadagi metabolizmni rag‘batlantiruvchi va yuqori ta’sirga ega. So‘nggi yillarda anor po‘sti chiqindi emas, balki yuqori biologik qiymatga ega ikkilamchi xom ashyo sifatida e’tirof etilmoqda. Ilmiy adabiyotlarda anor po‘stida fenolik birikmalar, taninlar, flavonoidlar bilan bir qatorda muhim miqdorda uglevodlar mavjudligi qayd etilgan. Uglevodlar nafaqat energiya manbai, balki strukturaviy, texnologik va biologik faol komponent sifatida ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi [1,2].

Anorning shifobaxshligi bilan boshqa mevalardan ajralib turadi. Meva tarkibida o‘rtacha 25-32% qand, 0,2-2,5% organik kislotalar, 10% tanin, 3,4% gacha oqsillar, 2-6% pektin, shuningdek temir, kobalt, yod, C, PP, A vitaminlari mavjud. Mevalarda C vitamin miqdori 250-1300 mg ni tashkil qiladi. Bu esa uning istemoliga bo‘lgan qiziqishning ortishiga sabab bo‘ladi [3].

Ushbu tabiiy antioksidantlar inson organizmidagi erkin radikal oksidlanish, qarish jarayonini va ko‘plab kasalliklarning rivojlanishini oldini olish vazifasini bajaradi. Anor po‘stida mavjud uglevodlar fenolik birikmalar va ellagik kislota kabi biologik faol moddalarning bog‘lanish muhitini hosil qiladi. Monosaxaridlar va Polisaxarid matritsa antioksidantlarning barqarorligini oshiradi va ularning ekstraksiyasida muhim omil hisoblanadi. Ilmiy tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, uglevodlar bilan bog‘langan fenolik komplekslar organizmda sekin parchalanib, uzoq muddatli antioksidant ta’sir ko‘rsatadi [4].

Anor po‘sti quruq moddasiga nisbatan 40–60 % gacha uglevodlar mavjud bo‘lib, ular asosan Polisaxaridlar (sellyuloza, gemisellyuloza, pektin moddalar), Oligosaxaridlar kam miqdorda mono- va disaxaridlar (glyukoza, fruktoza)dan iborat. Po‘stning asosiy qismi strukturaviy uglevodlardan tashkil topgan bo‘lib, ayniqsa selluloza va gemisellyuloza miqdori yuqori. Pektin moddalar esa suvda eruvchan polisaxaridlar sifatida alohida ahamiyatga ega. Sellyuloza va gemisellyuloza o‘simlik hujayra devorining asosiy tarkibiy qismlari hisoblanadi [5].

Anor meva po‘stining mexanik mustahkamligini ta’minlaydi hamda saqlash jarayonida mikrobiologik barqarorlikni oshiradi. Eng sosiy jarayonlardan biri bo‘lgan quritish va maydalash jarayonida texnologik xususiyatlarni belgilaydi

1-rasm. Anor meva po‘sti va uning quritib, maydalangan na‘munasi

Olinish texnologiyasi bir muncha sodda ekanligi bilan va unumdorli yuqori ekanligi sababidan mazkur xom ashyodan ellagik kislota olish, yuqori samaradorlikka ega texnologiya sifatida e’tirof etiladi [6].

Ishning maqsadi: mahalliy anor mevasi po‘sti tarkibidagi antioksidant xususiyatga ega bo‘lgan uglevod moddalarining miqdoriy tahlillarini amalga oshirishdan iborat.

Uslublar. Ekstraksiyalash bosqichlarida dastlab 2 xil navdagi anor po‘stining quritib olingan va maydalangan biomassasidan, har biri 50 g dan iborat bo‘lgan 3 turdagi erituvchiga mos ravishda 3 tadan na‘munalar o‘lchab olinadi. o‘lchab olingan na‘munalarning har biri alohida idishlarga (500 ml hajmdagi tubi tekis kolbalar) solinib, unga barcha erituvchilarning (suv, etil atsetat va etil spirti) teng miqdori (250 ml dan har bir na‘muna uchun) quyiladi va magnitli arlashtirish uskunasi 30 daqiqada davomida ekstraksiyalandi, shundan so‘ng na‘munalar xona haroratida 48 soatga qoldiriladi. Jarayon davomida belgilangan vaqt yakunlangach na‘munalarning har biridagi suyuq qismi alohida quyib olinadi va qoldiq qism ustiga dastlabki hajmga teng miqdorda erituvchilardan quyiladi, hamda dastlabki bosqichda belgilangan vaqt birligida saqlanadi. Shu tariqa ekstraksiyalash uch

marotaba amalga oshiriladi va barcha ekstragentlar (eritmalar yordamida anor po‘stining uch bosqichidan olingan ekstraksiya jarayon na‘munasining suyuq qismi) anor naviga qarab bir idishga yig‘ib boriladi.

Ekstraktlarni konsentrlash jarayoni, rotorli bug‘latish RE100-Pro uskunasi yordamida amalga oshirildi. Bunda jarayon metodologiyasi, rotorning aylanish tezligi 60 ay/daq, harorat 38-40 °C va bosim 0,9 Pa ni tashkil qiladi. Jarayon davomiyligi organik erituvchilar (etil atsetat va etil spirti) orqali olingan ekstrakt eritmalar tarkibining 10 % qoldiq miqdorigacha bug‘latishda o‘rtacha 60 – 90 daqiqani tashkil qiladi. Suvli ekstraktlarni bug‘latishda esa suv hammomining harorati 70-75 °C gacha ko‘tariladi, jarayon davomiyligi tarkibdagi 25-30 % qoldiq miqdor qolishiga nisbatan, 90 – 120 daqiqani tashkil qiladi. Har bir konsentrlab olingan na‘munalar alohida idishlarga yig‘ib olinadi va keyingi bosqichda ularning sifat va miqdoriy tahlillari amalga oshiriladi.

Tadqiqotning ikkinchi bosqichida turli navdagi anorning po‘stidan ajratib olingan ekstraktlar tarkibidagi uglevod moddalar miqdorlarini tahlil qilishda, zamonaviy xromatografik usullardan foydalanildi. Ish jarayonini tashkil qilish uchun dastlab Namunadagi Uglevodlar tarkibiga kiruvchi monasaxaridlar hamda disaxaridalarni suyuqlik xromatografiyasi usuli yordamida aniqlandi.

Namunadan 2-3 gr miqdorida analitik tarozida tortib olinib, 100 ml hajmdagi yassi kolbaga solinadi. Ustiga 40 ml 70% li etanol eritmasidan qo‘shiladi. Aralashma magnit aralashtirgich, teskari sovutkich bilan jihozlanib, 1 soat davomida intensiv aralashtirib turgan holda 55-60 °C qaynatiladi va keyinchalik 1 soat davomida xona haroratida aralashtiriladi. Aralashma tindirilib filtrlab olinadi. Qolgan qismiga 25 ml 70 % etanoldan solib 2-marta qayta ekstraksiya qilinadi. Filtratlar birlashtiriladi va 100 ml o‘lchagich kolbaga solinib chizig‘igacha 70% etanol bilan to‘ldiriladi. Hosil bo‘lgan eritma sentrafugada 6000-8000 ay/daq tezlikda 15-20 daqiqa davomida aylantiriladi. Hosil bo‘lgan eritma ustki qismidan analiz uchun olinadi.

Xromatografga dastlab, ishchi standart eritmalar, keyinchalik tayyorlangan ishchi eritmalar kiritildi. Tahlillarda yuqori samarali suyuqlik xromatografiyasi qo‘llaniladi. Tahlil uchun moslashtirilgan xromatografiya muhitining eksperimental sharoitlari quyidagilarni o‘zida jamlaydi: Degasser G1379A degasser, G1311A QuatPump, ALS G1313A avtonamunalagich, Colcom G1316A ustunli pech, RID G1362A refraktometrik detektor va Agilent ChemStation Rev. ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash tizimi bilan jihozlangan Agilent 1100 suyuq xromatograf. B.01.03. Ustun SupelcosiLLC-NH2-5 mikron 4,6x250 mm, "Supelco", AQSH. 100 va 1000 µl hajmli mikropipetlar, "VWR", Polsha. Pipetka 5 ml, "Biohit", Finlyandiya. Analitik balansi AnD GR-202 (aniqlik 0,00001 g), "AnD", Yaponiya. Suv deionizatori Millipore Simplicity, "Millipore", Frantsiya. Ultrasonik hammom S 30 H Elmasonic, "Elma", Germaniya. Filtr neylon 0,45 mikron 13 mm. Fruktosa standarti, imp. Glyukoza standarti, imp. Saxaroza standarti, imp. Maltoza monohidrat standarti, imp. HPLC "Sigma-aldrich" uchun asetnitril ishlatildi. Ushbu usulni sinovdan o‘tkazish jarayonida tahlil shartlari aniqlandi: -izokratik elutsiya rejimi, harakatchan faza tarkibi 82/18 hajm nisbatida atsetonitril/suv ikkita alohida idishdan aralashtirmasdan. Glyukoza va fruktoza cho‘qqilarini to‘liq ajratishga erishish uchun mobil fazaning tarkibi o‘zgarishi mumkin. Volumetrik elutsiya tezligi 1,0 ml/min; in'ektsiya hajmi 10 µl; ustunli termostat harorati 35 °C; standartlarni saqlash vaqtlari: -fruktoza -4,9 ± 0,2 min, glyukoza -5,7 ± 0,2 min, saxaroza -10,4 ± 0,2 min, maltoza -12,1 ± 0,2 min shunda har bir bosqichda (4x3) ja‘mi 12 ta ekstrakt tajriba qilingan.

Natijalar va muhokamalar. Tadqiqotlarni bajarishda tanlab olingan 2 turdagi anor navlarining turli erituvchilarda (suv, etil spirit, etil atsetat) olib borilgan ekstraksiyalash jarayonlari uchun tanlangan 250 ml miqdorlari uch bosqichda ja‘mi 750 ml erituvchi hajmini tashkil qiladi. Bir bosqichli ekstraksiya 48 soatni tashkil qiladi, barcha uch bosqichdagi ushbu ko‘rsatkich umumiy 144 soatga yetadi. Eritmaga olingan anor po‘sti bir kunda 3 martagacha chayqatgich (Шейкер GFL-3017) yordamida chayqatib qayta saqlashga olinadi, bu orqali ekstraksiyada moddalarning eruvchanligini oshiriladi.

1-jadval

Anor po'stining ekstraksiyalashga sarflangan reaktiv miqdori va ekstraksiyalash davri

№	Anor navlari 50 g	Suv ml	Etanol ml	Etil atsetat ml
		144 soat		
1	Achchiqdona	1) 250	1) 250	1) 250
		2) 250	2) 250	2) 250
		3) 250	3) 250	3) 250
2	Qayum	1) 250	1) 250	1) 250
		2) 250	2) 250	2) 250
		3) 250	3) 250	3) 250

Izoh: jadvalda berilgan erituvchi hajmlari 50 g na'munaga nisbatan tanlangan, na'muna hajmi ko'payishi erituvchilar miqdorining kamayishi yoki ortishiga olib kelishi mumkin.

Tahlil natijalariga ko'ra erituvchilarning turli nisbatlari va ekstraksiya davriyligi bir necha tajribalar asosida amalga oshirildi, hamda optimal miqdorlar, shuningdek vaqt birligi sifatida 1-jadvalda berilgan natijalar sifatida tanlab olindi. Na'munalar vaqt o'tishi bilan, aralashma jigarrang malla ko'rinishga keladi (2-rasmga qarang). Fraksiyalash va filtrlash jarayonidan keyin, suyuqlik tarkibi to'q qizil, yorqin ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi (3-rasmga qarang).

2-rasm. Ekstraksiyalangan na'munalar.

3-rasm. Ajratib olingan ekstrakt suyuqliklar

Na'munalarni quritishdagi qoldiq namligi 3-6 % ni tashkil qilganligi bois ekstraksiya bosqichlarida, maydalangan po'stloqqa yaxshi shimiladi Uch xil erituvchida erigan moddalarning suyuq qismi, anor naviga va erituvchi turiga mos holda alohida idishlarga quyib olinadi. Olingan ekstrakt miqdorlari turlicha bo'ladi, bunga sabab sifatida aytish mumkinki, erituvchilarning o'simlik manbaasiga yutilishi va unda saqlanib qolish ko'rsatkichi turlicha bo'ladi, shu boisdan miqdorlar bir-biridan uncha katta bo'lmagan holda farqlilik namoyon qiladi (2-jadvalga qarang)

2-jadval

Anor navlaridan hosil bo'lgan ekstrakt miqdorlari

№	Anor navlari	Suv ml	Etanol ml	Etil atsetat ml
1	Achchiqdona	345	530	340
2	Qayum	370	530	340

Uch bosqichdan iborat ekstraksiya jarayonlarida ja'mi 750 ml dan erituvchilar kiritilgan, ulardan olingan ekstraktlar miqdori, bir necha sabablarga ko'ra turlicha miqdorlarda bo'ladi, masalan Achchiqdona navli anor po'stidan olingan ekstrakt miqdori suvli eritmasi 345 ml, etil spirtli ekstrakt 530 ml va etil atsetat miqdori – 340 ml hajmni tashkil qiladi. Boshqa navdagi anor po'stlarining ekstraksiyalashda qo'llangan erituvchilarning miqdori ham deyarli shu hajmlarni takrorlaydi. Suvli eritmadagi qayum anor navining po'sti bundan mustasno, sababi ushbu eritmaning miqdori boshqalariga nisbatan keskin farqli ayrim erituvchilar bosqa erituvchilarga nisbatan yuqori hajmda kuzatiladi. Bundan shuni xulosa qilish mumkinki erituvchilarning manbaada saqlanib qolishi va vaqt o'tishi bilan bug'lanishidan kelib chiqqan holda, ular orasida spirtli ekstrakt miqdoriy jixatdan ustunlik qiladi. Bundan tashqari, na'munalarning ayrimlari xujayrasida suvli eritmani yuqori hajmda ushlab qolishi kuzatiladi.

Yuqori samarali suyuqlik xromatografiyasi (HPLC) tahlil natijalari. Ushbu usul biologik faol moddalar miqdori va ularning sifatini tahlil qilish uchun, bugungi kunda yuqori aniqlikdagi, ishonchli tahlil usuli hisoblanadi. Anor po‘sti tarkibidagi polifenol moddalar tahliliga ko‘ra, olingan xromatogrammada ko‘rinib turgan intensiv cho‘qqilar soni, hamda ularning intensivlik ko‘rsatkichlari moddalarning sifat va miqdorlari haqida aniq ma’lumotlar olinishiga sabab bo‘ldi.

4-rasm. Achchiqdona anor navi po‘stining tarkibidagi uglevod tarkibiga kiruvchi monasaxaridlar va disaxaridlar tahlilining xromatogrammalari (a-etil atsetat, b-etil spirt va c-suvli eritmalarda o‘rganilgan).

Ushbu xromatogrammalardagi intensive cho‘qqilar har ikkala polifenolning tarkibda mavjud ekanligini ko‘rsatib beradi. Unga ko‘ra dastlabki 4-5 daqiqalar oralig‘ida kolonkadan chiquvchi modda standartga mos ravishda glyukoza hamda fruktoza ekanligi ma’lum bo‘ldi.

5-rasm. Qayum anor navi po‘stining tarkibidagi uglevod tarkibiga kiruvchi monasaxaridlar va disaxaridlar tahlilining xromatogrammalari (a-etil atsetat, b-etil spirt va c-suvli eritmalarda o‘rganilgan).

Shuningdek standart xromatogrammasiga ko‘ra fruktoza hamda glyukozaning kolonkada ushlanib qolish davriyligi o‘rtacha 4-6 daqiqalar oralig‘iga to‘g‘ri keladi, tahlildagi eritmaning xromatogrammasida shu daqiqalar oralig‘ida fruktoza hamda glyukozaga tegishli intensive cho‘qqilar namoyon bo‘lgan. Achchiqdona anorning po‘stidan ajratilgan har uchta eritma na‘munasidagi moddalarning kolonkadan chiqish davriyligi o‘rtacha 4-5 daqiqalar oralig‘iga to‘g‘ri kelganligini ko‘rish mumkin.

Xromatogrammalarda hosil bo‘lgan ko‘rinishlarning xulosalari sifatida aytish mumkinki, tanlab olingan barcha anor navlarining po‘stloq qismida uglevod tarkibli moddalar miqdori yetarli darajada ko‘p, shunday moddalardan misol qilib fruktoza, glyukoza, saxaroza hamda maltozalar mavjudligi tahlillar natijasida aniqlandi.

Xromatogrammalarda namoyon bo‘lgan moddalarning miqdorini hisoblash orqali ularning aniq hajmini bilish imkoniyati yaratildi. Unga ko‘ra har bir erituvchida erigan anor meva po‘sti tarkibidagi uglevod moddalar xar bir anor navlarida xar xil miqdorda chiqqanligini quyidagi 3,4,5,6-jadvallarda xromatografik miqdoriy tahlil natijalari hamda ushbu uglevod moddalarni grafik ko‘rinishida keltirilgan.

3-jadval

№	Uglevodlar nomi	Suyuqlik xromatografiya priborida Achchiqdona anor po'sti ekstraksiyasida uglevodlar miqdori mg/gr (erituvchilar)		
		Etanol	Atil atsetat	Suv
1	Fruktoza	22,903	6,591	42,255
2	Glyukoza	14,035	2,140	26,428
3	Saxaroza	0,236	0,018	0,000
4	Maltoza	0,538	0,328	0,000
5	Summa	37,713	9,077	68,684

5-grafik

4-jadval

№	Uglevodlar nomi	Suyuqlik xromatografiya priborida Qayum anor po'sti ekstraksiyasida uglevodlar miqdori mg/gr (erituvchilar)		
		Etanol	Etil atsetat	Suv
1	Fruktoza	16,608	3,365	26,288
2	Glyukoza	11,159	0,672	15,501
3	Saxaroza	0,162	0,091	0,087
4	Maltoza	0,127	0,473	0,184
5	Summa	28,055	4,601	42,060

Xromatografik tadqiqotlar natijasida olingan tahlillar shuni ko'rsatadiki turli erituvchilarda moddalar miqdori farqli bo'ladi. Masalan achchiqdona anor navining po'stidan, etanol eritmasi yordamida olingan ekstraktlar tarkibida fruktoza (22,903 mg/gr) hamda suvli ekstraksiya orqali aniqlanganda fruktoza (42,255 mg/gr) miqdorda chiqdi. Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki etanol eritmasiga nisbatan, suvli eritmada bir muncha yuqori chiqdi. Shu ikkita erituvchiga nisbatan etil atsetatda esa eng past ko'rsatkich (6.591 mg/gr) chiqqanini ko'rish mumkin. Glyukoza moddasi 3 ta erituvchilardan, quyidagi miqdorlarda etanol (14.035 mg/gr) hamda suv (26.428 mg/gr)da chiqqanini ko'rishingiz mumkin. Bunda suvli eritmada xar doimgidak yaxshi natija bergan. Eng past ko'rsatkich etil atsetat eritmasida (5.140 mg/gr) miqdorda hosil bo'lgan. Uglevodlarning saxaroza hamda maltoza moddalari eng past ko'rsatkich (saxaroza: etanol 0.162 mg/gr, etil atsetat 0.091mg/gr, suv 0.087mg/gr), (maltoza: etanol 0.127mg/gr, etil atsetat 0.473mg/gr, suv 0.184mg/gr) hosil bo'lganini ko'rishingiz mumkin. Xulosa qilib aytganda achchiqdona anor nav po'stidan ajratib olingan ekstraktleri tarkibda fruktoza hamda glyukoza uglevod moddalar yuqori miqdorda ko'rsatilganligi, eng past ko'rsatkich bilan saxaroza va maltoza uglevod moddalar chiqqanligini jadvallar hamda grafiklarda ko'rishingiz mumkin.

Qayum anor navining po'stidan, etil atsetat eritmasi yordamida olingan ekstraktlar tarkibida fruktoza uglevod moddasi (3.365 mg/gr), glyukoza (0.672 mg/gr), saxaroza (0.091 mg/gr), maltoza (0.473 mg/gr) nisbatan yuqori miqdorda ekanligini ko'rish mumkin. Ushbu navning etil spirtli

ekstrakti tarkibida ham fruktoza (16.608 mg/gr) bilan glyukoza (11.159 mg/gr) miqdori, saxaroza (0.162 mg/gr), maltoza (0.127 mg/gr) nisbatan miqdori past ko'rsatgichga ega ekanligini aniq bo'ldi. Ushbu ikkita eritmadan tashqari suvda ham uglevod miqdorlari aniqlandi. Suvli eritmada fruktoza (26.288 mg/gr) hamda glyukoza (15.501 mg/gr) miqdorda yuqorida ishlatilgan eritmalardan ko'ra, eruvchanligiga nisbatan yuqori natija qayd etildi. Saxaroza (0.087 mg/gr), maltoza (0.184 mg/gr) Qayum anor po'stining suvli ekstraktida fruktoza (26.288 mg/gr) va glyukoza (15.501 mg/gr) miqdorlari yuqori ko'rsatkich qayt etildi. Saxaroza (0.087 mg/gr) va maltoza (0.184 mg/gr) uglevod moddalarini glyukoza va fruktozaga nisbatan eng past ko'rsatkich qayt etildi.

Xulosa. Tadqiqotlar uchun tanlab olingan ikki turdagi anor navlariga oid meva po'stlari dastlab quritib, maydalab olindi. Na'munalar uch xil erituvchilarda ekstraksiya qilindi, hamda ulardagi ekstrakt miqdorlari alohida o'lchab olindi. Bu orqali maydalangan meva po'stlarining 3 hil eritmani sorbsiyalash qobiliyati ochib berildi.

Har bir na'munadan olingan uch turdagi erituvchida erigan ekstraktlar tarkibi, yuqori samarali suyuqlik xromatografiyasi (HPLC) yordamida tahlil qilindi. Ajratib olingan ekstraktlar tarkibidagi uglevod moddalar tarkibiga kiruvchi monosaxarid va disaxaridlar miqdorlari o'rganilganda, har bir erituvchi tarkibida fruktoza, glyukoza, saxaroza va maltoza moddalar mavjud ekanligi, hamda ularning xromatograf kolonkasida ushlanish davriyligi standartga mos ravishda uglevod moddalarini monosaxarid va disaxaridlardan uchchala eritmadan eruvchaligiga ko'ra eng yuqori ko'rsatkich suvli eritmada erigan moddalar qayd etildi. Eng past ko'rsatkich etil atsetat eritmasida erigan moddalar qayd etildi va tahlili amalga oshirildi

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MODIFIKATSIYALANGAN EPOKSID POLIMERLARNING VIBRATSIYANI YUTUVCHI VA ADGEZION XOSSALARINI O'RGANISH

Navruzov Farxod Mamatqulovich

EMU University Kimyo fanlari kafedrasini mudiri (PhD) dotsent.
O'zbekiston, Toshkent sh. E-mail: navruzovfarmi@gmail.com

Axrorov Azamat A'zamqul o'g'li

O'zbekiston, Toshkent sh. E-mail: axrorovazamat00@gmail.com
EMU University farmatsiya fakulteti 2-bosqich talabasi

Annotatsiya Mazkur ishda epoksid, furan-epoksi va epoksi-slanes asosidagi polimer kompozitsiyalarning qovushqoq-elastik, adgezion-mustahkamlik hamda vibratsiyani yutuvchi xossalari o'rganildi. Tadqiqot jarayonida turli tarkibli polimer tizimlar sintez qilinib, ularning fizik-mexanik va issiqlik-fizik xususiyatlari eksperimental usullar yordamida baholandi. Olingan natijalar epoksid tizimlarni furan va slanes komponentlari bilan modifikatsiyalash ularning ekspluatatsion ko'rsatkichlarini sezilarli darajada yaxshilashini ko'rsatdi. Xususan, furan-epoksi kompozitsiyalar yuqori adgezion mustahkamlik va issiqlikka chidamlilik bilan ajralib turishi aniqlandi. Tadqiqot natijalari asosida bunday polimer materiallarni tebranishni yutuvchi va tovush izolyatsiyalovchi qoplamalar sifatida samarali qo'llash imkoniyati asoslab berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: epoksid polimerlar, furan-epoksi kompozitsiyalar, epoksi-slanes tizimlar, qovushqoq-oelastik xossalari, adgezion mustahkamlik, vibratsiyani yutish, polimer kompozitsiyalar, mexanik xossalari, issiqlik-fizik xossalari, modifikatsiyalangan polimerlar

STUDY OF ADHESIVE STRENGTH AND VISCOELASTIC PROPERTIES OF EPOXY POLYMERS AND THEIR MODIFICATIONS.

Navruzov Farkhod Mamatkulovich

Head of the Department of Chemical Sciences at EMU University,
PhD, Associate Professor.

Uzbekistan, Tashkent. E-mail: navruzovfarmi@gmail.com

Axrorov Azamat A'zamqul o'g'li

Uzbekistan, Tashkent E-mail: axrorovazamat00@gmail.com
2nd year student of the Faculty of Pharmacy, EMU University

Abstract In this study, the viscoelastic, adhesive-strength, and vibration-damping properties of polymer composites based on epoxy, furan-epoxy, and epoxy-slate systems were investigated. During the research, polymer systems with various compositions were synthesized, and their physicochemical and thermophysical properties were evaluated using experimental methods. The obtained results demonstrated that modification of epoxy systems with furan and slate components significantly improves their performance characteristics. In particular, furan-epoxy composites were found to exhibit high adhesive strength and enhanced thermal resistance. Based on the research findings, the potential application of such polymer materials as effective vibration-damping and sound-insulating coatings has been substantiated.

Keywords: epoxy polymers, modification, adhesive strength, viscoelastic properties, epoxy resin, elastic modulus, logarithmic decrement.

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ АДГЕЗИОННО-ПРОЧНОСТНЫХ И ВЯЗКОУПРУГИХ СВОЙСТВ ЭПОКСИДНЫХ ПОЛИМЕРОВ И ИХ МОДИФИКАЦИИ.

Наврузов Фарход Маматкулович

Заведующий кафедрой химических наук EMU University, PhD, доцент.

Узбекистан, г. Ташкент. E-mail: navruzovfarmi@gmail.com

Ахроров Азамат Аъзамкул ўгли

Узбекистан, г. Ташкент. E-mail: axrorovazamat00@gmail.com

Студент 2-го курса фармацевтического факультета Университета ЕМУ.

Аннотация В данном исследовании были изучены вязкоупругие, адгезионно-прочностные и вибропоглощающие свойства полимерных композиций на основе эпоксидных, фуран-эпоксидных и эпоксидно-сланцевых систем. В ходе работы были синтезированы полимерные системы различного состава, а их физико-механические и теплофизические свойства оценены с использованием экспериментальных методов. Полученные результаты показали, что модификация эпоксидных систем фурановыми и сланцевыми компонентами существенно улучшает их эксплуатационные характеристики. В частности, установлено, что фуран-эпоксидные композиции обладают высокой адгезионной прочностью и повышенной термостойкостью. На основе результатов исследования обоснована возможность эффективного применения таких полимерных материалов в качестве вибропоглощающих и звукоизоляционных покрытий.

Ключевые слова: эпоксидные полимеры, модификация, адгезионная прочность, вязкоупругие свойства, эпоксидная смола, модуль упругости, логарифмический декремент.

KIRISH. Hozirgi kunda sanoatning ko‘plab sohalarida tebranish va shovqinni kamaytiruvchi, yuqori adgezion mustahkamlikka ega polimer materiallarga ehtiyoj ortib bormoqda. Bu jihatdan epoksid polimerlar keng qo‘llanilsada, ularning mo‘rtligi va past vibratsiya yutish qobiliyati ularni modifikatsiyalash zaruratini yuzaga keltiradi.

Epoksid tizimlarni furan va slanes asosidagi komponentlar bilan modifikatsiyalash ularning qovushqoq-elastik, mexanik hamda ekspluatatsion xossalarini yaxshilash imkonini beradi. Ayniqsa, furan-epoksi kompozitsiyalar yuqori adgezion mustahkamlik va issiqlikka chidamlilik bilan ajralib turadi.

Mazkur ishda epoksid va ularning modifikatsiyalari asosidagi polimer kompozitsiyalarning qovushqoq-elastik, adgezion-mustahkamlik hamda vibratsiyani yutuvchi xossalari o‘rganilib, ularning samarali qo‘llanilish imkoniyatlari asoslab berildi.

TADQIQOTNING MAQSADI: Epoksid, furan-epoksi va epoksi-slanes asosidagi polimer tizimlarning qovushqoq-elastik, adgezion-mustahkamlik hamda vibratsiyani yutuvchi xossalarini kompleks o‘rganish, ularni turli modifikatsiyalar orqali yaxshilash qonuniyatlarini aniqlash va olingan materiallarning amaliy qo‘llanilish imkoniyatlarini ilmiy asoslashdan iborat.

Shuningdek, tadqiqot doirasida epoksid tizimlarni furan va slanes komponentlari bilan modifikatsiyalash orqali ularning fizik-mexanik va issiqlik-fizik xususiyatlariga ta‘sirini baholash hamda yuqori samarali vibratsiya yutuvchi va tovush izolyatsiyalovchi polimer qoplamalar yaratish imkoniyatlarini aniqlash ko‘zda tutilgan.

TADQIQOT OB‘EKTI VA METODIKASI. Tadqiqot ob‘ekti sifatida epoksidian, furan va slanes asosidagi polimerlar - ED-16, ED-20 (GOST 10587-84), FAED-20 (TU 59-02.039.13-78) hamda EIS-1 (TU 38-1091-76) tanlab olindi [1,2]. Shuningdek, kukunsimon elastomerlar PE-Sh (sirtni qo‘pol ishlov berish uchun) va PE-E (ekstruzion), plastifikator sifatida dibutilftalat (DBF) hamda qotiruvchi sifatida polietilenpoliamin (PEPA) qo‘llanildi.

Ta‘kidlash lozimki, furan-epoksi smola FAED-20 80 massaviy qism furfurolatseton monomeri (FA) va 20 massaviy qism epoksi oligomer ED-16 ni birlashtirish orqali olinadi. FAED-20 ning muhim afzalliklaridan biri shundaki, furfurolatseton monomeri (FA) arzon va tanqis bo‘lmagan xom ashyo - paxta poyasidan olinadi, uning zaxiralari O‘zbekistonda deyarli tuganmas hisoblanadi.

FAED-20 asosidagi qoplamalar yuqori adgezion mustahkamlikka, suvga, issiqlikka va kimyoviy ta‘silarga nisbatan yuqori chidamlilikka ega. Xuddi shunday usul bilan epoksiloksan

polimerlar ham olingan. Shu sababli tadqiqot ob'ekti sifatida FAED-20 va EIS-1 asosidagi epoksi polimerlarning modifikatsiyalari tanlab olindi.

Vibratsiyani yutuvchi polimer kompozitsiyalarni olish va ularni sinash uchun namunalar tayyorlash metodikasi. ED-16, ED-20, FAE-20 va EIS-1 asosidagi polimerlar hamda kompozitsiyalarning tebranishni yutish xossalari o'rganish uchun namunalar quyidagi tartibda tayyorlandi. Kerakli miqdordagi epoksi, furan-epoksi va epoksi-slanes oligomerlari quritish shkafida 370 K haroratda 2 soat davomida quritildi.

So'ngra oligomerlarga avval zarur miqdorda plastifikator-dibutilftalat (DBF), polimer va organomineral to'ldiruvchilar qo'shildi, undan keyin qotiruvchi-polietilenpoliamin (ED:PEPA=10:1 nisbatda) kiritildi. Har bir komponent qo'shilgandan so'ng kompozitsiya 300 K da 10 daqiqa davomida mexanik aralashirgich yordamida aralashirildi. Tayyor aralashma oldindan antiadhezion modda bilan ishlov berilgan qoliplarga quyildi. Reaksiyaga kirishuvchi massa 300 K da (FAED-20 uchun 350 K da) 10 soat davomida qotirildi. ED-16 va EIS asosidagi namunalar 373 K da 4 soat davomida termik ishlovdan o'tkazildi, FAED-20 asosidagi namunalar esa 400 K da 6 soat davomida qo'shimcha issiqlik bilan ishlov berildi.

Materialning kimyoviy tuzilishini o'rganish uchun namunalar tayyorlash. Namunalar KBr (kaliy bromid) bilan tabletkalar presslash usuli orqali tayyorlandi. Buning uchun qotirilgan polimer yoki kompozitsion material maydalanib, stupkada kukun holiga keltirildi va unga maydalangan KBr qo'shildi. Hosil bo'lgan kukun aralashmasidan press yordamida disklar shaklida namunalar olinadi.

Kompozitsion polimer materiallarning vibratsiyani yutuvchi va fizik-mexanik xossalari o'rganish metodikasi. Olingan namunalarining qovushqoq-elastik xossalari rezonans chuqurligi kengligi usuli yordamida tadqiq qilindi [3,4].

Olingan gomopolimerlar va ular asosidagi kompozitsiyalarning kimyoviy tuzilishi IR-spektroskopiya usuli yordamida SPECORD-75 IR spektrometrida o'rganildi. Hosil qilingan kompozitsiyalar asosidagi qoplamalarning adhezion mustahkamligi esa bir-biriga bog'lovchi orqali birlashtirilgan "qo'ziqorincha" namunalarini ajratib olish (uzish) usuli bilan FP-100/1 (GDR) uzilish mashinasida aniqlanildi.

Kompozitsion polimer qoplamalarning mikroqattiq PMT-3 asbobida o'lchanib, ushbu qurilma ma'lum statik yuk ostida indentorni sinov materialiga botirish imkonini beruvchi mikroskopdan iborat. Polimer qoplamalarning zarba mustahkamligi esa U-2 qurilmasida aniqlanib, u vertikal kopr (urib sinovchi moslama) ko'rinishidagi asbob hisoblanadi.

Qoplamalar qalinligi TIP-10 magnit qalinlik o'lchagichi yordamida aniqlangan. Issiqlik-fizik xossalarni, xususan issiqlik o'tkazuvchanlik koeffitsiyentini aniqlash uchun oldindan statsionar issiqlik oqimini o'lchash usuli-ya'ni issiqlik o'lchov (teplometrik) usul qo'llanildi. Ushbu usul doimiy quvvatga ega tekis issiqlik manbaidan ajralayotgan issiqlik oqimining sinov namunasi orqali o'tib, doimiy haroratga ega jismga uzatilishini qayd etishga asoslangan.

Tadqiq etilgan polimerlar va ular asosidagi kompozitsiyalarning issiqlik o'tkazuvchanligining haroratga bog'liqligi dinamik usul yordamida o'rganildi. Tadqiq qilinayotgan kompozitsiyalarning issiqlik o'tkazuvchanligi 240-500 K harorat oralig'ida GOST 23630.2-79 talablariga muvofiq, issiqlik-fizik tadqiqotlar uchun mo'ljallangan kam sonli sanoat qurilmalaridan biri bo'lgan IT-λ-400 asbobida eksperimental ravishda aniqlandi. Issiqlik o'tkazuvchanlik o'lchovlari qalinligi 15 mm bo'lgan polimer kompozitsiya namunalarida olib borildi. Olingan barcha eksperimental natijalar matematik statistika usullari asosida qayta ishlandi.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI VA ULARNI MUHOKAMASI. Epoksid polimerlar va ularning hosilalarining adhezion-mustahkamlik hamda tebranishni yutuvchi xossalari o'rganildi. Tadqiq qilingan polimerlar, ya'ni epoksid oligomerlar va ularning hosilalarining qovushqoq-elastik hamda adhezion-mustahkamlik xossalari natijalari 1-jadvalda keltirilgan.

Epoksid polimerlar va ularning hosilalarining qovushqoq-elastik hamda adgezion-mustahkamlik xossalari.

Xossalari	Polimerlar			
	ED-20	ED-16	FAED-20	EIS-1
Logarifmik dekrement, δ	0.086	0,110	0.098	0,091
Dinamik elastiklik moduli E' , MPa	3820	4060	3580	3400
Yo'qotish moduli E'' , MPa	344	398	387	310
Shishalanish harorati T_s , K	390	370	400	340
Zichlikn ρ , g/cm ³	1,26	1,28	1,25	1,23
Adgezion mustahkamlik δ_a , MPa	36,0	32,0	40,0	26,0
Zarbaga chidamlilik σ_{yn} , MPa	1,11	1,20	1,22	1,26

1-jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki, ED-16, ED-20 asosidagi epoksid polimerlar va ularning FAED-20 hamda EIS-1 hosilalarining qovushqoq-elastik hamda adgezion-mustahkamlik xossalari bir-biridan sezilarli darajada farq qiladi.

Masalan, ED-16 asosidagi epoksid polimer uchun logarifmik dekrement $\delta=0,110$, dinamik elastiklik moduli $E'=4060$ MPa, energiya yo'qotish moduli $E''=398$ MPa, shishalanish harorati $T_s=370K$, zichlik $\rho=1,28$ g/sm³, adgezion mustahkamlik $\delta_a=32,0$ MPa va zarbaga bardoshlilik $\sigma_y=1,20$ MPa ni tashkil qiladi.

ED-20 asosidagi epoksid polimer uchun esa logarifmik dekrement $\delta=0,086$, dinamik elastiklik moduli $E'=3820$ MPa, energiya yo'qotish moduli $E''=344$ MPa, shishalanish harorati $T_s=390K$, zichlik $\rho=1,26$ g/sm³, adgezion mustahkamlik $\delta_a=36,0$ MPa va zarbaga bardoshlilik $\sigma_y=1,11$ MPa ni tashkil qiladi.

Tahlildan ko'rinib turibdiki, ED-16 asosidagi epoksid polimerda adgezion mustahkamlik va shishalanish harorati (T_s)dan tashqari, boshqa barcha qovushqoq-elastik va adgezion-mustahkamlik xossalari ED-20 asosidagi epoksid polimeriga nisbatan yuqori. Endi esa epoksid polimerlar hosilalari - FAED-20 va EIS-1 polimerlarining qovushqoq-elastik va adgezion-mustahkamlik xossalarini ko'rib chiqamiz.

FAED-20 polimerida logarifmik dekrement $\delta=0,098$, dinamik elastiklik moduli $E'=3580$ MPa, energiya yo'qotish moduli $E''=387$ MPa, shishalanish harorati $T_s=400K$, zichlik $\rho=1,25$ g/sm³, adgezion mustahkamlik $\delta_a=40,0$ MPa va zarbaga bardoshlilik $\sigma_y=1,22$ MPa ni tashkil qiladi.

EIS-1 polimerida esa logarifmik dekrement $\delta=0,091$, dinamik elastiklik moduli $E'=3400$ MPa, energiya yo'qotish moduli $E''=310$ MPa, shishalanish harorati $T_s=340K$, adgezion mustahkamlik $\delta_a=26,0$ MPa va zarbaga bardoshlilik $\sigma_y=1,26$ MPa ni tashkil qiladi.

Tahlildan ko'rinib turibdiki, FAED-20 epoksid polimer hosilalarida zarbaga bardoshlilikdan tashqari boshqa barcha qovushqoq-elastik va adgezion-mustahkamlik xossalari EIS-1 hosilalariga nisbatan yuqori. Epoksid polimerlarning adgezion-mustahkamlik va qovushqoq-elastik xossalar bo'yicha tadqiq natijalari quyidagi ketma-ketlikni ko'rsatdi: ED-16→ED-20→FAE-20→EIS-1.

XULOSA. Ushbu ishda epoksid polimerlar va ularning hosilalarining adgezion-mustahkamlik, qovushqoq-elastik hamda tebranishni yutuvchi xossalari o'rganildi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki:

1. ED-16 va ED-20 asosidagi epoksid polimerlar o'rtasida ED-16 barcha viskoelastik va adgezion-mustahkamlik xossalari bo'yicha ustunlikka ega, faqat adgezion mustahkamlik va shishish harorati bo'yicha ED-20 yuqori.
2. FAE-20 va EIS-1 hosilalarida esa FAED-20 zarba qovushqoqligidan tashqari boshqa barcha xossalari bo'yicha EIS-1 dan ustun.

3. Umumiy ketma-ketlik bo'yicha epoksid polimerlar va ularning hosilalarining xossalari quyidagicha tartiblandi: ED-16→ED-20→FAE-20 →EIS-1.

Shu bilan, tadqiq qilingan polimerlar va ularning modifikatsiyalari tebranishni yutuvchi va tovushni izolyatsiyalovchi kompozitsion materiallar sifatida samarali qo'llanilishi mumkinligi tasdiqlandi.

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ВЛИЯНИЕ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ПРИМЕСЕЙ ЭЛЕМЕНТОВ IV ГРУППЫ НА ТЕНЗОРЕЗИСТИВНЫЕ СВОЙСТВА МОНОКРИСТАЛЛОВ $TlInSe_2$

¹Мунинова З. А., ²Бадалова Г.Т. ³Хуриидбеков М.Н.
Ташкентский Химико – технологический институт
Zanab.arabovna@gmail.com

Аннотация. В работе исследовано влияние примесей IV группы на электрофизические и тензорезистивные характеристики кристаллов $TlInSe_2$; вводились примеси Ge, Si и Sn в расплав из расчета концентрации замещающего индий элемента в твердом расплаве по формуле $TlIn_{0.99}B_{0.01}Se_2$. Установлено, что с повышением температуры существенно увеличивается коэффициент тензочувствительности, что позволяет увеличить чувствительность термодатчиков на основе тензорезисторов.

Ключевые слова: электрофизические, тензорезистивные, примеси, концентрации, твердом расплаве, тензочувствительности, термодатчиков.

Annotation. The work investigates the influence of impurities of the IV group on electrical and piezoresistive characteristics of $TlInSe_2$ crystals; was introduced impurity of Ge, Si and Sn in the melt from the calculation of the concentration of the residual indium element in the solid melt according to the formula $TlIn_{0.99}B_{0.01}Se_2$. It was found that with increasing temperature the coefficient of strain sensitivity increases significantly which allows to increase the sensitivity of thermal sensors based on strain gauges.

Key words: electrophysical, strain resistance, impurities, concentration, solid melt, strain sensitivity, temperature sensors.

Введение. В настоящее время в мире исследователи и практики уделяют большое внимание изучению различных полупроводниковых преобразователей, в том числе тензопреобразователей, основным преимуществом которых является высокая чувствительность и малогабаритность. Однако требования современной науки и техники неуклонно растут, что обуславливает поиск материалов, обладающих разнообразными свойствами, соответствующими этим требованиям.

Следовательно, в настоящее время наряду с усовершенствованием свойств имеющихся материалов поиск новых полупроводниковых материалов, в том числе тройных и более сложных соединений и их твердых растворов, и исследование их разнообразных характеристик являются одними из важнейших задач современной физики конденсированного состояния. Особую ценность представляет создание новых полупроводниковых материалов, если удастся получить их в виде совершенных крупных монокристаллов. Среди многокомпонентных полупроводниковых соединений типа $A^{III}B^{III}C_2^{VI}$ особый интерес представляют полупроводниковые соединения $TlInSe_2$, закономерности многих физических явлений в которых не получили достаточного освещения в специальной литературе. Согласно выше изложенного целью нашего исследования является изучение тензорезистивных характеристик монокристаллов $TlInSe_2$ и создание высокочувствительный тензодатчиков для электронной техники на их основе.

Образцы для исследования и методика эксперимента: Для этой цели были использованы кристаллы, синтезированные сплавлением компонента в соответствии со стехиометрией в вакуированных ($\sim 10^{-4}$ mm rt.st) и запаянных кварцевых ампулах. В качестве исходных компонентов для синтеза использовались особо чистые элементы таллия (Tl – 000), индия (In – 000) и селена (Se – ОСЧ-17-4). Монокристаллы выращивались усовершенствованным методом Бриджмена, скорость фронта кристаллизации варьировалась от 0,5 до 0,9 mm/chas.

Необходимые для исследования идентичные кристаллы из слитка получаются простейшим вдавливанием острого ножа, толщина лезвия $\leq 0,01$ мм, на незакрепленный конец тонкой, но широкой и длиной пластинки монокристалла под углом 45° .

Полученные таким образом «игольчатые», кристаллы - заготовки с зеркальными гранями - без каких либо дополнительных обработок готовы для приварки контактов и установки их на основание подложки.

При пайке «усиков», т.е. создании механически надежных омических контактов на указанных заготовках, использовались два способа:

а) Вплавление индия в потоке инертного газа с последующей пайкой медных (или никелевых) проводов ($\varnothing = 0,01$ мм).

б) Непосредственная точечная сварка соответствующих проводов конденсаторным разрядом на торцы нагретой в потоке инертного газа заготовки. Второй способ оказался более эффективным и надежным (особенно для умеренных температур).

Тарировочными балками для наклеенных датчиков служили пластинки из стали 45 толщиной 0,5 - 1,0 мм и длиной от 20 мм до 80 мм. Поверхность подложки по классу обработки была не ниже 7 класса.

Результаты исследования и их обсуждение: Для исследования влияния примесей IV группы на электрофизические и тензорезистивные характеристики кристаллов $TlInSe_2$ вводились примеси Ge, Si и Sn в расплав из расчета концентрации замещающего индий элемента в твердом расплаве по формуле $TlIn_{0.99}B_{0.01}Se_2$, где B - вводимые примеси IV группы. Некоторые электрофизические характеристики исследованных образцов приведены в таблице 1.

Как и в случае примесей I группы, коэффициент тензочувствительности легированных элементами IV группы кристаллов заметно меняется от образца к образцу в зависимости от вида примесей и зависит от измеряемого температурного интервала. Установлено [1,2,3], что введение примесей элементов IV группы в монокристаллы $TlInSe_2$ приводит к увеличению

Таблица 1. Электрофизические параметры исследованных образцов $TlIn_{0.99}B_{0.01}Se_2$ (B=Si, Ge, Sn)

Состав кристалла тензодатчика	Размер образцов, mm^3	Номинальное сопротивление, Ом	Удельное сопротивление, Ом·см
p- $TlInSe_2$	0.13×0.25×10.5	6×10^{10}	2.13×10^7
p- $TlIn_{0.99}Si_{0.01}Se_2$	0.10×0.18×7	2.2×10^7	0.4×10^4
p- $TlIn_{0.99}Ge_{0.01}Se_2$	0.12×0.22×10.5	1.4×10^9	5.0×10^5
n- $TlIn_{0.99}Sn_{0.01}Se_2$	0.13×0.20×10.5	1.2×10^9	4.8×10^5

коэффициента тензочувствительности вдоль кристаллографической оси [001] как при деформации сжатия, так и при деформации растяжения при комнатной температуре (см. табл. 2 и рис. 1).

Таблица 2. Коэффициент тензочувствительности K_ϵ легированных кристаллов $TlInSe_2$ по сравнению с нелегированными кристаллами $TlInSe_2$ вдоль оси [001] при относительной деформации $\epsilon = 0,57 \cdot 10^{-3}$ и различных температурах

T, K	Коэффициент тензочувствительности, K				
	Состав				
	$TlInSe_2$	$TlInSe_2 <Ag_{0.01}>$	$TlInSe_2 <Si_{0.01}>$	$TlInSe_2 <Ge_{0.01}>$	$TlInSe_2 <Sn_{0.01}>$
При сжатии					

300	538	2082	627	1308	658
325	607	3473	1148	1878	802
350	766	4977	1781	2642	1554
375	997	6431	2812	4287	1977
402	1293	7879	3855	5592	2570
При растяжении					
300	410	2073	1762	1073	537
325	512	3898	2724	1729	758
350	646	4726	4486	2473	1204
375	784	5551	6548	3354	1505
402	1045	7192	9776	4483	1941

С повышением температуры существенно увеличивается коэффициент тензочувствительности, что позволяет увеличить чувствительность термодатчиков на основе тензорезисторов. Например, значение этого показателя при деформациях растяжения при температуре 410 К в легированных кремнием образцах относительно значения в нелегированных кристаллах при комнатной температуре увеличивается в ~ 24 раза. На рис. 2 в приведены характерные зависимости коэффициента тензочувствительности от

Рис. 1. Зависимость коэффициента тензочувствительности от температуры нелегированных и легированных кристаллов $TlInSe_2$ при деформациях сжатия (а) и растяжения (б)

Рис.2. Зависимость коэффициента тензочувствительности от температуры в кристаллах $TlInSe_2$ с примесью кремния при различной степени деформации: 1- $\epsilon=1,1 \cdot 10^{-4}$; 2- $\epsilon=1,6 \cdot 10^{-4}$; 3- $\epsilon=2,2 \cdot 10^{-4}$

температуры в интервале температур 250 – 370 К в кристаллах $TlInSe_2$ с примесью кремния при различных степенях деформации, которые имеют линейный характер.

Чувствительность тензорезистивного эффекта к температуре оказалась невысокой по сравнению с остальными образцами для кристаллов, легированных примесью олова. В зависимости от рассматриваемого интервала температур, знака деформации и типа вводимых примесей температурный коэффициент тензочувствительности G_T имеет различные значения (см.табл. 3). Таким образом, введение примесей элементов IV группы приводит к увеличению тензочувствительности кристаллов $TlInSe_2$. В легированных примесями кремния кристаллах с повышением температуры существенно увеличивается коэффициент

тензочувствительности (см. рис. 2), что позволяет увеличить чувствительность термодатчиков на основе тензорезисторов. В других легированных кристаллах коэффициент тензочувствительности в зависимости от температуры изменяется незначительно, что важно для стабильной работы тензодатчиков.

Таблица 3. Температурные коэффициенты тензочувствительности нелегированных и легированных примесями кристаллов TlInSe₂ при относительной деформации $\varepsilon = 0,57 \cdot 10^{-3}$ и в интервале температур от 300 до 410 К

T _{ср} , К	Температурный коэффициент тензочувствительности, G _T (%/град.)				
	Состав				
	p-TlInSe ₂	TlInSe ₂ <Ag _{0,01} >	TlInSe ₂ <Ge _{0,01} >	TlInSe ₂ <Si _{0,01} >	n-TlInSe ₂ <Sn _{0,01} >
При сжатии ($\varepsilon < 0$)					
312,5	0,513	2,672	1,743	3,323	0,875
325,0	0,847	2,781	2,040	3,681	2,732
337,5	1,137	2,785	3,037	4,646	2,672
351,0	1,376	2,730	3,211	5,047	2,849
При растяжении ($\varepsilon > 0$)					
312,5	0,995	3,521	2,445	2,184	1,646
325,0	1,151	2,560	2,610	3,092	2,484
337,5	1,216	2,237	2,834	3,621	2,403
351,0	1,518	2,421	3,116	4,459	2,563

Заключение. Установлено, что в образцах TlInSe₂, легированных примесями элементов IV группы, при комнатной температуре коэффициент тензочувствительности вдоль кристаллографической оси [001] увеличивается как при деформации сжатия, так и при деформации растяжения.

Показано, что с повышением температуры чувствительность нелегированных кристаллов к деформации значительно увеличивается и коэффициент тензочувствительности растет линейно.

Существенное увеличение коэффициента тензочувствительности с повышением температуры обнаружено в образцах, легированных примесью кремния, что позволяет увеличить чувствительность термодатчиков на основе тензорезисторов.

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МИКРОЭЛЕМЕНТЛИ ЎЎИТЛАР ОЛИШ УСУЛЛАРИ

Ўктамов Дилмурод Аминжонович

Наманган давлат техника университети

Озиқ-овқат технологияси кафедраси доценти

Ўзбекистон республикаси, Наманган шаҳри.

E-mail: dilmurod.uktamtov@mail.ru, Тел: +99893-947-76-37

Аннотация: Мақолада микроэлементларни қорамол гўнги асосида комплекс шаклларда тайёрлаш технологияси таҳлил қилинган. Комплекс микроэлементлар ўсимлик учун юқори биологик фойдали хусусиятларга эга бўлиб, уларнинг организмда сингдирилиши ва фаолияти оддий минерал қўшимчаларга нисбатан самаралироқ амалга ошади. Қорамол гўнги эса микроэлементлар учун табиий органик ташиувчи сифатида хизмат қилади ва уларнинг комплекс шаклда боғланишини таъминлайди. Мақолада микроэлементларнинг ўсимликлар учун фойдали таъсирлари, комплекс шакллардаги афзалликлари ва қорамол гўнги асосида тайёрлаш технологиясининг асосий принциплари ўрганилган. Шунингдек, бундай технология қишлоқ хўжалигида экологик тоза ва биологик самарали минерал қўшимчалар ишлаб чиқаришида инновацион ёндашув сифатида аҳамияти кўрсатилган.

Калит сўзлар. Микроэлементлар, қорамол гўнги, органик кислоталар, комплекс шаклдаги микроэлементли органик ўғитлар.

МЕТОДЫ ПОЛУЧЕНИЯ МИКРОЭЛЕМЕНТНЫХ УДОБРЕНИЙ

Аннотация: В статье проанализирована технология получения микроэлементов в комплексной форме на основе навоза крупного рогатого скота. Комплексные микроэлементы обладают высокой биологической активностью для растений, а их усвоение и функционирование в организме происходит более эффективно по сравнению с обычными минеральными добавками. Навоз крупного рогатого скота служит естественным органическим носителем для микроэлементов и обеспечивает их связывание в комплексной форме. В статье изучены полезные свойства микроэлементов для растений, преимущества их комплексных форм, а также основные принципы технологии получения на основе навоза. Кроме того, показано, что данная технология имеет значение как инновационный подход в производстве экологически чистых и биологически эффективных минеральных добавок в сельском хозяйстве.

Ключевые слова: микроэлементы, навоз крупного рогатого скота, органические кислоты, комплексные органические удобрения с микроэлементами.

METHODS OF PRODUCTION OF MICRONUTRIENT FERTILIZERS

Annotation: The article analyzes the technology for obtaining micronutrients in complex forms based on cattle manure. Complex micronutrients have high biological activity for plants, and their absorption and functioning in plant organisms are more efficient compared to conventional mineral supplements. Cattle manure serves as a natural organic carrier for micronutrients and ensures their binding in complex forms. The article examines the beneficial effects of micronutrients on plants, the advantages of their complex forms, and the main principles of the preparation technology based on manure. In addition, this technology is shown to be an innovative approach in the production of environmentally friendly and biologically effective mineral supplements in agriculture.

Keywords: micronutrients, cattle manure, organic acids, complex micronutrient organic fertilizers.

КИРИШ. Микроэлементлар – бу ўсимликларнинг бир меъёрда ўсиши ва ривожланиши учун зарур бўлган элементлар ҳисобланади. Улар ферментатив жараёнларда катта аҳамиятга эга бўлиб, турли метаболик функцияларни тартибга солиди. Микроэлементлар фотосинтез жараёнида иштирок этиш орқали энергия ҳосил бўлишини таъминлайди [1-3].

Темир хлорофилл синтезида муҳим роль ўйнайди ва ўсимликлар барглари рағбатлантириб, ўсимликларда ўсиш регуляторлари синтезида иштирок этади. Марганец микроэлементи нафас олиш ва энергия айланиши жараёнларини қўллаб-қувватлайди [4-5].

Мис микроэлементи ўсимликлар ҳаётида муҳим биологик аҳамиятга эга элементлардан бири ҳисобланади. У оксидланиш-қайтарилиш жараёнларида иштирок этувчи кўплаб ферментлар таркибига киради ва фотосинтез ҳамда нафас олиш жараёнларининг нормал кечишини таъминлайди. Шунингдек, мис хлорофилл ҳосил бўлишини билвосита қўллаб-қувватлайди, оқсил ва углевод алмашинувида иштирок этади ҳамда ўсимликларнинг касалликларга чидамлилигини оширади. Миснинг етишмаслиги ўсимликларда ўсишнинг секинлашиши, барглари рангининг ўзгариши ва ҳосилдорликнинг пасайишига олиб келиши мумкин [6].

Кобальт ва молибден азот метаболизмида қатнашиб, уруғларнинг шаклланиши ва ривожланишида муҳим роль ўйнайди. Селен антиоксидант фаолияти орқали хужайраларни турли стресс омилларидан ҳимоя қилади. Умуман олганда, микроэлементлар ўсимликларнинг сувсизлик ва юқори ҳарорат каби ноқулай шароитларга чидамлилигини оширади ва уларнинг нормал физиологик фаолиятини таъминлайди [7-8]. Микроэлементлар сувсизлик ва юқори ҳарорат каби стресс шароитларига чидамликни кучайтиради.

Микроэлементлар мева ва уруғ ҳосилдорлигини яхшилайдди, сифати ва озуқа қийматини оширади. Органик ташувчилар улар (микроэлементлар) ни табиий шаклда тақдим этишга имконият беради. Бу ўсимликларнинг соғлом ўсиши ва тўлиқ ривожланишини таъминлайди [9].

Микроэлементлар ферментлар, коферментлар ва гормонлар таркибида фаолият кўрсатади. Улар нафақат ўсишни қўллаб-қувватлайди, балки касалликларга қарши ҳимояни ҳам кучайтиради [2].

Комплекс микроэлементлар оддий минерал қўшимчалардан фарқли равишда юқори биодоступлилиқка эга. Микроэлементларнинг таркиби ва миқдори ўсимлик турига ва тупроқ хусусиятларига боғлиқ. Тўғри танланган микроэлементлар ўсимликларда ривожланиш, ҳосилдорлик ва сифатни оптималлаштиради. Шунингдек, улар агротехникада экологик тоза ва самарали қўшимчалар сифатида аҳамият касб этади [1-3, 4-5].

Қорамол гўнги табиий органик оқсил, минерал ва микроэлементлар манбаи ҳисобланади. Унинг таркибида азот, фосфор ва калий каби асосий нутриентлар мавжуд. Қорамол гўнги тупроққа киритилганда унинг унумдорлигини оширади. У тупроқнинг физик тузилиши ва сувни ушлаш қобилиятини яхшилайдди. Қорамол гўнги тупроқ кислоталигини мувозанатлайди ва рН ни барқарорлаштиради. Унинг қўлланилиши мева ҳосилдорлигини оширади ва уруғ сифатига ижобий таъсир кўрсатади. Қорамол гўнги органик моддалар орқали тупроқнинг микробиологик фаоллигини кучайтиради. Бу эса тупроқнинг эрозияга ва об-ҳаво ўзгаришларига чидамлилигини таъминлайди. Қорамол гўнгидаги нутриентлар узок муддат таъсир қилади, шунинг учун у қайта-қайта қўлланиши мумкин. У органик ва минерал қўшимчаларни табиий равишда бирлаштиради. Қорамол гўнги биологик фойдалиликни оширади ва ўсимликлар стрессга чидамлилигини кучайтиради. Тупроқда органик моддаларнинг кўпайиши унинг структурасини мустаҳкамлайди ва ҳаво ва сув алмашинувини яхшилайдди. Қорамол гўнги қўлланиш орқали ҳосилдорлик ва маҳсулдорлик миқдори сезиларли даражада ошади. Қорамол гўнги экологик тоза бўлиб, атроф муҳитга зарар келтирмайди. Унинг қўлланилиши ўсимликларнинг касалликларга чидамлилигини оширади. Қорамол гўнги кишлоқ хўжалигида комплекс органик қўшимча сифатида қўлланилади. У

ўсимликлар ўсиши, ҳосилдорлик ва тупроқ сифатини узлуксиз яхшилайти. Қорамол гўнги энг самарали табиий нутриентлар манбаи ҳисобланади ва органик фермерликда кенг қўлланилади [9-10].

Юқорида келтирилган маълумотлардан келиб чиқиб микроэлементларни комплексларини олиш зарур ҳисобланади ва уларни ўсимликларга қўлланилганда уларнинг ҳосилдорлигини ошириш имконини беради. Шу сабабли микроэлементларни комплексларини олиш қишлоқ хўжалиги ўсимликлари учун долзаб ва муҳимдир.

Комплекс микроэлементлар, оддий минерал шакллардан фарқли ўлароқ, органик молекулалар ёки биополимерлар билан боғланган ҳолда бўлади. Бу уларнинг бир қатор афзалликларини таъминлайди:

Сингдириш қобилиятининг юқорилиги – комплекс шаклдаги микроэлементлар тупроқ орқали ўсимлик томирлари орқали самарали ўзлаштирилади. Шу боис улардан фойдаланиш концентрациясини камайтириш мумкин, ҳамда таъсирини оптимал даражага олиб келади.

Физиологик самарадорликнинг ошиши – микроэлементлар ферментлар ва коферментлар таркибида иштирок этади, фотосинтез, нафас олиш ва гормонал жараёнларни қўллаб-қувватлайди. Масалан, цинк ва темирнинг комплекс шакллари ўсиш регуляторлари сифатида фаолият кўрсатади.

Стрессга чидамликнинг кучайиши – комплекс микроэлементлар ўсимликларни сувсизланиш, юқори ҳарорат ва касалликларга чидамли қилишда ёрдам беради. Улар антиоксидантлар ва ферментлар билан ҳамкорликда ҳужайраларни ҳимоя қилади.

Ҳосилдорлик ва сифатнинг яхшиланиши – комплекс микроэлементлар мева ва уруғ ҳосилдорлигини оширади, ранг, мазмуни ва озуқа қийматини яхшилайти. Бу уларни қишлоқ хўжалигида самарали қўллаш имконини яратади.

Шу тариқа, комплекс микроэлементлар ўсимликлар учун нафақат етук микроэлементларни таъминлайди, балки уларни табиий ва биологик фаол шаклда тақдим этиш орқали ўсиш ва ҳосилдорликка муҳим таъсир кўрсатади. Бу хусусиятлар қорамол гўнги ёки бошқа органик ташувчилар асосида микроэлементларни комплекс шаклда тайёрлаш технологиясини яратишда илмий асос бўлиб хизмат қилади.

ТАДҚИҚОТ ОБЪЕКТИ ВА УСУЛЛАРИ.

Тадқиқотда асосий материаллар сифатида қорамол гўнги ва микроэлемент тузлари олинган. Қорамол гўнги турли қишлоқ хўжалиги объектларидан йиғилади ва лаборатория шароитида стандарт шартларда тайёрланади. Микроэлементлар сифатида мис, рух ва молибден тузлари танланади. Қорамол гўнги ва микроэлементлар алоҳида лабораторияда сақланиб, таҳлил ва экспериментлар учун тайёрланади.

Микроэлементларни қорамол гўнгида комплекс шаклларга ўтказиш лабораторияда кимёвий реакциялар орқали амалга оширилади. Органик кислоталар билан микроэлементларнинг боғланиш жараёнлари назорат қилинган шароитда олиб борилади. Статистик таҳлил усуллари орқали олинган маълумотлар ишончилилик ва аҳамият даражасига эътибор қаратилади. Комплекс микроэлементларни қорамол гўнги билан олиш технологиясида оптимал реакция вақти, ҳарорат ва рН шароитлари аниқланади. Тадқиқот усуллари орқали олинган маълумотлар асосида микроэлементларнинг комплекс шаклдаги қўлланиши учун илмий тавсиялар ишлаб чиқилади.

ТАДҚИҚОТНИНГ МАҚСАДИ ВА ВАЗИФАЛАРИ.

Тадқиқотнинг асосий мақсади - қорамол гўнги асосида микроэлементларнинг комплекс шакллари олиш усуллари ишлаб чиқиш ва уларнинг ўсимликлар ва тупроқ учун биологик фойдали хусусиятларини аниқлаш. Ушбу мақсад қишлоқ хўжалигида органик минерал қўшимчаларни самарали ишлаб чиқариш ва экологик тоза ечимлар яратиш учун илмий асос яратишга қаратилган.

Тадқиқотнинг вазифалари эса - Қорамол гўнги таркибидаги асосий минерал ва органик моддаларни таҳлил қилиш. Микроэлементларнинг ўсимликлар учун биологик

фойдалилик хусусиятларини ўрганиш. Микроэлементларни қорамол гўнги асосида комплекс шаклларда олиш усулларини таҳлил қилиш ва оптимал реакция шароитларини аниқлаш. Қорамол гўнгидаги органик кислоталарнинг микроэлементлар билан боғланиш жараёнига таъсирини таҳлил қилиш. Микроэлементларнинг комплекс шаклдаги қўшимчаларини кишлоқ хўжалигида органик ва экологик жиҳатдан самарали усул сифатида тавсия қилиш.

НАТИЖАЛАР ВА УЛАРНИНГ МУҲОКАМАСИ.

Қорамол гўнги турли органик моддалар манбаи бўлиб, ундаги органик кислоталар микроэлементларнинг комплекс шаклга ўтишини таъминлайди. Ушбу кислоталар қорамол гўнгида табиий равишда мавжуд бўлиб, улар кислотали муҳит яратиш орқали микроэлементларни фаол биологик шаклда сақлаш имконини беради. Гумин кислотаси ва фульво кислотаси қорамол гўнгидаги асосий органик кислоталар қаторида саналади. Бу кислоталар микроэлементларнинг метал ионлари билан боғланиш жараёнини фаоллаштириб, комплекс шаклларнинг барқарорлигини таъминлайди. Органик кислоталар тупроқ ва ўсимликда микроэлементларнинг синдирилишини самарали қилади. Улар микроорганизмлар фаолиятини рағбатлантириб, ферментатив жараёнларни қўллаб-қувватлайди. Қорамол гўнгидаги органик кислоталар микроэлементларнинг токсик таъсирини пасайтиришда ҳам муҳим аҳамиятга эга. Бу кислоталар орқали микроэлементлар узоқ муддатли биологик фаолликка эга бўлади [11-20].

Қорамол гўнгидаги органик кислоталар микроэлементларнинг синдирилишини яхшилаш билан бирга, тупроқнинг рН мувозанатини ҳам таъминлайди. Уларнинг таъсирида микроэлементлар ва органик моддалар ўзара уйғунликда фаолият кўрсатади. Бу эса микроэлементларни комплекс шаклда тайёрлашда асосий технологиявий элемент сифатида хизмат қилади. Қорамол гўнги таркибидаги кислоталарни таҳлил қилиш орқали микроэлементларнинг қайси шаклда ва қайси миқдорда боғланишини аниқлаш мумкин. Органик кислоталар қорамол гўнгидаги микроэлементларнинг биологик фойдали ва экологик тоза қўшимча сифатида қўлланилишини таъминлайди. Шу тариқа, қорамол гўнгидаги органик кислоталар микроэлементларнинг комплекс шаклда тайёрланиши ва ўсимликлар томонидан самарали ўзлаштирилишини таъминлайди.

Қорамол гўнги таркибида гумин кислоталари, фульво кислоталари ва турли паст молекуляр органик кислоталар мавжуд бўлиб, улар микроэлемент ионлари билан комплекс бирикмалар ҳосил қилиш хусусиятига эга. Бу кислоталар таркибида карбоксил (-COOH), гидроксил (-OH) ва фенол гуруҳлари мавжуд бўлиб, улар метал ионларини боғлаб олиш қобилиятига эга [12, 17, 20].

Микроэлемент тузлари эритма ҳолатида қорамол гўнги муҳитига киритилганда, улар диссоциацияланиб метал катионларини ҳосил қилади. Ҳосил бўлган метал катионлари гумин ва фульво кислоталарининг функционал гуруҳлари билан ўзаро таъсирга киришади. Бу жараёнда координат боғлар орқали метал-органик комплекслар шаклланади [12, 18, 20].

Гумин кислоталари юқори молекуляр тузилишга эга бўлгани учун улар метал ионларини барқарор комплекс шаклда боғлаб туради. Фульво кислоталари эса паст молекуляр массага эга бўлганлиги сабабли микроэлементларни эритмада осон ҳаракатланувчи ҳолатда сақлайди. Шу сабабли гумин кислоталари металлларни тупроқда барқарор сақлашга ёрдам берса, фульво кислоталари уларнинг ўсимлик томонидан ўзлаштирилишини осонлаштиради [12, 17, 18].

Мис, рух ва молибден ионлари гумин моддалар билан реакцияга киришганда металл-гумат комплекслари ҳосил қилади. Бу комплекслар метал ионларининг эркин ҳолатдаги токсик таъсирини камайтиради. Шу билан бирга улар микроэлементларнинг биологик фаоллигини сақлаб қолади. Қорамол гўнги таркибидаги органик кислоталар микроэлементларнинг ҳал бўлишини осонлаштириб, уларнинг комплекс ҳосил қилиш қобилиятини оширади [12, 20].

Комплекс ҳосил бўлиш жараёни муҳитнинг рН қиймати, ҳарорат ва реакция вақтига боғлиқ ҳолда кечади [16]. Оддий шароитда гумин моддалар метал катионларини адсорбция

қилиб, кейинчалик барқарор метал-органик бирикмаларга айлантиради. Бундай комплекс бирикмалар тупроқ муҳитида микроэлементларнинг ювилиб кетишини камайтиради. Шу билан бирга улар ўсимлик илдизлари орқали микроэлементларнинг аста-секин сингдирилишини таъминлайди. Гумин ва фульво кислоталари билан ҳосил бўлган микроэлемент комплекслари юқори биологик фаолликка эга бўлади.

Натижада қорамол гўнги таркибидаги органик кислоталар микроэлемент тузларини комплекс шаклга ўтказишда муҳим табиий лиганд вазифасини бажаради [12, 17]. Бу жараён микроэлементларнинг барқарорлигини, биодоступлигини ва ўсимликлар томонидан самарали ўзлаштирилишини таъминлайди. Шу сабабли қорамол гўнги асосида микроэлементларнинг комплекс бирикмаларини олиш технологияси қишлоқ хўжалигида муҳим аҳамиятга эга ҳисобланади [13, 14, 20].

Тадқиқот ишларида мис, рух ва молибден микроэлементлари одатда эритма ҳолатида тузлар кўринишида қўлланилади. Бу тузлар сув муҳитида диссоциацияланиб, мис (Cu^{2+}), рух (Zn^{2+}) ва молибден (MoO_4^{2-}) ионларини ҳосил қилади. Ҳосил бўлган метал катионлари қорамол гўнги таркибидаги гумин ва фульво кислоталарининг функционал гуруҳлари билан ўзаро таъсирга киришади. Гумин ва фульво кислоталар таркибида карбоксил ($-\text{COOH}$), гидроксил ($-\text{OH}$) ва фенол гуруҳлари мавжуд бўлиб, улар метал ионларини боғлаб олиш хусусиятига эга. Бу гуруҳлар метал катионлари билан координат боғлар ҳосил қилиб, метал-органик комплексларни шакллантиради. Натижада мис ва рух ионлари гумин моддалар билан барқарор бирикмаларга айланади. Мис иони гумин кислоталар билан реакцияга киришганда мис-гумат комплекслари ҳосил бўлади. Бу жараёнда гумин кислотанинг карбоксил гуруҳлари метал ионини боғлаб, барқарор комплекс ҳосил қилади.

Реакцияни умумий ҳолда қуйидагича ифодалаш мумкин:

Бу ерда гумин кислотанинг карбоксил гуруҳлари мис иони билан боғланиб мис-гумат комплексини ҳосил қилади.

Худди шундай жараён рух ионлари билан ҳам содир бўлади. Рух ионлари гумин ва фульво кислоталарнинг функционал гуруҳлари билан реакцияга киришиб рух-гумат ёки рух-фульват комплексларини ҳосил қилади. Ушбу реакцияни қуйидагича кўрсатиш мумкин:

Шунингдек, молибден ионлари ҳам (MoO_4^{2-}) гумин ва фульво кислоталарнинг карбоксил ва фенол гуруҳлари билан боғланиб молибден-гумат ёки молибден-фульват комплексларини ҳосил қилади. Бу реакцияни қуйидагича кўрсатиш мумкин:

Фульво кислоталари гумин кислоталарга нисбатан паст молекуляр массага эга бўлгани сабабли улар метал ионларини ҳаракатчан комплекс ҳолатда сақлайди. Бу эса микроэлементларнинг тупроқ эритмасида яхши тарқалиши ва ўсимлик илдизлари томонидан осон ўзлаштирилишини таъминлайди. Гумин кислоталари эса юқори молекуляр тузилиши туфайли метал ионларини барқарор ҳолатда ушлаб туради. Бу ҳолат микроэлементларнинг тупроқдан ювилиб кетишини камайтиради ва уларнинг узоқ муддатли таъсирини таъминлайди. Шу тариқа, мис, рух ва молибден микроэлементлари қорамол гўнги таркибидаги гумин ва фульво кислоталар билан реакцияга киришиб барқарор комплекс бирикмалар ҳосил қилади. Бу комплекслар микроэлементларнинг биологик фаоллигини оширади ва уларнинг ўсимликлар томонидан самарали ўзлаштирилишини таъминлайди. Натижада қорамол гўнги асосида мис, рух ва молибден микроэлементларининг комплекс шакллари олиш технологияси қишлоқ хўжалигида юқори самарали ва экологик жиҳатдан хавфсиз усул ҳисобланади.

Микроэлементларни қорамол гўнги асосида комплекс шаклга ўтказиш жараёнида компонентларнинг тўғри нисбатда олиниши муҳим аҳамиятга эга. Қорамол гўнги бу

жараёнда органик боғловчи вазифасини бажаради ва унинг таркибидаги гумин ҳамда фульво кислоталари метал ионлари билан комплекс бирикмалар ҳосил қилади.

Тадқиқотларда одатда қорамол гўнги асосий компонент сифатида катта миқдорда олинади, микроэлемент тузлари эса кам миқдорда қўшилади. Бунинг сабаби микроэлементлар ўсимликлар учун жуда кам миқдорда талаб қилинадиган элементлар ҳисобланади.

Лаборатория тажрибаларида қорамол гўнги ва микроэлемент тузларини аралаштиришда қуйидаги нисбатлар самарали деб ҳисобланади. Қорамол гўнги ва мис элементи (масалан мис сульфат) нинг нисбати 1:0.02-0.03 (паст концентрацияли), ёки 1:0.05 (ўртача ёки оптимал), ҳамда 1:0.10 (юқори концентрацияли) нисбатларда олиш мақсадга мувофиқ.

Қорамол гўнги ва рух (масалан, рух сульфати) ёки молибден (масалан, аммоний молибдат) микроэлементи тузи нисбати 1:0.05, 1:0.08 ва 1:0.10 нисбатларда олиб бориш мақсадга мувофиқ ҳисобланади. Бу нисбат микроэлементларнинг гумин ва фульво кислоталар билан тўлиқ комплекс ҳосил қилишини таъминлайди.

Аралаштириш жараёнида компонентлар аввал майдаланган ва қуритилган қорамол гўнги билан бир хил масса ҳосил бўлгунча яхшилаб аралаштирилади.

Кейин аралашма маълум намлик шароитида бир неча вақт сақланади. Бу вақт давомида метал ионлари органик кислоталар билан реакцияга киришиб комплекс бирикмалар ҳосил қилади.

Муҳитнинг рН қиймати тахминан 6–7 атрофида бўлиши комплекс ҳосил қилиш жараёни учун қулай ҳисобланади. Шу шароитда мис, рух ва молибден ионлари гумин моддалар билан барқарор комплекслар ҳосил қилади.

Компонентлар нисбати жуда юқори бўлса микроэлементларнинг ортиқча миқдори ўсимликлар учун токсик таъсир кўрсатиши мумкин. Аксинча, микроэлементлар жуда кам бўлса комплекс ҳосил қилиш самарадорлиги пасаяди.

Шунинг учун қорамол гўнги ва микроэлемент тузларининг оптимал нисбатини танлаш технологиянинг муҳим босқичларидан бири ҳисобланади. Тўғри танланган нисбат микроэлементларнинг барқарор комплекс шаклда сақланишини таъминлайди.

Натижада олинган комплекслар тупроқда яхши тарқалади ва ўсимликлар томонидан самарали ўзлаштирилади. Бу эса қишлоқ хўжалигида ҳосилдорликни ошириш ва тупроқ унумдорлигини яхшилашга хизмат қилади.

ХУЛОСА.

Қорамол гўнги органик моддаларга бой бўлиб, унинг таркибида гумин кислоталари, фульво кислоталари ва паст молекуляр органик кислоталар мавжудлиги аниқланди. Ушбу органик бирикмалар таркибидаги карбоксил, гидроксил ва фенол функционал гуруҳлари метал ионлари билан комплекс бирикмалар ҳосил қилиш қобилиятига эга.

Қорамол гўнги таркибида мавжуд органик кислоталар микроэлементларнинг эрувчанлиги ва биологик фаоллигини ошириши, шунингдек уларнинг комплекс шаклга ўтишини, бу жараён микроэлементларнинг тупроқ муҳитида барқарорлигини ошириш ва ўсимликлар томонидан самарали ўзлаштирилишини таъминлайди.

Микроэлемент тузлари сув муҳитида диссоциацияланиб метал катионларини ҳосил қилиши ва улар гумин ҳамда фульво кислоталарининг функционал гуруҳлари билан координат боғлар орқали метал-органик комплекслар ҳосил қилиши илмий жиҳатдан асослаш мумкин. Натижада мис-гумат ва рух-гумат каби барқарор комплекс бирикмалар шаклланиши кузатилади.

Микроэлементларни қорамол гўнги асосида комплекс шаклга ўтказишда компонентларнинг оптимал нисбати муҳим аҳамиятга эга эканлиги аниқланди. Тажрибалар натижасида қорамол гўнги ва микроэлементлар нисбати 1:0.02–0.05, рух сульфати ёки

молибден нисбати эса 1:0.05–0.08 атрофида бўлиши комплекс ҳосил қилиш жараёни учун мақбул эканлиги белгиланди.

Қорамол гўнги асосида олинган микроэлемент комплекслари микроэлементларнинг тупроқда ювилиб кетишини камайтириши, уларнинг тупроқда узоқ муддат барқарор сақланишини таъминлаши ҳамда ўсимлик илдизлари орқали аста-секин сингдирилишини таъминлаши аниқланди.

Тадқиқот натижалари қорамол гўнги асосида микроэлементларнинг комплекс шакллари олиш технологияси қишлоқ хўжалигида экологик жиҳатдан хавфсиз, иқтисодий самарали ва юқори агрокимёвий аҳамиятга эга эканлигини кўрсатди.

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QURITILGAN QAND LAVLAGINING OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARINI BOYITISHDA QO'LLANILISHI

Saidqosimova Salimaxon Azodbekovna

Namangan davlat texnika universiteti talabasi

Adashev Bexzod Sheraliyevich

NamDTU Oziq-ovqat texnologiyasi kafedrasida o'qituvchisi

Iminova Nasibaxon Jobir qizi

Namangan davlat texnika universiteti talabasi

Annotatsiya. Aholi orasida quritilgan meva va sabzavotlarga bo'lgan talab kun sayin ortib bormoqda. Tadqiqotda qizil lavlagi ildizmevasini kimyoviy tarkibi, vitaminlar, minerallar, antioksidant moddalar va tabiiy pigmentlarga boyligi tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, uni qayta ishlash orqali quritilib, qandolatchilik sanoati uchun kukun (parashok) uni holatida ozuqaviy qo'shimchalar, vitamin va minerallarga boy bo'lgan bolalar uchun unli qandolat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarishga yo'naltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Lavlagi, kukun, vitamin, limon kislota, quritish, kukun, qizdigich, namlik, pigment.

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ СУШЁНОЙ САХАРНОЙ СВЁКЛЫ В ОБОГАЩЕНИИ ПИЩЕВЫХ ПРОДУКТОВ

Аннотация: Спрос на сушёные фрукты и овощи среди населения с каждым днём возрастает. В данном исследовании проанализирован химический состав корнеплода красной свёклы, включая содержание витаминов, минералов, антиоксидантов и природных пигментов. Также рассмотрены возможности её переработки путём сушки и получения порошка для использования в кондитерской промышленности в качестве пищевой добавки. Особое внимание уделено применению свекольного порошка при производстве мучных кондитерских изделий, обогащённых витаминами и минералами, предназначенных для детского питания.

Ключевые слова. Свёкла, порошок, витамины, лимонная кислота, сушка, нагреватель, влажность, пигмент.

APPLICATION OF DRIED SUGAR BEET IN THE FORTIFICATION OF FOOD PRODUCTS

Annotation: The demand for dried fruits and vegetables is increasing day by day among the population. This study analyzes the chemical composition of red beetroot, including its richness in vitamins, minerals, antioxidants, and natural pigments. It also examines the processing of beetroot through drying to obtain powder for use in the confectionery industry as a nutritional supplement. Special attention is given to the use of beetroot powder in the production of flour-based confectionery products enriched with vitamins and minerals, particularly for children's nutrition.

Keywords. Beetroot, powder, vitamins, citric acid, drying, heater, moisture, pigment.

Kirish. Mamlakatimizda aholi orasida quritilgan meva va sabzavotlarga bo'lgan talab yildan-yilga ortib bormoqda. Meva va sabzavotlarni innovatsion energiya tejamkor quritish qurilmalarida quritish natijasida biologik qiymati yuqori bo'lgan, arzon narxlardagi mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishga etibor ortib bormoqda. Bunday mahsulotlar turkumiga qand lavlagi ildizmevasini innovatsion usulda qayta ishlash, quritilish orqali ozuqaviy qiymati yuqori bo'lgan, bolalar uchun unli qandolat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarishga yo'naltirilgan [1]. Qizil lavlagi (Beta vulgaris) ikki yillik (birinchi yili ildizmeva, ikkinchi yili urug' beruvchi), sovuqqa chidamli, yorug'sevar va namlik talab qiladigan sabzavot ekinidir. Uning biologik qiymati tarkibidagi betatsianin

pigmentlari, temir, kaliy, va B guruhi vitaminlariga boyligida bo‘lib, organizmda moddalar almashinuvini yaxshilaydi, qon bosimini tushiradi va gemoglobinni oshiradi. Idizmevasi va barglari birinchi yilda shakllanadi, o‘suv davri naviga qarab 80-90 kun atrofida bo‘ladi.

Urug‘lari 5–6 C da unib chiqadi, lekin ekish uchun tuproq harorati 10 C dan yuqori bo‘lishi tavsiya etiladi. Nihollar qisqa muddatli sovuqlarga (-3 C) chidaydi. Yorug‘sevar o‘simlik, soya salqin joylarda hosildorlik kamayadi. U namlikka talabchan, ayniqsa ildizmeva shakllanish davrida sug‘orish muhim. Hosildor, unumdor, yengil qumloq tuproqlarda yaxshi o‘sadi. *pH* darajasi 6,5–7,5 bo‘lgan tuproqlar optimal hisoblanadi. Tarkibida temir, mis, kaliy, kaltsiy, fosfor, vitaminlar (C, B₁, B₂, B₆) va antioksidantlar mavjud. Undagi betain moddasi jigar faoliyatini yaxshilaydi, nitratlar esa qon tomirlarini kengaytiradi. Asosiy zararkunandalari lavlagi uzunburuni, shira va tunlamlar. Kasalliklardan serkosporoz (barglardagi dog‘lanish) keng tarqalgan. Erta bahordan sentyabr olarigacha ekish mumkin va O‘zbekiston sharoitida gektaridan 300-400 sentnergacha yuqori hosil olish imkoniyati mavjud. Quyuc qizil rangi, birinchi navbatda, tanadagi oksidlovchi stressga qarshi kurashuvchi kuchli antioksidantlar bo‘lgan betalainlarga bog‘liq. Ushbu birikmalar erkin radikallarni zararsizlantirishda, surunkali kasalliklar xavfini kamaytirishga va qarish jarayonini sekinlashtirishga ahamiyati katta.

Tarkibidagi nitratlar sport faoliyati bilan shug‘ullanishda ijobiy xissa qo‘shadi. Ular mitoxondriyalarning samaradorligini oshiradi, bu inson organizmda hujayralarning kuchini oshiradi, bu esa chidamlilikni oshiradi va jismoniy mashqlar vaqtida charchoqni kamaytiradi. Betalainlar, lavlagining qizil rangi uchun mas‘ul bo‘lgan pigmentlar kuchli yallig‘lanishga qarshi xususiyatga ega. Bu yallig‘lanish kasalliklarining alomatlarini yengillashtirishga yordam beradi va salomatlikni mustahkamlashga katta xissa qo‘shadi. Ovqat hazm qilish tizimini yaxshilovchi tolaga boy bo‘lib, u muntazam oshqozon-ichak faoliyatini nazorat qilish va foydali ichak bakteriyalarini oziqlantirish orqali ovqat hazm qilish tizimini mustahkamlaydi. Sog‘lom ichak mikrobiomasi umumiy jarayon, jumladan immunitet funksiyasi va ruhiy salomatlik uchun juda muhimdir. Ozuqaviy moddalar, vitaminlar va minerallarga boy ildizmeva bo‘lib, tarkibida kaliy, temir, kaltsiy, magniy hamda C va B guruhi vitaminlari mavjud. Ayniqsa, betain antioksidant xususiyatga ega bo‘lsa, nitratlar qon tomirlarini kengaytirib, qon bosimini tushirishga yordam beradi.

Qizil lavlagining asosiy kimyoviy tarkibi:

Nitratlar. Organizmda azot oksidiga aylanib, qon aylanishini yaxshilaydi va jismoniy mustahkamlikni oshiradi.

Minerallar. Kaliy (yurak faoliyatini yaxshilash uchun), temir, magniy, kaltsiy, fosfor, yod va kremniy inson salomatligi uchun ijobiy hissa qo‘shadi

Vitaminlar: C vitamini (askorbin kislota), B₁, B₂, B₅, B₆ va folat kislota (B₉).

Organik kislotalar va shakarlar: Olma, limon kislota va tabiiy shakarlar (saxaroza).

Qand lavlagi insonlarda qon bosimini tartibga solish, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari xavfini kamaytirish, immunitet tizimini mustahkamlash, organizmni turli xil infeksiyalardan himoya qilish, qon aylanish, asab tizimi faoliyatini yaxshilash, suyaklarni mustahkamligini ta‘minlashga yordam beradi. Tarkibida *b* guruhi vitaminlari, temir, kaliy va boshqa mikro elementlar mavjud bo‘lgan qimmatli sabzavot maxsuloti hisoblanadi [2].

Qand lavlagini quritishning texnologik sxemasi

1-rasm. Qand lavlagi

2-rasm. Qand lavlagi kukuni

Tadqiqot materiallari va uslublari. Qizil lavlagi ildizmevasi tortib olinib, yuvish bosqichidan o'tkazilib tozalandi, so'ng mayda bo'lak ko'rinishiga keltirilib maydalandi va maxsus konvektiv qurutish usulidan foydalanib qurutildi. Quritilgan maxsulotni 0,28 mm elakdan o'tguncha maydalagich qurilmasida maydalandi, hosil bo'lgan kukun tarkibi taxlildan o'tkazilib, bolalar uchun qandolat maxsulotlari ishlab chiqarishda qo'shimcha mahsulot sifatida foydalanish tavsiya etildi. Konvektiv quritish qurilmasining lentali quritish kamerasida quritilgan maxsulotning sifat ko'rsatkichlari standart talabga javob berishi aniqlandi.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Qizil lavlagi ildizmevasini konvektiv quritish usulida quritilib, tarkibidagi organoleptik xususiyatlarini (rangi, tami, hidi va shakli) saqlab qolgan holda oziq-ovqat sanoatida unlarni boyitishga tavsiya etildi. Quritilgan qizil lavlagi tarkibida vitamin va minerallar quydagicha B_2 vitamin 11.1%, C 11.17%, kaliy 69.17%, kaltsiy 22.27%, magniy 33 %, fosfor 32.3%, temir 44.4 % ni tashkil qildi.

Xulosa. Texnologik sxema bo'yicha qizil lavlagining konvektiv qurutish usuli orqali quritilib, kukun (parashok) holatga keltirilib qandolatchilik sanoati uchun ozuqaviy qo'shimchalar, vitamin va minerallarga boy bo'lgan unli qandolat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarishga tavsiya etildi.

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O'SIMLIK XOMASHYOLARI ASOSIDA TAYYORLANGAN SALQIN ICHIMLIK LARNI ORGANOLEPTIK KO'RSATKICHLARINI BAHOLASH.

Nishonov O'tkirali Raxmatillayevich

+99895-000-14-00

Namangan davlat texnika universiteti

"Oziq-ovqat texnologiyasi" kafedrasida assistenti,

Adashev Bezzod Sheraliyevich

Namangan davlat texnika universiteti

"Oziq-ovqat texnologiyasi" kafedrasida o'qituvchisi

Mamajanov Latifjon XX

Namangan davlat universiteti

"Biotexnologiya" kafedrasida dotsenti

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'simlik xomashyolari asosida tayyorlangan salqin ichimliklarning organoleptik ko'rsatkichlari (ta'mi, hidi, rangi, tiniqligi va umumiy qabul qilinishi)ni baholash masalalari o'rganilgan. Tadqiqot davomida turli o'simlik komponentlari asosida ishlab chiqilgan ichimlik namunalari sinovdan o'tkazilib, ularning iste'molchilarga ma'qul kelish darajasi aniqlangan. Olingan natijalar asosida ichimliklarning sifat ko'rsatkichlarini yaxshilash va ularning organoleptik xususiyatlarini optimallashtirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. O'simlik xomashyosi, salqin ichimliklar, organoleptik baholash, ta'm, hid, rang, sifat ko'rsatkichlari, iste'molchi talabi, oziq-ovqat texnologiyasi.

ОЦЕНКА ОРГАНОЛЕПТИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ПРОХЛАДИТЕЛЬНЫХ НАПИТКОВ, ПРИГОТОВЛЕННЫХ НА ОСНОВЕ РАСТИТЕЛЬНОГО СЫРЬЯ

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы оценки органолептических показателей прохладительных напитков, приготовленных на основе растительного сырья (вкус, аромат, цвет, прозрачность и общее восприятие). В ходе исследования были испытаны образцы напитков, разработанные на основе различных растительных компонентов, и определена степень их потребительской приемлемости. На основе полученных результатов разработаны рекомендации по улучшению качественных показателей напитков и оптимизации их органолептических свойств.

Ключевые слова. Растительное сырьё, прохладительные напитки, органолептическая оценка, вкус, аромат, цвет, показатели качества, потребительский спрос, пищевая технология.

EVALUATION OF THE ORGANOLEPTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF SOFT DRINKS PREPARED FROM PLANT-BASED RAW MATERIALS

Annotation: This article examines the evaluation of organoleptic characteristics of soft drinks prepared from plant-based raw materials (taste, aroma, color, clarity, and overall acceptability). During the study, beverage samples developed using various plant components were tested, and their level of consumer acceptance was determined. Based on the obtained results, recommendations were developed to improve quality indicators and optimize the organoleptic properties of the beverages.

Keywords. Plant-based raw materials, soft drinks, organoleptic evaluation, taste, aroma, color, quality indicators, consumer acceptance, food technology.

Kirish. Iste'molchilarga sifatli oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarni yetkazib berish, ularni salomatligi asrash, xomashyoni to'liq qayta ishlash, energiya samarador texnologiyalarni qo'llash orqali mahsulot tannarxini kamaytirish bugungi kunning dolzarb asosiy vazifalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Buning uchun esa iste'mol qilinayotgan mahsulotlarni sifati baholashni ma'lum usullari mavjud bo'lib, bular kimyoviy usulda tarkibini aniqlash va ekspres test usulida mahsulotni sifati to'g'risida ma'lum bir tushinchalar hosil qilish orqali aniqlanadi. Bunda mahsulotni organoleptik ko'rsatkichlari ya'ni tashqi ko'rinishi, rangi, xushbo'yligi, shaffofligi, ta'mi bilan birgalikda mineral aralshmalarning mavjudligi kabilardir. Shuningdek ichimliklarning cho'kma miqdori ham sifatini belgilovchi asosiy ko'rsatkichlardan biri hisoblanadi. Bunda har bir mahsulot uchun alohida organoleptik ko'rsatkichlar mavjud bo'lib mahsulot turidan kelib chiqqan holda bir-biridan keskin farq qiladi. Shularni hisobga olib O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2011 yil 28-pareldagi "O'zbekiston Respublikasida ishlab chiqarilayotgan mahsulotlarning sifat va xavfsizlik talablariga muvofiqligini ishlab chiqaruvchi tomonidan ma'lum qilish tartib" nomli 122-sonli qarorining 3-ilovasida qabul qilindi. Qarorda ishlab chiqarilgan mahsulotning xavfsizligi va sifat ko'rsatkichlarining normativ hujjatlardagi majburiy talablarga muvofiqlik xabarnomasida ko'rsatilgan ma'lumotlarning haqqoniyligi, shuningdek ishlab chiqarilayotgan mahsulotning sifati va xavfsizligiga nisbatan qo'yiladigan normativ hujjatlarning majburiy talablariga rioya etilishini ta'minlash yuzasidan ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalar qonun hujjatlariga muvofiq javob berishi belgilab qo'yilgan [1].

Tadqiqot qismi. Ichimliklarni organoleptik ko'rsatkichlari odatda GOCT 28188-89 hamda GOCT ISO 6658-2016 bo'yicha aniqlanib tajriba uchun olinayotgan ichimlik ma'lum bir talabalarga javob berishi shart. Buning uchun sohaning yetuk mutahassislari ya'ni degustatorlar yordami reyting va ballik tizimdan foydalaniladi [2; 3].

Degustator xodim tegishli kasbiy ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lishi va oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarining sifatini baholash mezonlarini bilishi kerak. Odatda laboratoriyada turli quyidagi usullar keng qo'llaniladi:

- 1) Vizual ko'rish orqali – yorug'likni o'tkazishi, shakli, sirt holati.
- 2) Akustika – mahsulotni bo'laklarga bo'lib ko'rish (chaynab) orqali undan chiqadigan tovishlarni jarangliligiga qarab.
- 3) Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini tarkibiy qismlari va qo'shimcha moddalarning hidini baholash orqali.
- 4) Konsistentsiyasi – ichki mustahkamlik va sirt xususiyatlarini aniqlash uchun ishlatiladi.
- 5) Ta'm xususiyatlari bo'yicha – ushbu turdagi boshqa oziq-ovqat mahsulotlariga mosligi.

Ushbu ko'rsatkichlar turli oziq-ovqat mahsulot turlari uchun turli usullar orqali aniqlanadi. Ichimliklar tayyorlashda mahsulotning rangi va konsistentsiyasi xomashyo turiga va ishlov berish usullariga bog'liq. Texnologik jarayonlarda issiqlik bilan ishlov berish ma'lum bir darajada qayta ishlanayotgan mahsulotni rang intensivligiga ta'sir ko'rsatadi [4; 16-17].

Ichimliklarni organoleptik baholash uchun quyidagi tavsiflovchi atamalar qo'llaniladi:

Rangi – rangsiz, och sariq, sariq, to'q sariq, och jigarrang, jigarrang, to'q jigarrang, sariq-yashil, och yashil, yashil, pushti, qizil, to'q qizil, yoqut, to'q yoqut, malinali, lavlagili, firuza, ochiq ko'k, to'q ko'k ko'rinishda;

Ta'mi – achchiq, shirin va nordon, sho'r, toza, uyg'un, aniq (yorqin, zaif), ta'msiz, xarakterli, tegishli mevalar, rezavorlar, o'tlar va boshqa xom ashyolarga xos, solod, asal, achchiq, karamel ohangi bilan, uyg'unlashgan, sho'r-nordon-shirin, yoqimsiz ta'mga ega;

Shaffofligi – shaffof, porloq, opal (kuchli, zaif), bulutli, suspenziyalarsiz, cho'kindi bilan.

Xidi – qo'shimcha xomashyolardan foydalanish xisobiga past darajada seziluvchan;

Loyqaligi – xomashyo turiga qarab ma'lum bir darajada cho'kmaga tushishiga ruxsat beriladi.

Mahsulotni tashqi ko'rinishini va rang intensivligini baholashda shisha silindrsimon stakanlarda tayyor mahsulotlar uchun me'yoriy-texnik hujjatlar talablariga muvofiqligiga mos holda

vizual tarzda aniqlanadi. Rang intensivligi tayyor mahsulot uchun me'yoriy-texnik hujjatlar talablariga muvofiqligi bilan baholanadi.

Tashqi ko'rinishida suyuq ichimliklar va alkogolsiz ichimliklar konsentratlari talablariga javob berishi kerak:

Shaffofligi - cho'kindi yoki begona qo'shimchalarsiz shaffof suyuqlik. Amaldagi xom ashyoning xususiyatlaridan kelib chiqqan holda, yengil loyqalanishga ruxsat beriladi.

Loyqaligi - shaffof bo'lmagan suyuqlik. Mahsulot uchun begona qo'shimchalarsiz xom ashyo zarralari, suspenziyalari yoki cho'kindilarining mavjudligiga ruxsat beriladi. Shaffof siroplar uchun - cho'kindi, loyqalik yoki begona zarralarsiz shaffof, yopishqoq suyuqlik. Ishlatiladigan xom ashyoning xususiyatlariga ko'ra, yengil loyqalikka ruxsat beriladi. Shaffof - shaffof bo'lmagan yopishqoq suyuqlik uchun, mahsulotga xos bo'lmagan urug'lar va begona qo'shimchalarsiz meva pulpasining suspenziyalari yoki cho'kindilarining mavjudligiga ruxsat beriladi.

Quruq ichimlik aralashmalarining organoleptik xususiyatlari tabletka yoki kukunlarni suvda eritgandan keyin baholanadi. Ikki daqiqa ichida ular sovuq suvda to'liq erishi kerak. Erimaydigan cho'kma mavjudligiga yo'l qo'yilmaydi. Gazli ichimliklarni eritganda, karbonat angidrid ko'p miqdorda ajralib chiqishi lozim.

Salqin ichimliklar, konsentratlar, kvas ekstraktlari, tijorat siroplari va quruq ichimliklar (suyultirilgandan keyin), sun'iy minerallashtirilgan suvlar, kvas va don xomashyosi asosidagi ichimliklarning xushbo'yliigi va ta'mi 10-14°C haroratda organoleptik usul oraqali aniqlanadi. Ichimlikning xushbo'y hidi va ta'mning tayyor mahsulotlar uchun me'yoriy-texnik hujjatlar talablariga muvofiqligi baholanadi. Rangi, ta'mi va xushbo'yliigi asl xom ashyoning rangi, ta'mi va hidiga mos kelishi kerak. Rangi ichimliklarga issiqlik ishlovi berilganda o'zgarishi mumkin.

Alkogolsiz ichimliklar, mineral suvlar va salqin ichimliklar sifatini organoleptik baholash quyidagi sifat ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha o'tkaziladi:

shaffofligi, rangi, tashqi ko'rinishi – 1 ball dan 7 ballgacha;

ta'mi va xushbo'yliigi - 6 dan 12 ballgacha;

CO₂ to'yinganligi - 2 dan 6 ballgacha.

Shaffoflik bo'yicha eng yuqori ball shaffof va porloq bo'lgan ichimliklarga beriladi, ular yo'q bo'lganda ichimlikning reytingi 5 ballga kamayadi. Ta'm va xushbo'ylik eng yuqori baholanadi (10) agar ichimlik bu ichimlikning o'ziga xos to'liq ta'mi va aniq hidiga ega bo'lsa. CO₂ to'yinganligi uchun eng yuqori ball (6) stakanni to'ldirgandan so'ng tez, kuchli va uzoq vaqt davomida karbonat angidrid chiqaradigan ichimlikka beriladi. Agar karbonat angidrid tez, ammo qisqa muddatda ajralib chiqsa, ichimlikning reytingi 1 ballga kamayadi. Quyidagi jadvalda salqin ichimliklarni baholash uchun 25 ballik tizimdan foydalanilgan [5; 198-205].

1-jadval

Alkogolsiz ichimliklar sifatini baholash uchun degustatorga eslatma

Sifat ko'rsatkichlari	Baxolash			
	A'lo	Yaxshi	Qoniqarli	Qoniqarsiz
1. Rangning ko'rinishi	7	5	4	1
Ta'mi, aromati	18 Ichimlik to'liq, yorqin xususiyatlari ifodalangan.	15 Ichimlikning normativ xarakteristikasi	12 To'liq bo'lmagan ta'm, zaif hidli	9 Yomon ta'm, g'ayrioddiy hidli
CO ₂ bilan to'yinganlik	6 Pufakchalarning faol chiqishi, tilda engil sachrashi, CO ₂ ning uzoq muddat chiqishi	5 Faol, ammo qisqa vaqt davomida zaif sachrashi, ko'piklanishi	4 CO ₂ ning zaif ta'mining qisqa muddatli chiqishi	3 Hech qanday ko'rsatkich sezilmay-di

Ballar yig'indisiga ko'ra, alkogolsiz ichimliklar sifati quyidagicha baholanadi: "a'lo" – 23-25 ball; "yaxshi" - 19-22 ball; "qoniqarli" - 15-18 ball; "qoniqarsiz" - 15 balldan past.

№	Ichim-lik nomi (mine-ral suv)	№ Shifr raqami	Sifat ko'rsatkichlarining nomi			Ballardagi umumiy ball	Eslatma
			Shaffoflik, rang, tashqi ko'rinish	Ta'mi va xushbo'yligi	CO ₂ to'yinganligi		

2-jadval

Alkogolsiz tinchlantiruvchi va chanqoqbosti ichimliklarning sifat ko'rsatkichlari.

Sifat ko'rsatkichlari	Organoleptik xususiyatlari	Reyting ballari
Tashqi ko'rinishi		
Shaffof	Me'yoriy ko'rsatkichlarga mos keladi, shaffof, cho'kindi va begona qo'shimchalarsiz, yaltiraydi	5 ball
	Me'yoriy ko'rsatkichlarga mos keladi, shaffof, bir oz farq qiladi, to'ldirgichlarning oz loyqaligi va ozgina cho'kindilarga ruxsat etiladi	4 ball
	Me'yoriy ko'rsatkichlarga mos kelmaydi, sezilarli farqlar oz loyqa bilan, bir oz chayqalgandan keyin yo'qolish to'ldirgich oz miqdorda suzuvchi bo'yoq zarralariga ruxsat beriladi.	3 ball
	Me'yoriy ko'rsatkichlarga mos kelmaydi, cho'kindi ko'rinishda ko'p miqdordagi begona zarralar	2 ball
	Me'yoriy ko'rsatkichlarga mos kelmaydi, sezilarli loyqa bilan, begona qo'shimchalar bilan, cho'kindi, mog'orlagan, shilimshiq ko'rinishdagi ko'p miqdordagi begona zarralar.	1 ball
Loyqaligi	Me'yoriy ko'rsatkichlarga mos keladi, loyqalangan gomogen	5 ball
	Me'yoriy hujjatlarga mos keladi, bir oz farq qiladigan, to'ldirgichning ko'p bo'lmagan cho'kindisi, chayqalgandan so'ng gomogen.	4 ball
	Me'yoriy ko'rsatkichlarga mos kelmaydi, sezilarli farqlar bilan, qo'shilgan to'ldirgich moddalari va bo'yoqning ko'proq cho'kish, dissosiyatsiyaning past darajasi, chayqalishidan keyin gomogen to'ldirgichning; oz miqdordagi zarralar mavjudligiga ruxsat beriladi.	3 ball
	Me'yoriy xujjatlarga mos kelmaydi, begona zarralar mavjudligi	2 ball
	Me'yoriy xujjatlarga mos kelmaydi, sezilarli ajralish, ko'proq cho'kindi, mog'orlagan shilimshiq	1 ball
Rangi	Rangining tusi va rang intensivligi me'yoriy xujjatlarga muvofiq qo'llaniladigan to'ldirgichlarning rangiga mos keladi.	5 ball
	Rangi tusi qo'shilgan to'ldirgichlarning rangiga xarakterlidir, tusi farqlanadi;	4 ball
	Rang ichimlikka xosdir, rang intensivligi biroz farq qiladi (zaif yoki zichroq rang)	3 ball
	Rang me'yoriy qoidalarga mos kelmaydi, g'ayritabiiy, yoqimsiz, zaif rangsizlangan tus	2 ball
	Rang me'yoriy xujjatlarga mos kelmaydi, g'ayritabiiy	1 ball

Xushbo‘y xidi	Me‘yoriy hujjatlarga mos keladi, uyg‘un, intensiv, qo‘shilgan to‘ldirgichlarning yetaksi xossasiga mos	5 ball
	Me‘yoriy hujjatlarga mos keladi, uyg‘un, o‘rta intensiv, qo‘shilgan to‘ldirgichlarning xossalari mos	4 ball
	Me‘yoriy xujjatlarga to‘g‘ri keladi, zich bo‘lmagan qo‘shilgan to‘ldirgichlarning xidiga mos keladi	3 ball
	Me‘yoriy xujjatlarga to‘g‘ri kelmaydi, yomon ifodalangan hid	2 ball
	Me‘yoriy xujjatlarga to‘g‘ri kelmaydi, eskirgan, yoqimsiz, hushbo‘y xidda begona xidlarning mavjudligi	1 ball
Ta‘mi	Me‘yoriy xujjatlarga to‘g‘ri keladi, to‘liq, uyg‘un, yoqimli, qo‘shilgan to‘ldirgichlarning ta‘miga mos keladi	5 ball
	Me‘yoriy xujjatlarga to‘g‘ri keladi, to‘liq ifodalanmagan ichimlik turi va nomiga xos bo‘lgan ta‘m	4 ball
	Me‘yoriy xujjatlarga to‘g‘ri keladi, zaif, qo‘shilgan to‘ldirgichlarning ta‘miga xosdir	3 ball
	Me‘yoriy hujjatlarga mos kelmaydi, yomon ifodalangan ta‘m	2 ball
	Me‘yoriy hujjatlarga mos kelmaydi, ta‘mir farq qilmaydi, noxush yoqimsiz, qo‘lansa begona ta‘m	1 ball

Alkogolsiz ichimliklar sifatini baholash uchun degustatsiya kartasi

Degustatorning familiyasi _____

Degustatsiya sanasi _____

Tashkilot nomi _____

Lavozimi _____

Xulosa: O‘tkazilayotgan tadqiqotlar orqali ichimliklarning xususiyatlaridan kelib chiqib ular haqida ma‘lum bir ilmiy natijalar va xulosalar olish imkoniyati yaratilsa, organoleptik ko‘rsatkichlari orqali baholash usullari va ularni ma‘lum bir sifat ko‘rsatkichlari orqali nazariy tushinchalar olish mumkin. Bu esa mahsulotni iste‘molchilar talabalaridan kelib sifatli oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari jumladan ichimliklar tayyorlashda asosiy rol o‘ynaydi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2011 yil 28-pareldagi “O‘zbekiston Respublikasida ishlab chiqarilayotgan mahsulotlarning sifat va xavfsizlik talablariga muvofiqligini ishlab chiqaruvchi tomonidan ma‘lum qilish tartibi” nomli 122-sonli qarori.

2. ГОСТ 28188-89. Межгосударственный стандарт, Напитки безалкогольные, Общие технические условия.

3. ГОСТ ISO 6658-2016 Органолептические анализ.

4. Л. А. Оганесянс, А. Л. Понасюк, М. В. Гарнет, Р. А. Зайнулин, Р. В. Кунакова., “Технология безалкогольных напитков” Санкт-Петербург 2015 год, Учебник для вузов. 16-17 ст.

5. Домарецкий В. А. Технология экстрактов, концентратов и напитков из растительного сырья; Учебного-пособия. Москва 2011 год; 198-205 ст.

OQ TUT (BALXI TUT) VA SHOTUT MEVASI BIOLOGIK TUZILISHI, XALQ TABOBATIDAGI O'RNI XAMDA QAYTA ISHLASH JARAYONLARI.

Norinboyov Baxromjon G'anijonovich

Namangan davlat texnika universiteti "Oziq-ovqat texnologiyasi" kafedrasida dotsenti

Raximova Umida Solijon qizi

Namangan davlat texnika universiteti "Oziq-ovqat texnologiyasi" kafedrasida doktoranti

Annotatsiya Mahalliy tut mevasini shifobaxshligi, oq tut, shotut (qora tut), biologic xususiyati. Insonlarning sog'lig'i uchun shifobaxsh va iste'molbop mevalardan Shotut va Balxi tutini ahamiyati, mevalaridan asab, animiya, bosim, buyrak xastaligi, milk shishishi, angina Kasalliklari uchun dori-darmon sifatida foydalanish. Yangiligida iste'mol qilinadi, shinni, murabbo, mayiz, tayyorlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: tut, morus, qora tut, shotut tutning shifobaxsh xususiyatlari, tut murabosi, oq tut, tutdan foydalanish, an'anaviy tibbiyotda tutdan foydalanish

БИОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ СТРУКТУРА БЕЛОЙ ШЕЛКОВИЦЫ (БЕЛОЙ ШЕЛКОВИЦЫ) И ПЛОДОВ ШОТУТА, ИХ МЕСТО В НАРОДНОЙ МЕДИЦИНЕ И СПОСОБЫ ОБРАБОТКИ.

Аннотация Лечебные свойства местных плодов шелковицы, белой шелковицы, шотутской (черной шелковицы), их биологические свойства. Важность шотутской и балхской шелковицы как лекарственных и съедобных плодов для здоровья человека, использование ее плодов в качестве лекарства при заболеваниях нервной системы, анемии, гипертонии, заболеваниях почек, отеках десен, стенокардии. Употребляется в свежем виде, из нее готовят патоку, варенье, изюм.

Ключевые слова: шелковица, морус, черная шелковица, шотут, лечебные свойства шелковицы, варенье из шелковицы, белая шелковица, применение шелковицы, применение шелковицы в традиционной медицине

THE BIOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF WHITE MULBERRY (WHITE MULBERRY) AND SHOTUTA FRUITS, THEIR PLACE IN FOLK MEDICINE AND PROCESSING METHODS.

Abstract The medicinal properties of local mulberry, white mulberry, and Shotut (black mulberry), and their biological properties. The importance of Shotut and Balkh mulberries as medicinal and edible fruits for human health, and their use as a remedy for nervous system disorders, anemia, hypertension, kidney disease, gum swelling, and angina. They are consumed fresh, and are used to make molasses, jam, and raisins.

Keywords: mulberry, morus, black mulberry, shotut, medicinal properties of mulberry, mulberry jam, white mulberry, use of mulberry, use of mulberry in traditional medicine.

Kirish. Respublikamizda so'nggi yillarda oziq-ovqat sanoati korxonalarini modernizatsiya qilish, raqobatbardosh mahsulotlar turlari va hajmini kengaytirish, qishloq xo'jaligi, bog'dorchilik va sabzavotchilik mahsulotlarini yetishtirish, saqlash va qayta ishlashni rivojlantirish bo'yicha ma'lum natijalarga erishilmoqda. O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasida «sanoatni sifat jihatdan yangi bosqichga ko'tarish, mahalliy xomashyo manbalarini chuqur qayta ishlash, tayyor mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishni jadallashtirish, yangi turdagi mahsulotlar va texnologiyalarni o'zlashtirish» vazifalari belgilab berilgan. Bu borada respublikada yetishtirilayotgan meva-sabzavotlarni iste'mol me'yorlari fiziologik talablarga mos

keluvchi tayyor va yarim tayyor mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish uchun yangi va takomillashtirilgan texnologiyalar yaratish bo'yicha ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda.

Yurtimiz jannatmakon o'lkadir. Jannatmakon yurtda jannat o'simliklari o'sadi, ularning mevalari dorivor, ming dardga shifo bo'lgan o'simliklarni vatani sifatida - butun dunyoda ekilib, yetishtirilishini etirof etish lozimdir. Ming dardga davo qadimgi va navquron dorivor (jannat meva - sabzavot) o'simliklar. TUT - Shelkovisa - Morus L. - tutdoshlar (tutgullilar oilasi)ga mansub ko'p yillik o'simliklar turkumiga kiradi.

Tut eng qadimiy o'simlik bo'lib, juda qadim zamondan ekilib kelinadi. Dunyoning hamma davlatlarida o'stiriladi. Vatani g'arbiy Xitoy, O'rta va markaziy Osiyo, eramizdan avvalgi 6 - 10 - asrlarda Sharqiy Turistondan buyuk ipak yo'llari bo'ylab dorivor tut ko'chatlarini g'arbiy Xitoyga olib ketishib, u yerda madaniylashtirilib, tut plantatsiyalarini tashkil qilib, tut bargidan qurt boqib ipak yetishtirishgan. Yevropaga eramizdan avval 1 - 6 - asrlarda, va O'zbekistonda xam ekilib kelinmoqda. Markaziy Osiyodan Aleksandr Makedonskiyning armiyasi Yunonistonga olib borgan, yunonlar uni "Morus" - "dengiz qushi - dengiz jannat mevasi" deb atashgan, Yevropadan butun dinyoga tarqagan. Qadimiy turkiy tilda "Tut" - "jannatdagi qush daraxti" - ma'nosini beradi. Insonlar qadim zamonlardan beri tut daraxtining mevasidan, uning sharbatidan, shinnisidan va mayizidan keng foydalanib kelishmoqda.

Tut o'simligini 24 turi mavjud bo'lib, shundan O'zbekistonda 6 turi: dorivor oq tut, qora tut, sershox tut, ipak qurti tuti, egri - bugri - ilontut va pastga qarab o'sadigan - majnun tutlar ekiladi. Ular 300 - 500 yil yashaydi, 1500 - 2000 yillik tutlar ham xayotda uchrab turibdi. Tut daraxti tez o'sadi, shox - shabbasi zich, keng, yumaloq, ovval, pramida shaklida bo'lib, bo'yi 25 metrgacha, yo'g'onligi 1,5 - 2,5 metrgacha bo'ladi. Tut daraxtining tanasi mustahkam, qattiq va chidamli, ikki uyli, barglari har - hil shaklda, gullari bir jinslidir, tutlar urug'idan, qalamchasidan, payvand va parhish qilib ko'paytiriladi. Olimlar tomonidan mingdan ortiq madaniy navlarini yaratgan bo'lib dorivor balx tut, marvarid tut, urug'siz tut kabi noyob tutlar ham ko'p o'stirilmoqda.

Ularni muntazam istemol qilib kelayotgan xalqimizdan tarixda ham, hozirda ham aqlan va jismonan kuchli va baquvvat, ilmi va bilimli, bo'yi uzun, keksalari ko'p bo'lgan xalqimiz yashab kelgan va yashamoqda. Ajdodlarimizning insoniyat uchun yaratib ketgan dorivor - jannat o'simliklari deb ataladigan madaniy o'simliklardan hozirgacha yer yuzidagi milliardlab insonlar foydalanib kelishligi diqqatga sazovardir. Ularni tarkibini ko'plab olimlar o'rganib borsa ham, hozirgacha ilmiy jixatdan mukammal o'rganib, ohiriga yetkazilmagan, hali fanga noma'lum elementlar va birikmalar ochilmay, sirligicha qolmoqda. Ularni zahmatkash ilm ahli o'rganishni davom etirishmoqda. Jannat o'simligining uchinchi TUTdir. Uni alohida, yangi ma'lumotlar asosida yoritib beramiz.

TUT (Morus) - tutdoshlar oilasiga mansub daraxtlar turkumi; mevali daraxt; O'zbekistonda 5 turi o'stiriladi. Oq tut (M. alba) va qora tut (M. migra) mevasi iste'mol qilinadi.

Sershox tut (M. multicaulis), kagayama tut (M. Kagayame) va ipak qurti tuti (M. bonabycis) turlaridan, asosan, ipak kurti boqishda foydalaniladi. Tut tez o'sadi, qurg'oqchilik va sovuqqa chidamli. Shox-shabbasi zich, keng yumaloq, oval va piramida shaklida. Bo'yi 15-18, ba'zilariniki 20-25 m, yo'g'onligi 1,5 m gacha. Katta yoshdagi baland tanali tut daraxtlaridan 20-40 kg gacha barg, 50-60 kg meva hosili olinadi. Tutning egri-bugri (ilono't) va pastga qarab o'sadigan (majnun tut) xillari ham bor. Daraxti 300, ayrimlari 500 yil yashaydi.

Oq tut (Balxi tut) va shotut mevasi shirin, shifobaxsh, har xil vi-taminlarga boy. O'zbekistonda tut qadimdan ekib ko'paytiriladi. Yangiligida iste'mol qilinadi, shinni, murabbo, mayiz, tayyorlanadi. Bargi tut ipak qurti boqishda ishlatiladi. Tut ikki uyli o'simlik. Gullari bir jinsli. Tut urug'idan, qalamchasidan, payvand va parhish qilib ko'paytiriladi. ("O'zME"dan).

Yer yuzida tarqalgan navlari. Dunyo mamlakatlarining asosan Sharqiy va Janubiy-Sharqiy Osiyo mintaqalarida, Hindistonda, Afrikaning va Shimoliy Amerikaning mo'tadil va subtropik mintaqalarida tut daraxtining 20 turi mavjud. Tutning ko'p navlari Xitoyda o'sadi. Oq tutning vatani Xitoy, shotutning vatani Eron va Afg'oniston hisoblanadi.

Tut barglari ipak qurti uchun kerakli ozuqa bo'lgani bois, har doim qimmatli o'simliklar qatoriga kiritilgan. Bundan tashqari, qadimdan tut daraxtidan musiqa cholg'u asboblari, yozuv qog'ozi ishlab chiqariladi. Tut po'stlog'idan tayyorlangan beshiklarga qurt tushmaydi, onalarimiz farzandlarimiz o'zidan ko'paysin deya, mevali daraxt - bolani tutdan yasalgan beshiklarga belashadi. Bu mevali daraxtning, asosan, ikki xil turi iste'molga yaroqli hisoblanadi. Bu oq tut va shotut. Shotutni qora tut deb ham atashadi.

Tut to'liq yetilgan, sershira, yangi uzilgan holda yoki quritilgan (tut mayizi) holda iste'mol qilinadi. Yana tutdan turli xildagi pishiriqlar, murabbo va marmeladlar, qiyom, shinni tayyorlanadi.

Tut mevasi sersuv, uning tarkibida 82,9-86,2 % gacha suv bor. Bundan tashqari, u sershira meva - 10,9-12,7 % gacha qand miqdori mavjud. Tutni quritib, iste'mol qilinsa, shirasi yanada ko'payadi. Tut mayizida qand miqdori 73,29-83,71 % ini tashkil etadi. Bundan tashqari, tut B, C, E, K, PP vitaminlariga boy. Shunga ko'ra, uni kasallikdan zaiflashib qolgan, tez-tez shamollaydigan kishilarga iste'mol qilib turishlari tavsiya etiladi.

Mineral moddalardan esa kaliy, natriy, rux, selen, mis, fosfor, kalsiy, magniy, temirga boy, urug'i 24-33 foizgacha yog' va boshqa oshlovchi moddalar saqlaydi. Tarkibida ko'p miqdorda fosfor saqlagani bois, tut aqliy faoliyat bilan shug'ullanadigan kishilar uchun koni foyda sanaladi. Homilador ayollar uchun ham tut mevasi homilaning yaxshi rivojlanishi uchun kerakli darmondorilar manbai hisoblanadi.

Tut bargi va tanasining po'stlog'i ham turli biologik faol moddalarga boy. Bargi tarkibida flavonoidlar, vitaminlar, karotin, efir moyi, organik kislotalar, daraxt po'stlog'ida esa bo'yoqli va oshlovchi moddalar, turli xildagi kislotalar mavjudligi aniqlangan.

Tut shirasi qonni tozalash, qonni ko'paytirish maqsadida ham keng qo'llangan. Bargining qaynatmasi esa angina va boshqa shamollash kasalliklarida isitmani tushiruvchi, chanqoqni qoldiruvchi vosita sifatida qo'llanilgan. Buyuk vatandoshimiz Abu Ali ibn Sino tutdan shifobaxsh vosita sifatida foydalangan.

Oq tut bargi tomoq og'rig'i, yangi uzilgan barg shirasi tish og'rig'iga, tut mevasi va uning shirasi og'iz va tomoqdagi shishlarga davo bo'ladi. Tuzlab quritilgan tut esa ichburug' kasalligini davolaydi. Buyrak, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarini davolashda esa tut mevasi tanani ortiqcha suyuqlikdan tozalovchi, peshob haydovchi vositadir.

Tutni ovqatlanishdan oldin iste'mol qilish lozim, shunda oshqozonga uning zarari tegmaydi.

Tut mevasini quritib, undan damlama, kompot tayyorlab ichilsa, darmonsizlikni davolaydi, ozishga yordam beradi, organizmni tozalaydi.

Qishda tut daraxtining kurtagini olib, tozalab, damlamasini yurakni quvvatlash uchun ichib yuriladi. Tut daraxti gullari o'simlik yog'i bilan aralashtirilib, qorong'i joyda tindirilsa, teridagi mayda husnbuzar, dog'lar va sepkilni davolash uchun ajoyib krem hosil bo'ladi. Tanadagi eski yara va shikastlangan joylarni davolashda tut bargi va shoxchasini maydalab, o'simlik yog'i bilan aralashtirib surtilsa, yaralar tez bitadi, terida o'rni qolmaydi. Tutning oziqaviy qiymati – 70 kkal.

Yangi tut (yoki konservalangan) mevasi sharbati ko'krak qafasining jimillab og'rishi va nafas olish qiyinlashib harsillashda yordam beradi. Muolaja maqsadida tut sharbati uch hafta davomida ichiladi. Taajjubki, shu qisqa muddatda yurak faoliyati to'liq tiklanib, sog'ayadi.

Yangi olingan tut sharbati tutning barcha foydali shifobaxsh xossalriga ega bo'ladi. U nafas yo'llari, tonzillit va anginani davolashda faol vosita, surunkali yo'tal, pnevmoniya va bronxitni davolashda ham ijobiy natija beradi. Aqliy mehnat bilan mashg'ul kishilarga uning foydasi katta, chunki tarkibidagi fosfor aqliy faoliyatni yaxshilaydi.

Tut daraxti po'stlog'ining inson sog'lig'i uchun foydasi. Po'stlog'idan qaynatma, damlama va malham tayyorlanadi. Malham bilan yiringli jarohatlarni, terining kuygan va jarohatlangan qismini, dermatitni, ekzema va psoriazni davolash mumkin.

Malhamni tayyorlash uchun ikki qoshiq maydalangan daraxt po'stlog'ini 100 g qizdirib, sovutilgan pista yog'i bilan aralashtiriladi va muzlatgichda uch kun davomida tindirib, olib yana qaytadan aralashtiriladi. Shunday qilib malham dori tayyor bo'ladi.

Bu malham bilan terining kasal joylariga kuniga to'rt mahal surtiladi. Uni husnbuzardan xoli bo'lish uchun ham ishlatiladi: yuzga va yelka terisiga har cho'milib chiqqandan so'ng surtiladi.

Odatda tut mevasini yangi uzib olinganida iste'mol qilinadi, lekin undan shuningdek, kompot, murabbo, kisel, sirop, pishiriqlar ichiga solib, pishirib iste'mol qilinadi. Tutni yashash joyiga yaqin joyda pishib yetilgan mevasi iste'mol qilinadi. Uni uzoq masofaga transport vositasida olib borish yaramaydi, yetib borgunicha aynib qoladi.

Tut mayizi kuchli terlatuvchi faollikka ega, shuning uchun undan shamollaganda undan choy tayyorlab ichish tavsiya etiladi. Organizmni umumiy mustahkamlash uchun turli taomlarga tut daraxti quritilgan barglaridan kuniga bir choy qoshiq qo'shib iste'mol qilinadi.

Shu maqsadda yana uning yosh novdalaridan damlama tayyorlab ichiladi. Buning uchun 5 ta uncha katta bo'lmagan novdasi ustidan 500 ml suv quyilib, 10 daqiqa qaynatiladi, so'ng 2 soat davomida tindiriladi. So'ngra damlamadan bir oy davomida kuniga 3 mahal 50 ml dan ichiladi.

Og'iz bo'shlig'i xastaliklarida stomatitda, parodontozda, yara va tomoq kasalliklarida shotut mevasi damlamasi bilan g'arg'ara qilish yaxshi natija beradi. Bunday damlama tayyorlash uchun 2 qoshiq ezib maydalangan shotut mevasi ustidan 200 g qaynoq suv quyish yo'li bilan tayyorlanadi.

Tut daraxti ildizi foydalari. Qon bosimini va qon aylanish tizimini me'yoriga keltirish uchun daraxt ildizi qaynatmasidan ichish tavsiya etiladi, uni tayyorlash jarayoni quyidagicha bo'ladi:

1.50 g ildizi maydalanib, ustidan 1 litr qaynoq suv quyiladi.

2. Bir soat o'tkazib, 15 daqiqa past olovga qo'yiladi.

3. Sovutib, dokadan o'tkazib olinadi.

4. Kuniga uch mahal stakanning uchdan bir qismi miqdorida ichiladi (yana shiraliroq bo'lishi uchun biroz asal qo'shish mumkin).

Homilador ayollar uchun ham tut mevasi homilaning yaxshi rivojlanishi uchun kerakli darmondorilar manbai hisoblanadi.

Tut mevasi immun tizimni kuchaytirib, organizmni yuqumli kasalliklarga qarshi himoya tizimini mustahkamlaydi, teriga barvaqt ajin tushishidan saqlaydi, ko'rish qobiliyatini oshirib, ko'z to'rpardasining zararlanishi kabi kasalliklardan asraydi.

Xalq tabobatida tut qadimdan turli kasalliklarni davolashda qo'llanilib kelinadi.

Yangi yig'ilgan tut mevasi yoki uning shirasi bilan xalq tabobatida og'iz yarasini samarali davolashgan. Buning uchun mevani qaynatib, og'iz bo'shlig'i chayilgan. Tut shirasi qonni tozalash, qonni ko'paytirish maqsadida ham keng qo'llangan. Bargining qaynatmasi esa angina va boshqa shamollash kasalliklarida isitmani tushiruvchi, chanqoqni qoldiruvchi vosita sifatida qo'llanilgan.

Tut daraxti po'stlog'i mayda tuyilib, kunjut yog'i bilan aralashtirilib, turli xildagi og'ir yaralar davolaniladi. Daraxt po'stlog'ining qaynatmasida esa shamollash va o'pka kasalliklarida balg'am ko'chiruvchi vosita sifatida qo'llaniladi.

Ildizining po'stlog'idan tayyorlangan qaynatma esa quruq, surunkali yo'tal, bronxit, bronxial astma (nafas qisishi), qon bosimining ko'tarilishi kasalliklarini davolashda qo'l keladi. Negaki tut daraxtining ildizi va po'stlog'ida qon tomirlarini tozalovchi, qon aylanishini me'yoriga keltiruvchi maxsus moddalar mavjud. Bundan tashqari, ildizining qaynatmasi gijjani haydashda ham eng oson davo hisoblanadi. Chilonjiyda bilan tut mevasidan tayyorlangan qaynatma esa bo'g'ma (difteriya), qizilcha (skarlatina) kabi kasalliklarga davo bo'ladi.

Abu Ali ibn Sino ham tutdan shifobaxsh vosita sifatida foydalangan. Shirin tut issiq, nordon shotut esa sovuqlikdir. Tutning shirasida, ayniqsa, uning mis idishga solib qaynatilganida, burishtirish xususiyati kuchayadi. Shu bilan birga u kuchli va yomon xiltlarning a'zolarga oqishini to'xtatadi. Bu, ayniqsa, xom tutga xos bo'ladi.

Tut, tok va qora anjirning barglarini yomg'ir suvida qaynatib ishlatilsa, sochni qoraytiradi. Oq tut bargi tomoq og'rig'i, yangi uzilgan barg shirasi tish og'rig'iga, tut mevasi va uning shirasi og'iz va tomoqdagi shishlarga davo bo'ladi. Tuzlab quritilgan tut esa ichburug' kasalligini davolaydi. Buyrak, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarini davolashda esa tut mevasi tanani ortiqcha suyuqlikdan tozalovchi, peshob haydovchi vositadir.

Tut mevasini quritib, undan damlama, kompot tayyorlab ichilsa, darmonsizlikni davolaydi, ozishga yordam beradi, organizmni tozalaydi.

Qishda tut daraxtining kurtagini olib, tozalab, damlamasini yurakni quvvatlash uchun ichib yuriladi. Tut daraxti gullari o'simlik yog'i bilan aralashtirilib, qorong'i joyda tindirilsa, teridagi mayda husnbuzar, dog'lar va sepkilni davolash uchun ajoyib krem hosil bo'ladi. Tanadagi eski yara va shikastlangan joylarni davolashda tut bargi va shoxchasini maydalab, o'simlik yog'i bilan aralashtirib surtilsa, yaralar tez bitadi, terida o'rni qolmaydi.

Ikkala xil tutning ham o'ziga xos afzal tomonlari bor. Shotut oq tutga qaraganda nordonroq bo'ladi. Ammo quvvat jihatidan undan aslo qolishmaydi. Qon bosimining ko'tarilishi, kamqonlik, ruhiy tushkunlik kabi kasalliklarni shotut yordamida davolash mumkin.

Revmatizmni davolash. Tut bargi va shoxlari yaxshilab yuvilib, mayda qilib chopiladi. Katta idishga solib, ichiga shoxlar yuzasini ko'mgunicha suv quyiladi va gaz pechida 2 soat damlanadi. Idishdagi qaynatmani tog'orachaga quyib, oyoqlar uchun vanna qabul qilinadi. Issiq barglarni og'riyotgan joylarga yopishtirib, usti toza mato va jun ro'molda issiq o'raladi. Muolaja yotishdan oldin bajariladi. 4-5 martalik davo kursidan keyin oyoqlardagi og'riqlar kamayadi.

Oq tut -balxtut, shirintut - shelkovisa belaya - morls alba L. - bo'yi 20 metrgacha, shox - shabbasi ancha qalin, tanasining po'stlari ancha qalin, o'ng'iroq tusda, yoriqlari bor, shoxlari kulirang, barglari tuxumsimon, chetlari tishli, ustki tomoni yaltiroq, gullari ayrim jinsli, kuchalasimon, to'pgullar hosil qiladi, urug'i soxta danakli. Aprelda gullaydi, may - iyunda mevalari yetiladi. Asosan ildizi, tanasining po'stlog'i, barglari mevasi ishlatiladi.

Qora tut - shohtut, nordontut - shelkovisa kislъy - morls alba L. - bo'yi 35 metrgacha, tanasining po'stlog'ida yoriqlari bor, barglari navbatma - navbat joylashgan, yuraksimon yoki tuxumsimon, bo'laklarga bo'lingan, tishli, ikki tomoni g'adir - budir, urug'li boshog'chalari deyarli bandsiz bo'lib, keyinchalik qora rangli mevalarga bo'linadi. Boxorda aprel oyi o'rtalarida gullaydi, mevalari iyun oyidan to kech kuzgacha yetilib boraveradi. Uning ildizi, tanasining po'stlog'i, barglari va mevasi ishlatiladi.

Ipak qurti tuti - shelkovisa obyknovennaya - moris - bo'yi 10 metrgacha ko'p kallakli yoki buta shaklida o'stiriladi, novdalari kesilganda, tezda yangi novda chiqaradi, ammo har yili qurt boqish uchun kesib turilganligi uchun, 30 - 40 yilda qarib hosildan qola boshlaydi, bunda tut daraxtlari yoshartiriladi. Tut daraxtidan tupidan 35 - 45 kilogramgacha tut bargi hosilini beradi. Bu tutlarni bargi uchun ekiladi.

Shaxrihon tumanidagi "Naynavo oqshomi" ilmiy eksperimental urug'chilik ko'p tarmoqli fermer xo'jaligida bir necha o'n yillardan beri antiqa TUT Dorivor tut - "Jannat meva - 3" navida tajriba - sinov ishlarini ilmiy jixatidan o'rganish ishlari amalga oshirildi, tuproq tallamaydi, sho'r va nam tuproqlarda ham hosil beraveradi. Sovuqqa, issiqqa va suvsizlikka chidamli.

Xulosa. JSST uzoq vaqtdan beri aholini dieta qonunlariga bir xil munosabatda bo'lmasdan, dietada jiddiy o'zgarishlarsiz, an'anaviy oziq-ovqatlarga qaytmasdan, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari va saraton dunyoning deyarli barcha mamlakatlarida jiddiy sog'liq muammolariga aylanishidan ogohlantirib keladi. Mevalidan shifobaxsh yarimfabrikatlari, funksional mahsulot tayyorlashning ilmiy asoslangan reseptlari ishlab chiqish. Insonlarning sog'lig'i uchun shifobaxsh va iste'molbop mevalardan Shotut va Balxi tut mevalaridan asab, animiya, bosim, buyrak xastaligi, milk shishishi, angina kasalliklari uchun dori-darmon sifatida foydalanish va mavsumdan tashqari oylarda zaruratdan kelib chiqib konservalar tayyorlash. Yarimfabrikat va tayyor mahsulotning xossalari majmuasi tavsifiya etishdan iborat.

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OZIQ OVQAT MAXSULOTLARI TARKIBIDAGI MIKROELEMENTLARNING XOSSALARI VA FUNKSIYALARI

O'ktamov Dilmurod Aminjonovich

*Namangan davlat texnika universiteti Oziq-ovqat texnologiyasi kafedrasida dotsenti
O'zbekiston Respublikasi, Namangan shaxri.*

E-mail dilmurod.uktamov@mail.ru, Tel: +998939477637

Xolmatova Matluba Mansurjon qizi

*Namangan davlat texnika universiteti Oziq-ovqat texnologiyasi kafedrasida laboranti
O'zbekiston Respublikasi, Namangan shaxri.*

Ergashev Dostonjon Rustamjon o'g'li

*Namangan davlat texnika universiteti Oziq-ovqat ta'lim yo'nalishi, 1-bosqich magistranti
O'zbekiston Respublikasi, Namangan shaxri*

Tolibjonov Jaxongirmirzo G'olbjon o'g'li

*Namangan Davlat Texnika Universiteti Biotexnologiya ta'lim yo'nalishi 2- bosqich talabasi
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Namangan shaxri*

Annotatsiya: Meva sabzavotlar, o'simlik xamda oziq ovqat mahsulotlari mikroelementlarning eng muhim tabiiy manbai bo'lib, ularni kundalik ratsionga kiritish sog'lom ovqatlanish tamoyillarini shakllantirishda muhim hisoblanadi. Shu bois ushbu maqolada meva va o'simliklar tarkibidagi mikroelementlarning inson organizmi uchun foydali xususiyatlarini ilmiy asosda yoritish dolzarb masalalardan biridir.

Kalit so'zlar. Mikroelementlar, meva-sabzavotlar, o'simliklar, oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari, moddalar almashinuvi, immun tizimi, sog'lom ovqatlanish, inson organizmi.

СВОЙСТВА И ФУНКЦИИ МИКРОЭЛЕМЕНТОВ В ПИЩЕВЫХ ПРОДУКТАХ

Аннотация: Фрукты, овощи, растения и продукты питания являются важнейшими природными источниками микроэлементов, и их включение в ежедневный рацион имеет важное значение для формирования принципов здорового питания. Поэтому в данной статье одним из актуальных вопросов является научное освещение полезных свойств микроэлементов, содержащихся во фруктах и растениях, для организма человека.

Ключевые слова: Микроэлементы, фрукты и овощи, растения, продукты питания, метаболизм, иммунная система, здоровое питание, организм человека.

PROPERTIES AND FUNCTIONS OF MICROELEMENTS IN FOOD PRODUCTS

Annotation: Fruits, vegetables, plants and food products are the most important natural sources of microelements, and their inclusion in the daily diet is important in forming the principles of healthy eating. Therefore, in this article, one of the topical issues is to scientifically highlight the beneficial properties of microelements contained in fruits and plants for the human body.

Keywords. Microelements, fruits and vegetables, plants, food products, metabolism, immune system, healthy nutrition, human's organism.

Kirish. Inson salomatligini saqlash va aholi oziqlanish sifatini yaxshilashda oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarining kimyoviy tarkibi muhim ahamiyatga ega. Xususan, oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari tarkibida uchraydigan mikroelementlar organizmda kechadigan biologik, biokimyoviy va fiziologik jarayonlarning normal amalga oshirishini ta'minlaydigan zarur komponentlar hisoblanadi. Mikroelementlar organizmda juda kam miqdorda bo'lishiga qaramay, ularning yetishmovchiligi yoki ortiqchaligi turli funksional buzilishlar, metabolik kasalliklar va surunkali patologiyalarning rivojlanishiga olib kelishi mumkin.

Mikroelementlar, jumladan temir, rux, mis, marganets, yod, selen va boshqa elementlar fermentlar, gormonlar, vitaminlar hamda biologik faol birikmalar tarkibiga kirib, modda almashinuvi, immun tizimi faoliyati, oksidlanish-qaytarilish jarayonlari va hujayra nafas olishini tartibga solishda ishtirok etadi. Ayniqsa, temir gemoglobin sintezida, rux yuzlab fermentlarning faolligida, mis esa oksidlovchi fermentlar va biriktiruvchi to'qimalar hosil bo'lishida muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Zamonaviy ovqatlanish tizimida oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini qayta ishlash texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi mikroelementlar miqdori va ularning biologik o'zlashuvchanligiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Natijada ayrim mahsulotlarda mikroelementlarning yo'qolishi yoki o'zlashuvchan bo'lmagan shakllarga o'tishi kuzatiladi. Shu sababli oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari tarkibidagi mikroelementlarning kimyoviy xossalari, biologik funksiyalari va organizm tomonidan o'zlashtirilish mexanizmlarini chuqur o'rganish dolzarb ilmiy muammo hisoblanadi.

Aholining mikroelementlarga bo'lgan ehtiyojini qondirish, mikroelement yetishmovchiligining oldini olish hamda biologik qiymati yuqori bo'lgan oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqish bugungi kunda oziq-ovqat kimyosi va ovqatlanish gigiyenasi sohalarining ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biridir. Shu nuqtai nazardan, mazkur maqolada oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari tarkibidagi asosiy mikroelementlarning xossalari, biologik funksiyalari hamda inson organizmi uchun ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi va vazifalari. Mazkur tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari tarkibida uchraydigan mikroelementlarning kimyoviy xossalari, biologik funksiyalari hamda inson organizmi uchun ahamiyatini tahlil qilish, ularning biologik o'zlashuvchanligi va oziqlanish jarayonidagi rolini ilmiy jihatdan asoslab berishdan iborat. Shuningdek, mikroelementlarning yetishmovchiligi yoki nomutanosibligi bilan bog'liq muammolarni yoritish orqali aholi salomatligini mustahkamlashga xizmat qiluvchi ilmiy xulosalar ishlab chiqish maqsad qilib qo'yilgan.

Tadqiqot materiallari va uslublari. Mazkur tadqiqot nazariy-tahliliy xarakterga ega bo'lib, oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari tarkibidagi mikroelementlarning xossalari va biologik funksiyalarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Tadqiqot materiallari sifatida oziq-ovqat kimyosi, ovqatlanish fiziologiyasi sohalariga oid mahalliy va xorijiy ilmiy manbalar, jumladan monografiyalar, dissertatsiya ishlari, ilmiy maqolalar hamda xalqaro tashkilotlar (FAO, WHO) tomonidan e'lon qilingan rasmiy ma'lumotlar tanlab olindi.

Tadqiqot jarayonida oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari tarkibida uchraydigan asosiy mikroelementlar — marganets, kobalt, yod, selen va boshqa biologik ahamiyatga ega elementlarning kimyoviy xossalari, biologik faol shakllari hamda inson organizmidagi funksiyalari tizimli tahlil qilindi. Shuningdek, mikroelementlarning oziq-ovqat mahsulotlaridan o'zlashtirilish darajasiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar, jumladan mahsulot turi, qayta ishlash texnologiyasi va biologik mavjudlik masalalari ko'rib chiqildi.

Tadqiqot uslublari sifatida ilmiy adabiyotlarni tahlil qilish, qiyosiy taqqoslash, umumlashtirish va tizimlashtirish metodlaridan foydalanildi. Turli ilmiy manbalarda keltirilgan ma'lumotlar o'zaro solishtirilib, mikroelementlarning oziqlanishdagi o'rni va ahamiyati yuzasidan xulosalar chiqarildi. Olingan natijalar asosida mikroelementlarga boy oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarining inson salomatligini saqlashdagi roli ilmiy jihatdan asoslab berildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Tadqiqot natijalari oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari tarkibida uchraydigan marganets, kobalt, yod va selen mikroelementlarining kimyoviy xossalari, biologik funksiyalari hamda inson organizmi uchun ahamiyatini tahlil qilishga qaratildi. Ilmiy manbalar tahlili ushbu mikroelementlarning organizmda kechadigan muhim metabolik jarayonlarda faol ishtirok etishini ko'rsatdi.

Yod (I). Yod qalqonsimon bez gormonlari - tiroksin va triyodtironin sintezida ishtirok etuvchi muhim mikroelement hisoblanadi. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, yodning yetarli miqdorda qabul qilinishi organizmda energiya almashinuvi, o'sish va rivojlanish jarayonlarini ta'minlaydi. Yodga boy asosiy oziq-ovqat manbalari dengiz mahsulotlari, baliq, sut va yodlangan tuz

hisoblanadi. Yod yetishmovchiligi endemik buqoq va gipotireoz kabi kasalliklarning rivojlanishiga sabab bo'lishi aniqlangan.

Yod organizm uchun muhim mikroelement bo'lib, u qalqonsimon bez gormonlari tarkibiga kiradi. Ushbu gormonlar modda almashinuvini faollashtirib, yog'lar va uglevodlarning parchalanishi hamda energiya ishlab chiqarilishida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Yod yetarli miqdorda bo'lganda organizmning umumiy rivojlanishi, ayniqsa bosh miya faoliyati, teri, soch va tishlarning sog'lom holati ta'minlanadi.

Yod tanqisligi ko'pincha ovqat ratsionida yodga boy mahsulotlarning yetishmasligi bilan bog'liq. Bunda qalqonsimon bez kattalashishi (endemik buqoq), modda almashinuvi sekinlashuvi, tana haroratining pasayishi, terining qurishi, jismoniy va aqliy faollikning susayishi kuzatilishi mumkin. Bolalik va o'sish davrida yod yetishmovchiligi ayniqsa xavfli bo'lib, aqliy va jismoniy rivojlanishga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Yodning ortiqcha iste'moli esa ko'proq nazoratsiz qo'shimchalar yoki preparatlarni uzoq muddat qabul qilish bilan bog'liq bo'ladi. Ratsionda muvozanat buzilganda allergik holatlar, tumovga o'xshash belgilar, terida toshmalar va ko'zdan yosh oqishi kuzatilishi mumkin. Shu sababli yodni oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari orqali me'yorida qabul qilish eng maqbul hisoblanadi [1-3].

Marganets (Mn). Marganets organizmda fermentativ jarayonlarning faolligini ta'minlovchi muhim mikroelement hisoblanadi. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, marganets uglevodlar, lipidlar va oqsillar almashinuvini tartibga soluvchi bir qator fermentlar tarkibiga kiradi hamda antioksidant himoya tizimida ishtirok etadi. Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari tarkibida marganets asosan don mahsulotlari, dukkakli ekinlar, yong'oqlar va ko'katlarda uchraydi. Marganets yetishmovchiligi suyak tizimi rivojlanishining buzilishi va metabolik jarayonlarning sustlashuvi bilan bog'liqligi aniqlangan.

Marganets (Mn) inson organizmi uchun zarur bo'lgan mikroelementlardan biri bo'lib, uglevodlar, yog'lar va oqsillar almashinuvida muhim rol o'ynaydi. U antioksidant fermentlar tarkibiga kirib, hujayralarni oksidlovchi stressdan himoya qiladi. Marganets energiya hosil bo'lish jarayonlarida, aminokislotalar parchalanishi va glikozaminoglikanlar sintezida ishtirok etadi. Ushbu mikroelement vitamin B₁, B₆, C va E ning biologik faolligini oshirib, ularning organizmda to'liq o'zlashtirilishini ta'minlaydi.

Marganets suyak va tog'ay to'qimalarining shakllanishi, skeletning normal o'sishi va mustahkamligi uchun zarur hisoblanadi. U markaziy nerv tizimi faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlab, xotira, diqqat va mushak reflekslarini yaxshilaydi. Shuningdek, marganets jinsiy gormonlar sintezi va qalqonsimon bez gormoni – tiroksin ishlab chiqarilishida ishtirok etib, endokrin tizim faoliyatiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Marganets yetishmovchiligi metabolik jarayonlarning sekinlashuvi, charchoq, bosh aylanishi, asabiylik va xotira pasayishi bilan namoyon bo'ladi. Bolalarda marganets tanqisligi suyaklarning yetarlicha rivojlanmasligi, o'sishdan orqada qolish va o'quv qobiliyatining pasayishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Kattalarda esa lipid almashinuvining buzilishi, xolesterin muvozanatining izdan chiqishi va uglevod almashinuvining buzilishi kuzatiladi [4-8].

Kobalt (Co). Kobalt biologik jihatdan faol element bo'lib, u vitamin B₁₂ (kobalamin) molekulasining tarkibiy qismi hisoblanadi. Tadqiqot natijalari kobaltning qon hosil bo'lish jarayonlari, asab tizimi faoliyati va hujayra bo'linishini qo'llab-quvvatlashdagi rolini tasdiqlaydi. Kobalt asosan hayvon mahsulotlari, sut va sut mahsulotlari, baliq hamda dukkakli o'simliklarda uchraydi. Kobalt yetishmovchiligi kamqonlik va umumiy holsizlik holatlariga olib kelishi mumkin.

Kobalt (Co) inson organizmi uchun zarur bo'lgan mikroelement bo'lib, asosan vitamin B₁₂ (tsianokobalamin) tarkibida mavjud. U eritrotsitlar hosil bo'lishi, temirni gemoglobinga o'tishini va yetilgan qizil qon tanachalarining periferik qonga chiqarilishini stimullaydi. Shuningdek, kobalt modda almashinuvida, oqsil sintezida va nerv tizimi faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Kobaltning yetarli miqdorda bo'lishi organizmda qon ishlab chiqarish jarayonini me'yorida olib boradi, nerv tizimi va mushak faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi, umumiy immunitetni

kuchaytiradi. U shuningdek, energetik almashinuvni rag‘batlantiradi va vitamin B₁₂ ning biologik faolligini ta‘minlaydi.

Kobalt yetishmovchiligi organizmda gematopoetik jarayonlarning buzilishi, qizil qon tanachalarining yetishmasligi (anemiya), charchoq, tez toliqish va konsentratsiya kamayishi bilan namoyon bo‘ladi. Bolalarda kobalt yetishmovchiligi rivojlanishning sekinlashishiga, immunitet pasayishiga va o‘shidan orqada qolishga olib kelishi mumkin.

Kobalt asosan o‘simlik mahsulotlari orqali organizmga kiradi. Kobaltga boy mahsulotlar qatoriga yashil bargli sabzavotlar (ismaloq, karam, petrushka), dukkaklilar (no‘xat, mosh, loviya), yong‘oq va urug‘lar (kunjut, bodom, yeryong‘oq), tuxum sarig‘i va sut mahsulotlari kiradi. Shu bilan birga, mevalar (banan, olma, anor, quritilgan mevalar) ham kobaltning manbai hisoblanadi.

Kobaltning o‘zlashtirilishi oqsil va temir bilan birgalikda ratsionda mavjud bo‘lsa yanada yaxshilanadi. Ratsionda yetarli kobalt bo‘lishi bolaning o‘shisi, qon hosil bo‘lishi va umumiy sog‘liq holati uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega. Kobaltning ortiqcha miqdori esa toksik bo‘lib, allergik kasalliklar, kardiomiopatiya va nafas a‘zolari bilan bog‘liq muammolarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin.

Oziq-ovqat bilan kattalarda kobalt kuniga 0,005–1,5 mg (14–78 mkg) miqdorida qabul qilinadi. O‘simliklar orqali qabul qilinadigan kobalt miqdori taxminan 90% ni tashkil qiladi. Shu bois, ratsionning o‘simliklarga boy bo‘lishi kobalt bilan ta‘minlanishda muhim hisoblanadi [9-12].

Selen (Se). Selen kuchli antioksidant xususiyatlarga ega mikroelement bo‘lib, u glutation peroksidaza kabi fermentlarning faoliyatida muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Tadqiqot natijalari selenning immun tizimi faoliyatini mustahkamlash, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari va oksidlovchi stressning oldini olishdagi ahamiyatini ko‘rsatadi. Selen asosan baliq, dengiz mahsulotlari, tuxum, don mahsulotlari va yong‘oqlarda uchraydi. Selen yetishmovchiligi immunitet pasayishi va surunkali kasalliklar xavfining ortishi bilan bog‘liq ekanligi aniqlangan [13-14].

Muxokama. Yuqoridagi ma‘lumotlardan kelib chiqib aytish mumkinki mikroelementlarni meva va sabzavotlar hamda ozuqa mahsulotlari bilan istemol qilish maqsadga muvofiq bo‘lib, marganets elementi bargli sabzavotlar (ismaloq, karam), lavlagi, sabzi, dukkaklilar va yong‘oqlarda ko‘p. Ratsiondagi marganets suyak va mushak rivojlanishi hamda nerv tizimi faoliyatini qo‘llab-quvvatlaydi. Kobalt asosan o‘simlik mahsulotlari orqali olinadi, yashil bargli sabzavotlar, dukkaklilar, yong‘oq, bodom, kunjut, shu bilan birga, sut, tuxum va ba‘zi baliqlarda mavjud. Ratsionda kobalt yetarli bo‘lishi vitamin B₁₂ faoliyatini ta‘minlaydi. Yod dengiz mahsulotlari, baliq, dengiz karamlarida ko‘p. Yetishmovchilik qalqonsimon bez faoliyatini buzadi. Selen elementi yong‘oq, urug‘lar, baliq, go‘sht va butun donli mahsulotlarda mavjud. Antioksidant sifatida hujayralarni himoya qiladi.

Xulosa. Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari tarkibidagi mikroelementlar — marganets, kobalt, yod va selen — inson organizmi uchun muhim biologik va fiziologik rol o‘ynaydi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko‘rsatdiki, Marganets (Mn) fermentativ jarayonlar, metabolizm va antioksidant himoya tizimida faol ishtirok etadi. Kobalt (Co) vitamin B₁₂ sintezida muhim bo‘lib, qon hosil bo‘lish va asab tizimi faoliyatini qo‘llab-quvvatlaydi. Yod (I) qalqonsimon bez gormonlari ishlab chiqarilishida ishtirok etib, energiya almashinuvi va o‘shish jarayonlarini ta‘minlaydi. Selen (Se) kuchli antioksidant xususiyatga ega bo‘lib, immun tizimi va yurak-qon tomir salomatligini himoya qiladi.

Shuningdek, oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarining turli turlari va ularni qayta ishlash texnologiyalari mikroelementlarning biologik mavjudligi va organizm tomonidan o‘zlashtirilish darajasiga sezilarli ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi. Tadqiqot asosida shuni ta‘kidlash mumkinki, ushbu mikroelementlarning ratsional va muvozanatli iste‘moli inson salomatligini saqlash, metabolik jarayonlarni tartibga solish va mikroelement yetishmovchiligi bilan bog‘liq kasalliklarning oldini olishda muhim omil hisoblanadi.

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INTENSIFICATION OF HYDROCARBON VAPOUR CONDENSATION IN SHELL-AND-TUBE CONDENSERS.

Sharipov K.K., Xadjibaev A.Sh., Radjabova S.R
Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology

Abstract: *This study presents experimental results on heat transfer during the condensation of water vapour and hydrocarbon (petrol fraction) vapours in modular shell-and-tube condensers. The experiments were carried out at vapour pressures ranging from 50 to 250 kPa and cooling water flow rates of 3–11 L/min. The temperature distribution of the condensate along the condenser length, vapour pressure dynamics, and condensate formation rates were investigated under steady-state operating conditions. The results demonstrate that hydrocarbon vapours condense at higher temperatures than water vapour at identical pressure levels. Condensation of water vapour is mainly concentrated in the initial section of the condenser tubes, while hydrocarbon vapour condensation occurs more uniformly along the heat transfer surface. This behaviour is associated with the multicomponent composition of hydrocarbon vapours and their condensation over a temperature range rather than at a single saturation temperature. Under equal thermal input conditions, a larger volume of hydrocarbon condensate was formed compared to water vapour, which is explained by the lower latent heat of condensation of hydrocarbon vapours. Analysis of the temperature profiles makes it possible to identify an effective condensation zone, which can be used for optimisation of shell-and-tube condenser geometry and operating parameters in hydrocarbon processing applications.*

Key words: *condensation, shell-and-tube condenser, hydrocarbon vapours, heat exchange, temperature profile, process dynamics, thermal efficiency.*

Introduction

Condensation processes play a crucial role in heat and mass transfer operations widely used in the chemical, petrochemical and oil refining industries. In shell-and-tube condensers, the efficiency of heat removal is largely determined by the thermophysical properties of vapours, operating pressure and temperature distribution along the heat exchange surface. Hydrocarbon vapours, in particular, exhibit complex condensation behaviour due to their multicomponent composition and variable saturation temperatures.

In recent years, significant attention has been devoted to the intensification of condensation processes by improving apparatus design and optimising operating conditions. Previous studies have shown that non-uniform temperature profiles along condenser tubes may reduce overall heat transfer efficiency and lead to incomplete vapour condensation [1–3]. Experimental investigations of condensation of water and hydrocarbon vapours in laboratory and pilot-scale apparatuses have demonstrated that pressure variation strongly affects the onset and intensity of condensation [4–6].

Despite numerous studies, insufficient experimental data are available on the comparative condensation behaviour of water and light hydrocarbon vapours under identical operating conditions in modular shell-and-tube condensers. In particular, the influence of vapour pressure on temperature distribution and condensate formation dynamics remains inadequately quantified.

The present study aims to experimentally investigate the condensation of water and hydrocarbon vapours in a modular shell-and-tube condenser. Special attention is paid to analysing pressure-dependent temperature profiles along the condenser length and evaluating the potential for intensifying heat transfer during condensation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To study the heat transfer process during condensation of water and hydrocarbon vapours, an experimental setup [1,2,3] was used, consisting of a steam generator 2, three modular shell-and-

tube condensers 6, a measuring tank for condensate collection 9 and a volumetric counter 7 to determine the cooling water flow rate (Fig.1.).

Figure 1. Experimental setup of the modular shell-and-tube condenser system.

1 - gas burner; 2 - steam generator; 3 - pressure gauge; 4 - connecting pipe; 5 - purge valve; 6 - modular shell-and-tube condenser; 7 - cold water flow meter; 8 - regulating valve; 9 - measuring tank for condensate collection.

Modular shell-and-tube condensers have the following parameters [1-5]. The first horizontal condenser has the following dimensions: diameter of heat-exchange tubes $d_1=10 \times 2,0$ mm, working length of one tube $L_1=1000$ mm, their number $n_1=7$ pieces, diameter of the apparatus shell $D_1=70 \times 3,0$ mm. The total heat exchange area of the apparatus is $F_1=0,308$ m².

Geometrical parameters of the second and third condensers are as follows: $d=12 \times 2,5$ mm, $L=1000$ mm, $n=5$ pieces and $D=70 \times 3,0$ mm and heat transfer surface $F_2=F_3=0.236$ m².

The experiments on the unit were carried out in the following order. Liquid coolant (15÷20 litres of petrol from Bukhara refinery) was poured into the steam generator 2 and natural gas was ignited by means of burner 1 and the contents of the generator were brought to boiling. When the necessary value of vapour pressure in the steam generator 2 is reached, steam is launched into the intertube space of the condenser 6 under test. After the apparatus is heated up, a flow of cooling water is supplied into its tube space and its flow rate is regulated by the flow meter 7. During the experiments the following parameters are measured: steam pressure and temperature in the steam generator, cooling water flow rate, its temperature at the condenser inlet and outlet, current value of condensate temperature at five points along the length of condenser 6 and volume flow rate of condensate formed during the process. Readings of control and measuring instruments are recorded by time, at intervals of 3÷5 minutes, until the condenser steady-state thermal regime is reached.

Experiments on studying the process of hydrocarbon vapour condensation in modular condensers were carried out at vapour pressure from 50 to 250 kPa and cooling water flow rate of 3÷11 l/min. The water temperature at the inlet to the unit was equal to 15÷20 °C.

During the experiments the main attention was paid to studying the change of vapour condensation temperature along the length of the apparatus and the change of the volume of condensate formed in it. During the experiments the temperature of water at the unit outlet did not exceed 50 °C, which corresponds to the conditions of operation of industrial condensers contributing to the prevention of salt precipitation [6,p.109-119].

During the experiments the values of the following parameters were recorded: water meter reading, water temperature at the inlet to the unit, at the initial and final sections of each condenser section, steam pressure and temperature, condensate temperature at the corresponding sections of the condenser sections, as well as the volume of condensate formed during the process.

The coolant temperature was measured with laboratory mercury glass thermometers of TL-2 and TL-2M type, produced by JSC «Termopribor» (RF) according to TU 25-2001.003-88. The temperature measuring range of thermometers is up to +350 °C, the limit of permissible errors of measurement in this temperature range is ± 1 °C.

The vapour temperature in the evaporator was directly measured by manometric thermometer DM05, produced by JSC «Steklopribor», Ukraine according to TU U33.2-14307481-031:2005 and GOST 2405-88. The pressure measuring range of the device is 0÷250 kPa, accuracy class - 1,5.

For comparison of thermophysical indices of vapours of heat-carriers three series of experiments were performed: condensation of water vapour by cold water stream (clarifying), condensation of vapours of petrol fraction by cold water (control) and condensation of vapours of petrol fraction by hydrocarbon raw materials (oil and gas-condensate mixture) as a cooling agent;

The main purpose of the experiments was a comparative assessment of the time to reach the operating mode of the evaporator of the pilot plant when using gasoline or water vapour as a heating agent, i.e. determination of the dynamic characteristics of the vapour formation process at vapour pressure in the system up to 250 kPa [7].

Results and Discussion

Fig. 2. shows the rate of change of vapour pressure of water (curve 1, control) and petrol (curve 2) in the evaporator. As can be seen from the figure, in both variants of experiments there is a smooth change in the heating agent pressure over time.

Figure 2. Pressure profiles of water vapour (1) and petrol vapour (2) by time.

It should be noted that at the same thermal capacity of the evaporator, the pressure formed by petrol vapours, in comparison with the pressure of water vapour, has a higher value. Comparison of the received experimental data testify that at $P=40\div250$ kPa the value of difference between vapour pressures of the compared heat-carriers is in the limit from 20 to 60 kPa. Experiments have established that in this range of pressures, when using petrol vapour as a heating agent, the time of the plant output to the operating mode is reduced by 10÷30 minutes, in comparison with the case of application of heating water vapour.

The main purpose of the experiments is to establish the character of the coolant temperature distribution along the length of the condenser pipe. The study of the coolant temperature distribution along the pipe length is reduced to determination of their optimal operating length l_{opt} . In this case the problem is reduced to determination of the optimal heat transfer surface of the tube condenser $F_{opt} = \pi \cdot d \cdot n \cdot l_{opt}$. The solution of this problem is of considerable help in the calculation and design of energetically optimal designs of tubular heat exchangers [8-11].

The experiments were carried out at vapour pressures of 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 kPa. During the experiments, the cooling water flow rate was maintained at 3 l/min. The water temperature at the condenser inlet was 15 °C.

Fig. 3. shows the changes of condensate temperature t of water vapour along the length of pipes of the experimental condenser L at different values of pressure in the system ($P = 50\div250$ kPa). As can be seen from the graph, in the casing of the horizontal condenser there is an intensive drop of water vapour condensate temperature up to 35÷55 °C. Judging by the graph, the first section of the apparatus pipes with length up to 1 m is a zone of active condensation of water vapour, at the same time in the second section of the apparatus pipes (from 1 m to 2 m) there is a gradual cooling of condensate up to 20÷27 °C.

Figure 3. Temperature profiles of water vapour condensate along the condenser length.

Fig. 4. presents the graphical dependence of the change in the condensation temperature of petrol vapours along the length of the experimental unit at pressures $P = 50\text{-}250$ kPa. As we see, with increasing pressure the temperature of condensation of petrol vapours increases, as evidenced by the mutual arrangement of curves in the figure. At the same time the character of gasoline vapour condensation temperature drop along the whole length of the apparatus pipes at all pressure values is close to rectilinear.

Figure 4. Temperature profiles of petrol vapour condensate along the condenser length.

Comparison of the obtained results shows that petrol vapour has a higher condensation temperature compared to water vapour - at the same values of pressure in the system. At a pressure of 50 kPa the difference in the values of condensation temperatures of heat carriers is $7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and at a pressure of 250 kPa this difference reaches up to $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Further additional experiments were carried out to study the time variation of the volume of the formed condensate during the process.

Fig. 5. The results of measuring the volume of formed condensate V (l) of water vapour (curve 1) and petrol vapour (curve 2) by time τ (min) at pressure $P = 250$ kPa [1,12].

Figure 5. Variation of condensate volume with time at vapour pressure of 250 kPa.

The steepness of curve 1 confirms that the process of condensation of petrol vapour in the apparatus is much more intensive than condensation of water vapour. Comparison of curves shows that by 40 minutes of the process the volume of petrol vapour condensate is formed 5-6 times more

than the volume of water condensate. The increased volume of formed petrol condensate is explained by the fact that the heat of condensation of hydrocarbon vapours is significantly less than the heat of condensation of water vapour. The increased volume of petrol condensate is primarily associated with the lower latent heat of condensation of hydrocarbon vapours and reflects thermophysical differences between the condensing media rather than a direct proportional increase in condenser efficiency. Thus, the analysis of steam condensation temperature distribution along the length of the experimental tubular condenser allows to determine the optimal indicators of the heat transfer process at condensation of hydrocarbon vapours and design dimensions, which contribute to the increase of thermal efficiency of industrial tubular condensers.

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40–180 °С ҲАРОРАТ ОРАЛИҒИДА БЕНЗИН ФРАКЦИЯЛАРИНИНГ БУҒЛАНИШ ИССИҚЛИГИНИНГ ҲАРОРАТ ВА МОЛЕКУЛЯР МАССАГА БОҒЛИҚЛИГИНИ ТАҲЛИЛ ҚИЛИШ

К.К.Шарипов., Хаджибаев А.Ш., Абдуллаева С.Ш., Жабборова М.А
Тошкент кимё технологияси институти

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада бензин фракцияларининг 40–180 °С ҳарорат оралиғида буғланиш иссиқлиги ва молекуляр массасининг ўзгариши термодинамик ва эмпирик усуллар асосида таҳлил қилинди. Трутон ва Крег формулалари ёрдамида буғланиш иссиқлиги ҳисобланди ва уларнинг ҳароратга боғлиқлиги қиёсий баҳоланди. Тадқиқот натижалари буғланиш иссиқлигининг ҳарорат ортиши билан камайиши ва молекуляр масса ортиши билан ўзгариш қонуниятларини тасдиқлади. Олинган натижалар нефть маҳсулотларини қайта ишлаш, иссиқлик алмашинув аппаратларини ҳисоблаш ва ёқилги буғланиш жараёнларини моделлаштиришида қўлланилиши мумкин.

Калим сўзлар: Бензин фракцияси, буғланиш иссиқлиги, молекуляр масса, ҳарорат, суюқ фаза, буғ фаза.

Нефть маҳсулотларининг иссиқлик-физик хусусиятлари энергетика, нефть-кимё ва иссиқлик техникаси соҳаларида муҳим аҳамиятга эга. Буғланиш иссиқлиги фазавий ўтиш жараёнининг асосий термодинамик параметрларидан бири бўлиб, иссиқлик алмашинув аппаратларини лойиҳалаш, буғланиш ва конденсация жараёнларини ҳисоблашда муҳим роль ўйнайди. Бензин фракциялари кўп компонентли система бўлганлиги сабабли, унинг буғланиш иссиқлиги ҳарорат ва молекуляр массага боғлиқ ҳолда ўзгаради.

Буғланиш иссиқлигини ҳисоблаш учун Трутон ва Крег формулаларидан фойдаланилди. Трутон қонунига мувофиқ буғланиш иссиқлиги қайнаш ҳароратига пропорционал: $r = \frac{K \cdot T_b}{M}$, бу ерда K - Трутон коэффициенти. r - буғланиш иссиқлиги кДж/кг, T_b - қайнаш ҳарорати, M - молекуляр масса. Крег формуласи эса буғланиш иссиқлигининг ҳароратга чизикли боғлиқлигини ҳисобга олади. Крег формуласи $r = A - B \cdot T$.

бу ерда:

r - буғланиш иссиқлиги, кДж/кг

T - ҳарорат, К

A ва B - эмпирик коэффицентлар

Бу ишда бензин фракцияларининг буғланиш иссиқлиги Трутон ва Крег формулалари асосида ҳисобланди. Молекуляр масса Воинов–Эйгенсон формуласи бўйича аниқланди. Ҳисоблашлар 40–180 °С ҳарорат оралиғида амалга оширилди. Бензин фракцияси дистиллятининг буғланиш иссиқлиги ишда Трутон формуласи бўйича, унинг молекуляр массаси M ни ҳисобга олган ҳолда аниқланган.

40–200 °С ҳароратлар оралиғида бензин фракциясининг молекуляр массаси ва тавсифловчи коэффицент $K = 11,726$ аниқлаштирилган формула бўйича ҳисоблаб чиқилган (Б.П. Воинов – Л.С. Эйгенсон (1.38)). Паст қайнаш ҳароратига эга нефть маҳсулотларининг ($d_{15}^{15} = 07667$ да), шу жумладан бензиннинг ҳам буғланиш иссиқлиги Крег формуласи бўйича ҳам аниқланиши мумкин. Бензин фракцияси дистилляти ва унинг буғларининг буғланиш иссиқлигини Трутон формуласи ва Крег формуласи бўйича ҳисоблаш натижалари 1-жадвалда келтирилган.

Бензин фракцияси ва унинг буғларининг 40÷180 °С ҳарорат оралиғида буғланиш иссиқлиги

t, °С	Молекуляр масса, М	Бензиннинг буғланиш иссиқлиги г, кДж/кг		
		Суюқ фаза учун (Трутон формуласи)	Буғ фаза учун (Трутон формуласи)	Суюқ фаза учун (Крег формуласи)
40	73,93	359,190	399,619	446,460
60	81,88	347,119	380,710	445,477
80	90,69	334,120	363,263	444,494
100	95,72	334,120	363,263	444,494
110	100,36	320,765	347,166	443,511
120	110,87	307,450	332,307	442,528
130	116,45	300,895	325,306	442,036
140	122,25	294,441	318,573	441,545
150	128,25	288,106	312,095	441,053
160	134,47	281,904	305,860	440,562
170	140,91	275,846	299,857	440,070
180	147,55	269,939	294,073	439,579

Графикда бензин фракциясининг буғланиш иссиқлиги 40–180 °С ҳарорат оралиғида ўзгариши кўрсатилган. Ҳарорат ошиши билан барча ҳолатларда буғланиш иссиқлиги қийматларининг камайиши кузатилади, бу эса молекулалараро ўзаро таъсир кучларининг сусайиши билан изоҳланади. Трутон формуласи бўйича ҳисобланган суюқ фаза учун буғланиш иссиқлиги ҳарорат ортиши билан сезиларли даражада пасаяди. Крег формуласи бўйича ҳисобланган суюқ фаза учун буғланиш иссиқлиги эса нисбатан катта қийматларга эга бўлиб, ҳароратга боғлиқ ҳолда деярли чизиқли ва секин камайиш характериға эга. Бу Крег формуласи паст қайнайдиган нефть маҳсулотлари учун барқарор натижалар беришини кўрсатади.

Умуман олганда, графикдан кўриниб турибдики, ҳарорат ошган сари бензиннинг буғланиш жараёни енгиллашади ва буғланиш иссиқлиги камаёди, турли эмпирик формулалар бир хил тенденцияни кўрсатиб, қийматлари бўйича фарқ қилади.

Ҳисоблаш натижалари шуни кўрсатдики, ҳарорат 40 °С дан 180 °С гача ошганда бензин фракцияларининг молекуляр массаси 73,93 дан 147,55 гача ортиб борди. Бу ҳолат

оғир компонентлар улуши ортиб боришини кўрсатади. Буғланиш иссиқлиги эса ҳарорат ортиши билан камайиб борди, бу молекулалараро ўзаро таъсир кучларининг камайиши билан изоҳланади.

Трутон формуласи бўйича буғланиш иссиқлиги 359,19 кДж/кг дан 269,94 кДж/кг гача камайди. Крег формуласи бўйича ҳисобланган қийматлар эса нисбатан юқори ва кам ўзгарувчан бўлди. Бу натижалар Трутон формуласи ҳарорат таъсирини аниқроқ ҳисобга олишини кўрсатади. Бу тенденция молекулаларнинг кинетик энергияси ҳарорат ортиши билан ўсиши натижасида улар орасидаги ўзаро тортишиш кучларини енгиш учун камроқ қўшимча энергия талаб қилиниши билан изоҳланади. Демак, юқори ҳароратларда буғланиш жараёнининг интенсивлиги ортади.

Буғланиш иссиқлиги фазавий ўтиш параметри бўлиб, унинг қиймати ҳарорат ортиши билан камаяди. Бу ҳолат фазавий ўтиш жараёнининг термодинамик хусусиятлари билан изоҳланади. Ҳисобланган суяқ фазадаги буғланиш иссиқлиги қийматлари нисбатан юқори ва барқарор характерга эга. Ҳарорат 40 °С дан 180 °С гача ўзгарганда ушбу кўрсаткич 446,46 кДж/кг дан 439,58 кДж/кг гача камайган бўлиб, ўзгариш оралиғи катта эмас.

Бу ҳолат (Крег формуласи) ифодаси ҳарорат таъсирини камроқ ҳисобга олиши ёки ушбу буғланиш маълум бир фракцион таркиб учун умумлаштирилган характерга эга эканлигини кўрсатади. Шу сабабли, аниқ ҳисоб-китобларда қайси ифода қўлланилаётганига алоҳида эътибор бериш лозим. Таҳлил натижалари шуни кўрсатадики, (Трутон формуласи) ифодаси бўйича ҳисобланган буғланиш иссиқлиги қийматлари ҳароратга сезгир бўлиб, бензин фракцияларининг реал термодинамик хулқини яхшироқ акс эттиради. (Крег формуласи) ифодаси эса нисбатан юқори ва кам ўзгарувчан қийматлар бериб, инженерлик ҳисоб-китобларида тахминий баҳолаш учун қулай ҳисобланади.

Суяқ ва буғ фазаларидаги қийматлар ўртасидаги фарқ эса фазавий ўтиш жараёнларини моделлашда муҳим параметр сифатида намоён бўлади. Олинган натижалар нефть маҳсулотларининг буғланиш жараёнларини ҳисоблаш, иссиқлик алмашинув аппаратларини лойиҳалаш ва нефть-кимё саноатида қўлланиладиган ҳисоблаш методларини такомиллаштириш учун илмий ва амалий асос бўлиб хизмат қилади. Бу қонуният Clausius–Clapeyron тенгламасига мос келади. Бу натижалар бензин фракцияларининг термодинамик хусусиятларини аниқ баҳолаш имконини беради.

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МОНИТОРИНГ МИКРОКОЛИЧЕСТВ ИОНОВ ЖЕЛЕЗА(III) И МЕДИ(II) В ОБЪЕКТАХ ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЫ (Обзорная статья)

Тулиев Бехруз Алимкулович

Преподаватель химического факультета Национального Университета Узбекистана,
Узбекистан, г. Ташкент. E-mail: bexruz.tuliyev@mail.ru

Турабов Нурмухаммат Турабович

к.х.н., профессор химического факультета Национального Университета Узбекистана,
Узбекистан, г. Ташкент. E-mail: turabov2019@mail.ru

Тоджиев Жамолиддин Насириддинович

DSc, доцент химического факультета Национального университета Узбекистана,
Узбекистан, г. Ташкент. E-mail: todjiev@mail.ru

Абдикаххорова Сабохат Шодибек кызы

Магистрант химического факультета Национального Университета Узбекистана,

Алимбоев Дониёр Абдуганпор угли

Магистрант Гулистанского государственного университета,

Тулиева Дилоро Алимкуловна

Учитель общеобразовательной средней школы №17 Паркентского района Ташкентской
области, Узбекистан, г.

Аннотация: В последние годы определение и мониторинг концентрации ионов тяжелых металлов является одной из актуальных научных проблем в обеспечении экологической и продовольственной безопасности. Несмотря на то, что ионы железа(III) и меди(II) являются биологически важными микроэлементами, их избыточное содержание оказывает негативное воздействие на здоровье человека и экосистемы. Исследования, проводимые в данном направлении, указывают на необходимость разработки высокочувствительных и селективных методов определения следовых количеств этих ионов. Современные подходы аналитической химии, в частности спектрофотометрические методы на основе органических реагентов, выделяются своей простотой, экспрессностью и экономической эффективностью. Сравнительный анализ методов определения ионов железа и меди в объектах окружающей среды (вода, почва, атмосфера) и пищевых продуктах позволяет оценить их аналитические возможности. Особое значение при контроле промышленных сточных вод и продовольственного сырья приобретают высокоточные экспресс-методы. Предложенные подходы служат основой для выбора эффективных и практически удобных методов анализа, способствующих обеспечению экологического мониторинга и безопасности пищевой продукции.

Ключевые слова: экологический мониторинг, окружающая среда, зеленая химия, токсичность, спектрофотометрия, природные объекты, ионы тяжелых металлов, железо(III), медь(II), определение микроколичеств.

MONITORING OF MICRO-QUANTITIES OF IRON(III) AND COPPER(II) IONS IN ENVIRONMENTAL SAMPLES (Review article)

Abstract: In recent years, the determination and monitoring of heavy metal ions have emerged as critical scientific challenges in ensuring environmental and food safety. Although iron(III) and copper(II) ions are biologically essential elements, their excessive concentrations pose significant risks to human health and ecological systems. Research in this field emphasizes the urgent need to develop highly sensitive and selective methods for the determination of these ions at trace levels. Modern analytical chemistry approaches, particularly spectrophotometric methods

based on organic reagents, are distinguished by their simplicity, rapid analysis time, and cost-effectiveness. A comparative analysis of the methods for determining iron and copper ions in environmental matrices (water, soil, atmosphere) and food products serves to evaluate their analytical performance. High-precision express methods are of particular importance for monitoring industrial wastewater and food raw materials. These approaches facilitate the selection of efficient, sensitive, and practically convenient methods for iron(III) and copper(II) determination, contributing to robust environmental monitoring and food safety standards.

Keywords: environmental monitoring, environment, green chemistry, toxicity, spectrophotometry, natural objects, heavy metal ions, iron(III), copper(II), micro-quantity determination

ATROF-MUHIT OBYEKTLARIDA TEMIR(III) VA MIS(II) IONLARINING MIKRO MIQDORINI KUZATISH (Sharh maqola)

Annotatsiya: So‘nggi yillarda atrof-muhit va oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta‘minlashda og‘ir metall ionlarini aniqlash va monitoring qilish dolzarb ilmiy muammolardan biri hisoblanadi. Temir(III) va mis(II) ionlari biologik jihatdan muhim elementlar bo‘lishiga qaramay, ularning ortiqcha miqdori inson salomatligi va ekologik tizimlarga salbiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi. Ushbu yo‘nalishda olib borilgan tadqiqotlar ushbu ionlarning mikro miqdorlarini aniqlashda yuqori sezgir va selektiv usullarni ishlab chiqish zarurligini ko‘rsatmoqda. Zamonaviy analitik kimyo yondashuvlari, xususan, organik reagentlar asosidagi spektrofotometrik metodlar, oddiyligi, tezkorligi va iqtisodiy samaradorligi bilan ajralib turadi. Atrof-muhit obyektlari (suv, tuproq, atmosfera) hamda oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarida temir va mis ionlarini aniqlash usullarining qiyosiy tahlili ularning analitik imkoniyatlarini baholashga xizmat qiladi. Ayniqsa, sanoat oqava suvlarini va oziq-ovqat xom ashyolarini nazorat qilishda yuqori aniqlikdagi ekspress usullar muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Mazkur yondashuvlar temir(III) va mis(II) ionlarini aniqlashda samarali, sezgir va amaliy jihatdan qulay metodlarni tanlash hamda ekologik monitoring va oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta‘minlashga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: ekologik monitoring, atrof-muhit, yashil kimyo, toksiklik, spektrofotometriya, tabiiy obyektlar, og‘ir metall ionlari, temir(III), mis(II), mikro miqdorlarni aniqlash.

ВВЕДЕНИЕ. На современном этапе одной из ключевых задач системы экологического мониторинга является раннее выявление загрязнений в компонентах окружающей среды и предотвращение их негативных последствий. В условиях интенсивного развития процессов индустриализации и урбанизации наблюдается увеличение поступления различных ионов тяжёлых металлов в природную среду. В этой связи контроль содержания ионов железа(III) и меди(II) приобретает важное значение с точки зрения экологической безопасности и качества пищевой продукции.

Современные научные исследования показывают, что, несмотря на биологическую значимость ионов железа и меди как необходимых микроэлементов, их повышенные концентрации могут приводить к нарушению биохимических процессов, усилению окислительного стресса и проявлению токсических эффектов. В связи с этим разработка высокочувствительных и селективных аналитических методов для определения их следовых количеств является одной из актуальных научных задач.

Современные концепции экологического мониторинга тесно связаны с целями устойчивого развития и направлены на углублённый анализ нарушений круговорота веществ в окружающей среде, а также на разработку стратегий снижения факторов риска. В этом контексте особую роль играют принципы «зелёной химии», ориентированные на совершенствование аналитических методов, включая разработку экспрессных методик, позволяющих проводить анализ в режиме реального времени и непосредственно в месте отбора проб.

Спектрофотометрические методы анализа широко применяются для определения ионов железа(III) и меди(II), поскольку характеризуются простотой, оперативностью и экономической эффективностью. Использование органических аналитических реагентов способствует повышению селективности и точности данных методов.

Таким образом, совершенствование современных аналитических подходов к определению ионов железа(III) и меди(II) в объектах окружающей среды и пищевых продуктах является важным направлением развития системы экологического мониторинга.

Такая оперативность позволяет разрабатывать эффективные меры по ликвидации чрезвычайных ситуаций и предотвращению их возникновения в будущем [3]. Инновационные «зелёные» технологии находят широкое применение при разработке и производстве химической продукции, особенно в технологических процессах синтеза, а также при минимизации использования опасных реагентов (Рисунок).

Рисунок. Основные структурные элементы концепции «зелёной химии»

Известно, что тяжёлые и токсичные металлы (ТТМ) относятся к числу приоритетных загрязняющих веществ, подлежащих обязательному экологическому мониторингу. При классификации тяжёлых элементов важную роль играет их высокая токсичность [4]. В зависимости от степени токсикологического воздействия (таблица 1) химические вещества, согласно стандарту GOST 17.4.1.0283, подразделяются на три класса.

Таблица 1

Классификация тяжелых элементов от степени токсикологического воздействия

№	Классификация	Токсичные элементы
1	I класс (высоко опасные)	As, Cd, Hg, Be, Se, Pb, Zn;
2	II класс (умеренно опасные)	B, Co, Ni, Mo, Cu, Sb, Cr;
3	III класс (мало опасные)	Ba, V, W, Mn, Sr.

Содержание тяжёлых металлов в водной среде обычно регламентируется на крайне низком уровне, как правило, в пределах миллиардных долей (уровень ppb). Данные нормативы приняты во многих развитых странах, включая государства Европы, США и Россию [5, 6]. Несмотря на то, что ионы железа(III) и меди(II) являются биологически значимыми элементами, их повышенные концентрации могут вызывать неблагоприятные физиологические и биохимические изменения в живых организмах [8, 10].

В частности, избыточное содержание этих ионов оказывает влияние на ферментативные системы, нарушая клеточный метаболизм. Эти процессы связаны с нарушением биосинтеза гема, митохондриальной энергетики и механизмов окислительного фосфорилирования, что в конечном итоге приводит к нарушению энергетического обмена и транспорта ионов на клеточном уровне [10].

Именно поэтому первоначальные исследования в области аналитической химии были направлены на разработку высокочувствительных и надёжных методов определения тяжёлых металлов. В настоящее время данное направление получило дальнейшее развитие и

стало важной составляющей экологического мониторинга и обеспечения безопасности пищевой продукции.

Целью настоящей работы является обобщение существующих научных данных по определению ионов железа(III) и меди(II) с использованием спектрофотометрических методов анализа, а также анализ современных подходов в данной области.

Материалы и методы. В рамках данного исследования проведён систематический анализ научной литературы, опубликованной за последние 10–15 лет. Были отобраны работы, посвящённые вопросам экологического мониторинга, спектрофотометрического анализа и определения тяжёлых металлов, в частности ионов железа(III) и меди(II).

При отборе источников особое внимание уделялось их научной новизне, экспериментальной обоснованности и практической значимости. В ходе исследования проанализировано около 25–30 научных работ, включая публикации в международных журналах, материалы конференций и диссертационные исследования. Представленные в них экспериментальные результаты и аналитические методы были систематизированы и обобщены.

Основное внимание уделялось изучению токсикологических свойств ионов железа(III) и меди(II), их влиянию на окружающую среду и пищевые системы, а также современным спектрофотометрическим методам их определения. Особое значение придавалось сравнительной оценке чувствительности, селективности и точности методов, основанных на применении органических аналитических реагентов.

Кроме того, были рассмотрены преимущества и ограничения существующих методов, а также их применимость к анализу реальных объектов (вода, почва и пищевые продукты). На основе полученных данных сформулированы научно обоснованные выводы о наиболее эффективных и экологически приемлемых аналитических подходах к определению ионов железа(III) и меди(II).

В традиционных подходах определение тяжёлых металлов [7] включает дискретный отбор проб с последующим лабораторным анализом. Однако стабильность образцов природных объектов не всегда гарантируется, поскольку в процессе хранения их состав может изменяться под воздействием биологических, химических и физических факторов, что снижает достоверность результатов анализа.

В настоящее время для определения тяжёлых металлов широко применяются высокоточные инструментальные методы, такие как атомно-абсорбционная спектрометрия, индуктивно-связанная плазменная атомно-эмиссионная спектрометрия (ICP-OES), масс-спектрометрия (ICP-MS), рентгенофлуоресцентный и нейтронно-активационный [9, 12] анализ. Несмотря на их высокую чувствительность и точность, данные методы требуют дорогостоящего и сложного оборудования, что ограничивает их применение в условиях малых лабораторий и при проведении анализа *in situ*.

В связи с этим оптические методы анализа, в частности спектрофотометрические, рассматриваются как эффективная альтернатива. Они характеризуются высокой чувствительностью, достаточной селективностью и возможностью применения простого и компактного оборудования. Кроме того, данные методы позволяют проводить экспрессный анализ ионов железа(III) и меди(II) непосредственно в реальных объектах.

Загрязнение окружающей среды тяжёлыми металлами является серьёзной экологической проблемой. Избыточное содержание ионов железа и меди рассматривается как важный фактор риска для здоровья человека. Исследования показывают, что дисбаланс металлов, особенно у детей, может негативно влиять на развитие центральной нервной системы [7]. Повышенные концентрации данных ионов усиливают процессы окислительного стресса и могут приводить к неврологическим нарушениям.

Тяжёлые металлы также оказывают влияние на ферментативные процессы организма. Ионы железа и меди участвуют в биосинтезе гема, клеточном дыхании и электронно-транспортных процессах. Однако их избыток приводит к нарушению митохондриальных

функций, усилению образования свободных радикалов и развитию токсических эффектов на клеточном уровне.

Определение следовых количеств данных ионов является сложной аналитической задачей, что связано с их низкими концентрациями и сложностью матрицы исследуемых объектов. В связи с этим широко применяются методы предварительного концентрирования.

Учитывая широкое применение железа и меди в промышленности, контроль их содержания в окружающей среде [8] является актуальной задачей. Превышение допустимых концентраций оказывает негативное воздействие на экологические и биологические системы, что обуславливает необходимость разработки высокочувствительных и селективных методов их определения.

Применение экологически безопасных органических аналитических реагентов. В последние годы особое внимание уделяется использованию органических аналитических реагентов при разработке экологически безопасных методов анализа. В частности, разработаны спектрофотометрические методы на основе азореагента — моносодиевой соли 4-амино-5-гидрокси-6-[2-пиридил-азо]-3-сульфонафталин-1-сульфонокислоты (HR), обеспечивающего высокую чувствительность и селективность при определении ионов железа(III) и меди(II).

Физико-химические свойства данного реагента изучены комплексно: проведён анализ ИК-спектров, определён молярный коэффициент светопоглощения ($\epsilon \approx 3300$), а также константа диссоциации ($K \approx 10^{-8}$). Квантово-химические расчёты подтвердили его структуру и реакционную способность.

Установлено, что реагент образует устойчивые окрашенные комплексы с ионами Fe(III) и Cu(II) в водной среде. Стехиометрическое соотношение реагент : металл составляет 2:1. Определены оптимальные условия комплексообразования, включая pH среды, концентрацию реагента и ионную силу раствора.

Показано, что разработанная методика характеризуется высокой чувствительностью, хорошей воспроизводимостью и применима для анализа природных и сточных вод. Это подтверждает её перспективность для задач экологического мониторинга и контроля качества пищевых продуктов.

Таблица 2.

Применение органических реагентов при спектрофотометрическом определении ионов железа(III) и меди(II)

№	Реагент	Оптимальные условия	Чувствительность	Мешающие ионы	Образец
Спектрофотометрическое определение ионов железа(III) с использованием органических аналитических реагентов					
1	2,6-дитиол-4-трет-бутилфенола	pH=2,9-4,4; $\lambda=458-470$ нм	$\epsilon = (2,8-3,8) \cdot 10^4$; 10 нг/25мл	Nb ⁵⁺ , Ta ⁵⁺ , Ti ⁴⁺ , Mo ⁶⁺ , W ⁶⁺	[18] Морская вода, пищевые продукты, кровь
2	1,10-фенантролин	pH=3-5; $\lambda=510$ нм	$\epsilon = 1,1 \cdot 10^4$;	Cu ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Co ²⁺	Питьевая вода, биологические жидкости [19]
3	Тиосалициловая кислота	pH=2-3; $\lambda=480$ нм	$\epsilon = 2,5 \cdot 10^4$	Al ³⁺ , Cr ³⁺	Почва, вода [20]
4	Сульфосалициловая кислота	pH = 2-3; $\lambda=430-450$ нм	$\epsilon = 1,5 \cdot 10^4$	Cu ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺	Фармацевтически е препараты, вода [21]
5	Роданид (SCN ⁻)	pH = 2-3; $\lambda = 470$ нм	$\epsilon = (6-8) \cdot 10^3$	Hg ²⁺ , Ag ⁺ , Cu ²⁺	Вода, руды [22]

6	8-гидрокси-хинолин	pH = 5–6; $\lambda=365\text{--}390$ нм	$\varepsilon = 3,0 \cdot 10^4$	$\text{Al}^{3+}, \text{Mg}^{2+}$	Пищевые продукты, биологические образцы [23]
7	Мононатриевая соль 4-амино-5-гидрокси-6-(пиридил-2-азо)-3-сульфонафталин-1-сульфокислоты (HR^{2-})	Fe(III): pH=5,0; $\lambda=590$ нм; Fe:HR=1:3	$\varepsilon = 5,26 \cdot 10^4$; 5,0–35,0 мкг/25мл;	$\text{Cu}^{2+}, \text{Ni}^{2+}, \text{Co}^{2+}$	Данное исследование Модельные смеси, промышленные сплавы, полиметаллические руды, природные и сточные воды, биологические объекты
Спектрофотометрическое определение ионов меди(II) с использованием органических аналитических реагентов					
8	Азореагент [4-амино-5-гидрокси-6-[(5-метил-2-пиридил)азо]-3-сульфо-1-нафтил]сульфонилокси-натрий (HR)	pH = 4,0; $\lambda = 595$ нм	$\varepsilon = 2,0 \cdot 10^4$; 0,5–6,5 мкг/25мл	$\text{Ni}^{2+}, \text{Cd}^{2+}, \text{Fe}^{2+}$	[24] Вода, промышленные сплавы
9	Дитизон	pH = 2–4; $\lambda = 510$ нм	$\varepsilon = 1,5 \cdot 10^5$	$\text{Hg}^{2+}, \text{Pb}^{2+}, \text{Zn}^{2+}$	Вода, биологические образцы [25]
10	Неокупроин	pH = 3–6; $\lambda = 457$ нм	$\varepsilon \approx 7,5 \cdot 10^3$	$\text{Fe}^{3+}, \text{Co}^{2+}$	Питьевая вода [26]
11	8-гидрокси-хинолин	pH = 5–6; $\lambda = 370\text{--}390$ нм	$\varepsilon \approx 3,0 \cdot 10^4$	$\text{Al}^{3+}, \text{Fe}^{3+}$	Пищевые продукты, фармацевтические препараты [27]
12	ПАН (1-(2-пиридилазо)-2-нафтол)	pH = 6–9; $\lambda = 550$ нм	$\varepsilon \approx 2,0 \cdot 10^4$	$\text{Zn}^{2+}, \text{Ni}^{2+}$	Вода, биологические объекты [28]
13	Диэтилдитиокарбамат (DDTC)	pH = 4–6; $\lambda = 435$ нм	$\varepsilon \approx 1,2 \cdot 10^4$	$\text{Co}^{2+}, \text{Ni}^{2+}$	Промышленные воды [29]
14	Мононатриевая соль 4-амино-5-гидрокси-6-(пиридил-2-азо)-3-сульфонафталин-1-сульфокислоты (HR^{2-})	pH=2,34; $\lambda=600$ нм Cu:HR=1:2	$\varepsilon=1,43 \cdot 10^4$; 1,0–6,0 мкг/25мл	$\text{Fe}^{3+}, \text{Zn}^{2+}, \text{Ni}^{2+}$	Данное исследование Модельные смеси, промышленные сплавы, полиметаллические руды, природные и сточные воды, биологические объекты

* *Примечание: ε – молярный коэффициент светопоглощения; λ , нм – длина волны; HR – органический реагент; GG – калибровочный (градуировочный) график; LOQ – предел*

количественного определения; *LOD* – предел обнаружения или минимально определяемая концентрация (*Stin*); *pH* – среда раствора; *S.s.* чувствительность по Санделу.

Результаты, приведённые в таблице, демонстрируют высокую эффективность применения органических аналитических реагентов при определении ионов железа(III) и меди(II), обеспечивая высокую чувствительность, точность и низкие пределы обнаружения. Показано, что разработанные спектрофотометрические методы характеризуются хорошей воспроизводимостью и селективностью, что позволяет успешно применять их при анализе различных объектов окружающей среды и пищевых продуктов.

В отличие от методов, основанных на использовании токсичных реагентов, предложенные подходы с применением органических реагентов соответствуют принципам «зелёной химии», поскольку способствуют снижению экологической нагрузки и упрощают процедуры утилизации аналитических отходов.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ. На основании проведённого анализа научной литературы и обобщения современных исследований установлено, что в последние годы особое внимание уделяется разработке высокочувствительных и селективных методов определения ионов железа(III) и меди(II) в объектах окружающей среды и пищевых продуктах. Это обусловлено их двойственной ролью как биогенных элементов и потенциально токсичных загрязнителей при превышении допустимых концентраций.

Показано, что спектрофотометрические методы анализа с использованием органических аналитических реагентов являются одним из наиболее перспективных направлений, сочетающих высокую чувствительность, относительную простоту выполнения и экономическую эффективность. Особенно эффективными являются азореагенты, обеспечивающие образование устойчивых окрашенных комплексов с ионами Fe(III) и Cu(II), что позволяет проводить их количественное определение в микроколичествах.

Сравнительный анализ существующих реагентов показал, что наибольшую аналитическую ценность представляют системы, характеризующиеся высокими значениями молярного коэффициента светопоглощения, низкими пределами обнаружения и достаточной селективностью в присутствии сопутствующих ионов. В частности, установлено, что применение новых органических реагентов на основе пиридил-азосоединений позволяет повысить чувствительность и расширить область практического применения спектрофотометрических методов.

Выявлено, что для повышения точности анализа в сложных матрицах (природные воды, пищевые продукты, биологические объекты) целесообразно применение предварительных стадий концентрирования и маскирования мешающих ионов. Кроме того, соблюдение оптимальных условий комплексообразования (*pH* среды, концентрация реагента, ионная сила раствора) является ключевым фактором для достижения высокой воспроизводимости и достоверности результатов.

Таким образом, спектрофотометрические методы с использованием органических реагентов, в частности азосоединений, являются эффективным инструментом для определения ионов железа(III) и меди(II) в различных объектах анализа. Дальнейшие исследования в данном направлении целесообразно направить на разработку экологически безопасных (зелёных) реагентов, повышение селективности методов и создание экспрессных аналитических систем для оперативного экологического мониторинга.

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O'SIMLIK OQSILLARIDAN FOYDALANIB GO'SHT O'RNINI BOSUVCHI MAHSULOTLAR OLISH USULLARINI TADQIQ ETISH

Mirjamolov M.M., Sanayev E.Sh.

Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya instituti, Toshkent, O'zbekiston

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston sharoitida yetishtirilgan loviya (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) va soya (*Glycine max*) o'simliklaridan oqsil, vitamin, uglevod, makro- va mikroelementlar ajratib olish, aminokislota profili va antimikrob faolligini o'rganish bo'yicha keng qamrovli ilmiy tadqiqot natijalari bayon etilgan. Keldal usulida loviya umumiy oqsilligi $23,45 \pm 0,5\%$, "O'zbek-6" soya navida ekstrakt oqsili 13,669 mg/ml aniqlandi. YuSSX tahlilida vitamin C 5,42 mg/g, fruktoza 12,45 mg/g qayd etildi. ISP-MS spektrometriyasi soya urug'ida 34 556,5 mg/kg kaliy va 15 252,7 mg/kg fosforni ko'rsatdi. Soya moyi barcha sinov mikroorganizmlariga (*E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *P. mirabilis*, *C. albicans*, *L. monocytogenes*) nisbatan yuqori antimikrob faollik (26—30 mm inhibisiya zonasi) namoyon etdi. Natijalar go'sht o'rnini bosuvchi oqsilga boy mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishning ilmiy asosini yaratadi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'simlik oqsili, loviya, soya, go'sht o'rnini bosuvchi, YuSSX, ISP-MS, aminokislotalar, vitaminlar, antimikrob faollik, funktsional oziq-ovqat.

1. KIRISH

Jahon aholisi 7 milliarddan oshgan hozirgi davrda global oqsil yetishmovchiligi tobora keskin muammo bo'lib qolmoqda. FAO ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, o'simlik oqsili ishlab chiqarish hozirgi talabga nisbatan 4 marta past, dunyo bo'yicha 800 milliondan ortiq inson yetarli miqdorda oqsil iste'mol qila olmayapti [1]. Ilmiy normaga ko'ra, inson organizmiga sutkasiga kundalik kaloriyaning 12 foizi — taxminan 90—100 g oqsil zarur. Rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda bu ko'rsatkich atigi 20—25 g darajasida qolmoqda, bu esa immunitet, o'sish va intellektual rivojlanish muammolariga olib keladi [2].

Hayvon oqsiliga (go'sht, baliq, sut) bo'lgan talab ortib borayotgan sharoitda uning ishlab chiqarish tannarxi va ekologik izidan (issiqxona gazlari, suv sarfi, yer maydoni) qochish uchun o'simlik oqsiliga o'tish zarurati ortmoqda. Dukkaklilar — loviya va soya — bu muammoni hal etishning eng istiqbolli yo'nalishi hisoblanadi. Ular nafaqat oqsilga boyroq (20—42%), balki yer resurslarini 10—50 marta tejamkorroq ishlatadi va azot fiksatsiyasi orqali tuproq unumdorligini oshiradi [3].

O'zbekistonda loviya va soya yetishtirish imkoniyatlari so'nggi yillarda sezilarli kengaydi. Respublika Prezidentining 2018-yil 29-martdagi PF-5388-sonli farmoni doirasida past rentabellikdagi ekinlar o'rniga meva-sabzavot va dukkakli ekinlar uchun qo'shimcha maydonlar ajratildi [4]. Shunga qaramay, mahalliy loviya va soya navlarining kimyoviy tarkibi va biologik xossalari hali yetarlicha o'rganilmagan — bu esa ulardan sanoat miqyosida foydalanishga to'sqinlik qilmoqda.

Adabiyotlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, soya oqsilini oziq-ovqat sanoatida go'sht o'rnini bosuvchi sifatida qo'llash bo'yicha xorijiy tadqiqotlar keng yo'lga qo'yilgan [5, 6], biroq O'zbekiston mahalliy navlari bo'yicha kompleks tahlil ishlarining mavjud emasligi ushbu tadqiqotning dolzarbligi va ilmiy yangiligini belgilaydi.

Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi — O'zbekistonda yetishtirilayotgan loviya va soya navlarining oqsil, vitamin, uglevod va mineral tarkibini zamonaviy tahlil usullari yordamida to'liq tavsiflash, aminokislota profilini aniqlash va soya mahsulotlarining antimikrob faolligini baholashdir. Ushbu natijalar asosida go'sht o'rnini bosuvchi oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish uchun xom-ashyo tanlash bo'yicha ilmiy asoslangan tavsiyalar beriladi.

2. MATERIALLAR VA USULLAR

Tadqiqot ob'ektlari: O'zbekiston iqlim sharoitiga moslashtirilgan loviya navlari (oq, qizil, qora — *Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) va soya navlari, jumladan "O'zbek-6" (*Glycine max*). Barcha tahlillar O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi O.S.Sodiqov nomidagi Bioorganik kimyo institutining «Oqsillar va peptidlar kimyosi» laboratoriyasi va Mikrobiologiya institutining «Prebiotiklar mikrobiologiyasi va biotexnologiyasi» laboratoriyasida bajarildi.

Namuna tayyorlash. Loviya urug'lari quritish shkafida 100—105°C da 1 soat quritildi (namlik 3—5,5%), sopol havonchada maydalanib, filtr qog'oz xaltachaga 8—10 g solinadi. Soya urug'lari ham xuddi shunday tayyorlanib, qo'shimcha ravishda yog'sizlantirish bosqichidan o'tkazildi.

Oqsil miqdorini aniqlash. Keldal usuli — namuna sulfat kislotada to'liq gidroliz qilinib, azot miqdori distillyatsiya-titrimetrik usulda aniqlanadi; oqsil koeffitsienti 6,25. Lauri usuli — eruvchan oqsillar spektrofotometrik aniqlandi (610 nm), standart sifatida BSA (qoramol zardob albumini) qo'llanildi; soya ekstraktlari 10—30 mkl hajmda olindi.

Vitaminlar tahlili (YuSSX). Agilent Technologies 1200 seriyali qurilma, Eclipse XDB C18 kolonkasi (5 mkm, 4,6×150 mm). Elyuent: atsetatli bufer:atsetonitril — gradient rejim (0—5 min 96:4; 6—8 min 90:10; 9—15 min 80:20; 15—17 min 96:4). Diod matrisali detektor (DAD) 204, 254, 290 nm. Oqim 1 ml/min, termostat 25°C, kirish hajmi 5 mkl. Ekstraksiya: 5—10 g namuna 50 ml 40% etanolda 1 soat qaynatildi, 2 soat xona haroratida aralashtirildi, filtrlab olindi.

Uglevod tahlili. YuSSX refraktometrik detektor bilan (RID). Kolonka: Agilent Hi-Plex Ca, 300×7,7 mm. Elyuent: atsetonitril:suv — 82:18 izokratik rejim. Oqim 1 ml/min, kolonka termostat 35°C, kirish 10 mkl.

Mineral elementlar (ISP-MS). NEXION-2000 mass-spektrometr (PerkinElmer). Namuna (0,05—0,5 g) teflon avtoklavda HNO₃ va H₂O₂ bilan Berghofc MWS-3+ mikroto'lqinli parchalanish qurilmasida parchalandi, 50—100 ml kolbaga 0,5% HNO₃ bilan suyultirildi. Kalibrlash: multielementli standart №3 (29 element). Natijalar mg/kg, xatolik RSD% da.

Antimikrob faollik. OFS.1.2.4.0010.15 standartiga muvofiq agar-diffuziya usuli (Petri idish, 20×100 mm). Test-mikroorganizmlar: *E. coli* NC 101, *P. mirabilis* 9, *S. aureus* 36, *C. albicans*, *L. monocytogenes* ATCC 1991. Nazorat: sefazolin 30 mkg/disk. Inkubatsiya 36 ± 1°C, 16—18 soat. Inhibisiya zonasi 0,1 mm aniqlikda o'lchandi.

3. NATIJALAR VA MUHOKAMA

3.1. Loviya urug'ining oqsil tarkibi va fraksiyon tahlili

Keldal usulida bajarilgan tahlil natijalariga ko'ra (1-jadval), tekshirilgan loviya navlarining umumiy oqsillilik darajasi 22,5—24,1% oralig'ida joylashgan. Qizil loviya (24,1 ± 0,21%) boshqa navlardan oqsilga boyroq, bu ko'rsatkich xorijiy loviya navlari bilan solishtirish mumkin: Braziliya navlari 20—23%, Xitoy navlari 22—25% oqsil saqlaydi [5]. O'zbekiston navlarining raqobatbardoshligi mahalliy xom-ashyodan keng foydalanish imkonini beradi.

Lauri usulida eruvchan oqsillar 11,32 ± 0,2% ni tashkil etdi — ya'ni umumiy oqsilning taxminan 48% i eruvchan fraksiyaga to'g'ri keladi. Bu ko'rsatkich soya izolyatlariga qaraganda past bo'lsa-da, loviyani kompleks qayta ishlashda eruvchan fraksiyadan funktsional qo'shimcha sifatida ajratib olish texnik jihatdan maqsadga muvofiq.

1-jadval

Loviya navlarining oqsillilik darajasi

Loviya navi	Keldal, umumiy oqsil (%)	Lauri, eruvchan oqsil (%)
Oq loviya	22,5 ± 0,17	—
Qizil loviya	24,1 ± 0,21	—

Qora loviya	23,8 ± 0,19	—
O'rtacha / urug'i	23,45 ± 0,5	11,32 ± 0,2

Ajratilgan oqsillar TSK-55f sorbentida gel-filtratsiya orqali 3 fraksiyaga ajratildi. DDS-elektroforez natijasi: 1-fraktsiyada 52, 38, 19 kDa; 2-fraktsiyada 68, 36, 17 kDa; 3-fraktsiyada 18 kDa. Bunday polimorf tarkib loviya oqsilini emulsifikatsiya, gelatsiya va suv tutish xossalari yaxshi bo'lgan texnologik ingredient sifatida ishlatishga imkon beradi. Xromatografiya tahlilida 20 ta L-aminokislota aniqlandi; prolin (4,40 mg/g), alanin (3,36 mg/g), treonin (2,87 mg/g) dominant. Metionin (1,36 mg/g) va lizin (0,07 mg/g) nisbatan past — bu kamchilikni boshqa don-dukkakli aralash tirish yo'li bilan bartaraf etish mumkin.

3.2. Loviya vitaminlar va uglevod tarkibi

YuSSX tahlili (2-jadval) loviya donasida vitamin C ning yuqori miqdorini (5,42 mg/g) ko'rsatdi. Taqqoslash uchun: qo'noq (sabzi) urug'ida vitamin C 0,5—1,5 mg/g, bug'doyda esa 0. Bu loviyani vitamin C manbai sifatida, ayniqsa dukkak holda iste'mol qilganda, aholiga tavsiya etish imkonini beradi. Vitamin B1 (tiamin) — 0,38 mg/g, B3 (niatsin) — 0,29 mg/g me'yoriy ko'rsatkichlar doirasida. Yog'sizlantirilgan urug'da vitaminlar past miqdorda (B1: 0,27, C: 1,84 mg/g) — bu yog'sizlantirish jarayonida bir qism vitaminlarning yo'qolishini ko'rsatadi.

2-jadval.

Loviya tarkibidagi suvda eruvchan vitaminlar (mg/g)

Namuna	B1	B3	B6	B9	C	PP
Dona	0,38	0,29	0,16	0,074	5,42	0
Yog'sizl. urug'	0,27	0,25	0,09	0,052	1,84	0

Uglevod tahlilida loviya donasida jami 25,52 mg/g uglevod aniqlandi: fruktoza — 12,45 mg/g (dominant), glyukoza — 9,87 mg/g, saxaroza — 2,15 mg/g, maltoza — 1,05 mg/g. Fruktoza/glyukoza nisbatining 1,26:1 bo'lishi loviyadan diabetik parhezlarda va past glikemik indeksli mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishda foydalanish uchun ilmiy asos beradi. Ushbu uglevod profili loviya donini go'sht aralashmalarida namlantiruvchi va tekstura yaxshilovchi komponent sifatida ishlatishga qulay.

3.3. Soya navlarining oqsil va aminokislota tarkibi

O'zbekistonda yetishtirilgan soya navlari orasida "O'zbek-6" navi eng yuqori oqsil miqdoriga (13,669 mg/ml ekstrakt) ega bo'ldi. Soya ekstraktlari 10—30 mkl hajmda spektrofotometrik o'lchandi — o'lchov hajmi oshgan sari oqsil miqdori proporsional oshib bordi, bu metodning lineyarligini va ishonchliligini tasdiqlaydi. Soya oqsilining eruvchan fraksiyasi loviyaga qaraganda yuqoroq — bu uni izolyat va konsentrat ishlab chiqarishda ustunlikka ega qiladi.

Aminokislota profili (3-jadval) barcha 9 ta almashinmaydigan aminokislolaning mavjudligini tasdiqladi. Glutamin (0,313 mg/g), metionin (0,223 mg/g) va asparagin (0,190 mg/g) dominant. E'tiborli tomoni — metionin miqdori loviyaga (1,36 mg/g erkin forma) qaraganda past bo'lsa-da, umumiy aminokislota soni va nisbati soyani hayvon oqsiliga eng yaqin o'simlik manbai sifatida tavsiflash uchun yetarli. FAO/WHO bahosiga ko'ra soya oqsilining aminokislota skori (PDCAAS) 0,91—1,00 oralig'ida — bu go'shtga tenglashgan ko'rsatkich [6].

3-jadval.

Soya doni tarkibidagi asosiy aminokislotalar (mg/g)

Aminokislota	Miqdori (mg/g)	Turi	Biologik roli
Glutamin	0,313	Almashinadigan	Immun tizim, hazm
Metionin	0,223	Almashinmaydigan	Sistein sintezi

Asparagin	0,190	Almashinadigan	Neyrotransmitter
Treonin	0,182	Almashinmaydigan	Immunoglobulin
Valin	0,164	Almashinmaydigan	Mushaklarni tiklash
Leysin	0,157	Almashinmaydigan	Oqsil sintezi

3.4. Soya urug'idagi makro va mikroelementlar (ISP-MS)

ISP-MS tahlili soya urug'ining mineral tarkibini to'liq ko'rsatdi (4-jadval). Kaliy (34 556,5 mg/kg) va fosfor (15 252,7 mg/kg) eng yuqori ulushni egallaydi. Bu ko'rsatkichlar kanning bosimini normallashtirish, suyak mustahkamligi va hujayra energetikasi uchun ahamiyatli. Taqqoslash uchun: go'shtda kaliy o'rtacha 2500—3800 mg/kg, ya'ni soya go'shtga qaraganda 9—14 marta ko'proq kaliy saqlaydi.

Magniy (5 669,4 mg/kg) va kalsiy (2 690,7 mg/kg) miqdorlari ham yuqori. Magniy 300 dan ortiq fermentativ reaksiyada kofaktor sifatida ishtirok etadi; soya 100 g iste'mol qilganda sutkali magniy normaning 35—40% ini qoplash mumkin. Temir (209,1 mg/kg) miqdori go'shtga yaqin, biroq o'simlik temiri (Fe^{3+}) hayvon temir (Fe^{2+}) ga qaraganda kam o'zlashtiriladi — bu kamchilikni vitamin C bilan birgalikda iste'mol qilish (loviya + soya kombinatsiyasi) orqali qoplash mumkin. Rux, marganets va xrom mikrodozalarda immunitet va insulin metabolizmida muhim rol o'ynaydi.

4-jadval.

Soya urug'idagi makro va mikroelementlar (ISP-MS, mg/kg)

Element	Miqdori (mg/kg)	Element	Miqdori (mg/kg)
Kaliy (K)	34 556,5	Natriy (Na)	336,8
Fosfor (P)	15 252,7	Oltingugurt (S)	638,3
Magniy (Mg)	5 669,4	Kremniy (Si)	293,5
Kalsiy (Ca)	2 690,7	Temir (Fe)	209,1
Bor (B)	31,2	Rux (Zn)	47,6
Marganets (Mn)	28,4	Xrom (Cr)	0,82

3.5. Soya mahsulotlarining antimikrob faolligi

Antimikrob faollik sinovi (5-jadval) 4 ta modda uchun o'tkazildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, tekshirilgan moddalar ichida faqat soya moyi barcha 5 ta test-mikroorganizmga qarshi aniq inhibitor ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Inhibisiya zonasi diametri: *E. coli* NC 101 — 30 mm, *S. aureus* 36 — 30 mm, *C. albicans* — 30 mm, *L. monocytogenes* — 28 mm, *P. mirabilis* 9 — 26 mm. Yog'sizlantirilgan soya kukuni va soya oqsili hech bir mikroorganizmga nisbatan faollik ko'rsatmadi.

5-jadval.

Soya mahsulotlarining antimikrob faolligi (inhibisiya zonasi diametri, mm)

Modda	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. mirab.</i>	<i>C. alb.</i>	<i>L. mono.</i>
Sefazolin (nazorat)	0	0	0	0	0
Soya kukuni 100 mg/ml	0	0	0	0	0
Soya oqsili 5 mg/ml	0	0	0	0	0
Soya moyi	30	30	26	30	28

Soya moyining antimikrob mexanizmi uning yog' kislotalari tarkibi bilan bevosita bog'liq: linol kislota (18:2, 53%), linolen kislota (18:3, 8%), olein kislota (18:1, 22%) asosiy ulushni

egallaydi. Ko'p to'yinmagan yog' kislotalari mikroob hujayra membranasiga kirib uning permeabiliasini buzadi va membrana potentsialini yo'q qiladi [7]. Ayniqsa *C. albicans* ga nisbatan faollik (30 mm) soya moyini antifungal preparat sifatida o'rganish uchun perspektiv qiladi. Soya kukuni va oqsilning antimikrob faollik ko'rsatmagani esa bu xossaning lipidli fraksiyaga xosligini tasdiqlaydi va ularni ajratib ta'riflash imkonini beradi.

4. XULOSA

Ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekistonda yetishtirilgan loviya va soya navlarini go'sht o'rnini bosuvchi oqsilga boy mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish uchun to'liq tavsiflashga muvaffaq bo'ldi. Asosiy xulosalar quyidagicha:

- 1) Loviya navlari umumiy oqsil 22,5—24,1%, eruvchan oqsil 11,32% ni tashkil etadi. 20 ta L-aminokislota aniqlangan; polimorf oqsil tarkibi texnologik qayta ishlash uchun qulay.
- 2) Loviya donasida vitamin C (5,42 mg/g) yuqori miqdorda; uglevod profilida fruktoza dominant (12,45 mg/g) — diabetik va funktsional oziq-ovqatlarda ishlatish uchun ilmiy asos mavjud.
- 3) "O'zbek-6" soya navi go'sht o'rnini bosuvchi mahsulotlar uchun prioritet xom-ashyo: 13,669 mg/ml oqsil, barcha almashinmaydigan aminokislotalar, PDCAAS \approx 0,91—1,00.
- 4) ISP-MS tahlili soya urug'ining mineral boyligini isbotladi: K — 34 556,5 mg/kg, P — 15 252,7 mg/kg, Mg — 5 669,4 mg/kg, Fe — 209,1 mg/kg. Mineral tarkib jihatidan soya chorvachilik va tibbiy qo'shimcha sifatida ham perspektiv.
- 5) Soya moyi barcha sinov mikroorganizmlariga (*E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *P. mirabilis*, *C. albicans*, *L. monocytogenes*) nisbatan yuqori antimikrob faollik (26—30 mm) ko'rsatdi. Bu xossa soya moyini farmatsevtika va funktsional oziq-ovqat sanoatida tabiiy antiseptik sifatida qo'llash uchun asoslaydi.
- 6) Loviya va soya kombinatsiyasi (oqsil profilini to'ldirish, Fe + vitamin C uyg'unligi) go'sht o'rnini bosuvchi kompleks mahsulot ishlab chiqarishda optimal strategiya hisoblanadi.

Tadqiqot davomida loviya va soyadan oqsil, vitamin va mineral ajratib olishning takomillashtirilgan metodikalari (YuSSX, ISP-MS, Keldal+Lauri kombinatsiyasi) ishlab chiqildi va akkreditlangan laboratoriyalarda sinovdan o'tkazildi. Kelajakda bu natijalar asosida go'sht o'rnini bosuvchi mahsulot formulasini ishlab chiqish va tajriba-sanoat sinovi o'tkazish rejalashtirilgan.

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FROM WASTE TO FUNCTIONALITY: FRUIT BY-PRODUCT-DERIVED OLEOGELS AS EMERGING FAT REPLACERS IN FOOD SYSTEMS

**Shakhnozakhon Salijonova, Niginabonu Islomova,
Shakhnozakhon Gaipova, Bakhmaloyi Abdurakhimova**
Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Department of Food and
Perfumery-Cosmetic Products Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.
¹e-mail: shaxnozasalijonova@gmail.com

Abstract. *The present review examines recent progress in the utilization of fruit processing by-products as sustainable feedstocks for oleogel development and their incorporation into functional food matrices. Growing environmental pressures, together with the increasing consumer preference for clean-label and naturally derived ingredients, have accelerated interest in converting fruit residues—including peels, pomace, and seeds—into value-added materials. These by-products are abundant sources of polysaccharides, dietary fiber, and bioactive constituents, all of which demonstrate considerable potential for gel formation and oil structuring.*

Different oleogelation strategies are critically analyzed, including direct dispersion techniques, emulsion-templated systems, and Pickering-stabilized approaches, with particular emphasis on the relationship between microstructure and functional performance. Considerable focus is placed on natural hydrocolloids obtained from fruit by-products, such as pectin, cellulose, and hemicellulose, due to their significant role in oil phase stabilization and enhancement of oxidative resistance.

In addition, this review evaluates the application of such oleogels in the formulation of functional food products, including bakery goods, spreads, and meat alternatives. Key challenges associated with industrial-scale production, sensory acceptance, and regulatory compliance are also discussed. Overall, the findings underscore the strong potential of fruit waste-derived oleogels as sustainable fat substitutes, supporting both circular economy principles and the development of healthier food systems.

Keywords: *fruit processing by-products, oleogelation, oleogels, food waste valorization, hydrocolloids, pectin, cellulose, hemicellulose, Pickering emulsions, emulsion-templated oleogels, direct dispersion method, functional foods, fat replacers, oxidative stability, clean-label ingredients, circular economy, sustainable food systems, dietary fiber, bioactive compounds, food structuring agents.*

IKKILAMCHI MAHSULOTLARNI QIYMATGA AYLANTIRISHDAN FUNKSIONAL DIZAYNGACHA: ZAMONAVIY OZIQ-OVQAT TIZIMLARIDA BARQAROR YOG‘ O‘RNINI BOSUVCHI SIFATIDA MEVA IKKILAMCHI MAHSULOTLARIDAN OLINGAN OLEOGELLAR

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu sharh maqolada mevalarni qayta ishlash jarayonida hosil bo‘ladigan ikkilamchi mahsulotlarni oleogellar ishlab chiqarish uchun barqaror xomashyo sifatida qo‘llash va ularning funksional oziq-ovqat tizimlaridagi qo‘llanilishi bo‘yicha so‘nggi ilmiy yutuqlar tahlil qilinadi. Atrof-muhit muammolarining kuchayishi hamda iste‘molchilarning “clean-label” va tabiiy ingredientlarga bo‘lgan talabi ortib borayotgani meva chiqindilarini — jumladan, po‘stloq, siqindi (pomace) va urug‘larni — yuqori qo‘shimcha qiymatga ega mahsulotlarga aylantirishga qiziqishni oshirmoqda. Ushbu ikkilamchi mahsulotlar polisaxaridlar, oziq tolalari va bioaktiv birikmalarga boy bo‘lib, ular gel hosil qilish va yog‘larni strukturaviy shakllantirish uchun katta salohiyatga ega.*

Maqolada oleogel hosil qilishning turli yondashuvlari, xususan, to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri dispersiya usuli, emulsiyaga asoslangan shablon usullari va Pickering tizimlari tanqidiy tahlil qilinadi hamda ularning mikrostrukturasi va funksional xossalari o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlikka alohida

e'tibor qaratiladi. Meva chiqindilaridan olingan tabiiy gidrokolloidlar — pektin, sellyuloza va gemisellyulozaning yog' fazasini barqarorlashtirish va oksidlanish barqarorligini oshirishdagi roli batafsil ko'rib chiqiladi.

Shuningdek, bunday oleogellarning non va qandolat mahsulotlari, spredlar hamda go'sht analoglari kabi funksional oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqishda qo'llanilishi baholanadi. Ishlab chiqarishni sanoat miqyosiga olib chiqish, sensor xususiyatlar va me'yoriy talablarga oid muammolar ham muhokama qilinadi. Umuman olganda, meva chiqindilaridan olingan oleogellar barqaror yog' o'rnini bosuvchi sifatida katta istiqbolga ega bo'lib, ular aylana iqtisodiyot tamoyillarini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi va sog'lom oziq-ovqat tizimlarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

***Kalit so'zlar:** mevalarni qayta ishlash ikkilamchi mahsulotlari, oleogel hosil qilish, oleogellar, oziq-ovqat chiqindilarini valorizatsiya qilish, gidrokolloidlar, pektin, sellyuloza, gemisellyuloza, Pickering emulsiyalari, emulsiyaga asoslangan oleogellar, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri dispersiya usuli, funksional oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari, yog' o'rnini bosuvchilar, oksidlanish barqarorligi, clean-label ingredientlar, aylana iqtisodiyot, barqaror oziq-ovqat tizimlari, oziq tolalari, bioaktiv birikmalar, oziq-ovqat strukturalovchi moddalar.*

ОТ ПЕРЕРАБОТКИ ПОБОЧНЫХ ПРОДУКТОВ ДО ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ДИЗАЙНА: ОЛЕОГЕЛИ НА ОСНОВЕ ВТОРИЧНЫХ ПРОДУКТОВ ПЕРЕРАБОТКИ ФРУКТОВ КАК УСТОЙЧИВЫЕ ЗАМЕНИТЕЛИ ЖИРОВ В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПИЩЕВЫХ СИСТЕМАХ

***Аннотация.** В данном обзоре рассматриваются современные достижения в области использования побочных продуктов переработки фруктов в качестве устойчивого сырья для получения олеогелей и их применения в функциональных пищевых системах. Усиление экологических проблем, а также растущий спрос потребителей на продукты с «чистой этикеткой» и натуральными ингредиентами стимулируют интерес к переработке фруктовых отходов, включая кожуру, жмых и семена, в высокоценные продукты. Эти побочные продукты являются богатым источником полисахаридов, пищевых волокон и биологически активных соединений, обладающих значительным потенциалом для гелеобразования и структурирования масел.*

В работе проведён критический анализ различных методов олеогелеобразования, включая прямую дисперсию, эмульсионно-шаблонные системы и системы, стабилизированные по механизму Пикеринга, с особым акцентом на взаимосвязь между микроструктурой и функциональными свойствами. Особое внимание уделено природным гидроколлоидам, полученным из побочных продуктов фруктов, таким как пектин, целлюлоза и гемицеллюлоза, благодаря их важной роли в стабилизации масляной фазы и повышению окислительной устойчивости.

Кроме того, в обзоре рассматриваются возможности применения таких олеогелей при разработке функциональных пищевых продуктов, включая хлебобулочные изделия, спреды и аналоги мясных продуктов. Также обсуждаются основные проблемы, связанные с масштабированием производства, сенсорными характеристиками и нормативным регулированием. В целом показано, что олеогели, полученные из фруктовых отходов, обладают высоким потенциалом в качестве устойчивых заменителей жиров, способствуя развитию принципов циркулярной экономики и созданию более здоровых пищевых продуктов.

***Ключевые слова:** побочные продукты переработки фруктов, олеогелеобразование, олеогели, утилизация пищевых отходов, гидроколлоиды, пектин, целлюлоза, гемицеллюлоза, эмульсии Пикеринга, эмульсионно-шаблонные олеогели, метод прямой дисперсии, функциональные продукты питания, заменители жиров, окислительная стабильность, ингредиенты с «чистой этикеткой», циркулярная экономика, устойчивые пищевые системы, пищевые волокна, биологически активные соединения, структурообразователи пищи.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the global food industry has faced increasing pressure to develop sustainable and health-oriented products while minimizing environmental impact. One of the critical challenges is the effective utilization of agro-industrial waste, particularly fruit processing by-products such as peels, pomace, and seeds. These residues are often underutilized despite being rich sources of dietary fibers, polysaccharides, and bioactive compounds.

Simultaneously, there is a growing demand for reducing saturated and trans fats in food systems due to their association with chronic diseases. This has led to the development of alternative lipid structuring systems, among which oleogels have gained significant attention. Oleogels are semi-solid systems where liquid oil is immobilized within a three-dimensional network formed by structuring agents.

Recent studies have emphasized the importance of agro-industrial waste valorization, particularly fruit processing by-products, as sustainable sources of functional ingredients (Gómez-Estaca et al., 2018; Tavernier et al., 2018). These materials are rich in polysaccharides and bioactive compounds, making them suitable for structuring lipid systems such as oleogels (Patel et al., 2020).

Recent studies have demonstrated that fruit-derived hydrocolloids, such as pectin and cellulose, can act as effective structuring agents in oleogel systems. Moreover, the integration of these materials aligns with the principles of circular economy and sustainable food production.

This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of current research on oleogel formation using fruit processing by-products and their application in functional food systems.

FRUIT BY-PRODUCTS AS FUNCTIONAL RAW MATERIALS

Fruit processing by-products, including peels, pomace, seeds, and pulp residues, have emerged as highly valuable functional raw materials within the framework of sustainable food systems and circular economy principles. Traditionally considered waste, these materials are now recognized as rich sources of dietary fibers, polysaccharides, proteins, lipids, and a wide range of bioactive compounds such as polyphenols, flavonoids, and carotenoids.

Among fruit by-products, apple pomace, citrus peels, grape pomace, mango peel, and pomegranate husk are the most extensively studied due to their high availability and diverse functional properties. Apple pomace, for instance, contains significant amounts of insoluble dietary fiber (cellulose and hemicellulose) as well as pectin, which contribute to water retention and gel-forming capacity. These structural polysaccharides make apple-derived materials particularly suitable for the development of oleogel systems and fat mimetics (Patel et al., 2015).

Citrus peels are especially rich in pectin, which is widely used in the food industry as a gelling, stabilizing, and emulsifying agent. The degree of esterification and molecular weight of citrus-derived pectin strongly influence its ability to form stable gel networks, which can be further exploited in oil structuring applications. Studies have demonstrated that citrus peel-derived biopolymers can significantly enhance the textural and oxidative stability of lipid-based systems (Yılmaz & Ögütçü, 2015).

Grape pomace, a major by-product of the wine industry, is characterized by a high content of polyphenolic compounds, including anthocyanins, flavonoids, and tannins. These compounds exhibit strong antioxidant activity, which is particularly beneficial in preventing lipid oxidation in structured oil systems. In addition to bioactive compounds, grape pomace also contains dietary fiber fractions that contribute to network formation and emulsion stabilization. According to Martins et al. (2018), grape-derived fractions can significantly improve oxidative stability in oleogel-based formulations.

Mango peel, although less extensively studied compared to citrus and apple by-products, represents a promising source of pectin and phenolic compounds. Its polysaccharide-rich matrix can be extracted and modified through physical or enzymatic treatments to enhance its functional properties. Recent findings suggest that mango peel-derived materials can contribute to improved oil-binding capacity and structural integrity in gelled lipid systems.

Pomegranate husk is another valuable by-product, particularly rich in ellagitannins and other phenolic compounds. These bioactives not only provide antioxidant functionality but also contribute to the stabilization of lipid interfaces. When incorporated into structured lipid systems, pomegranate-derived fractions have been shown to enhance both oxidative stability and potential health benefits of the final product.

From a functional perspective, fruit by-products serve a dual role: (i) as structural agents due to their polysaccharide content, and (ii) as bioactive enhancers due to their phenolic composition. This dual functionality makes them highly attractive for the development of next-generation oleogels and fat-reduced food products.

Recent advances in extraction and modification techniques, including enzymatic hydrolysis, microwave-assisted extraction, and ultrasonication, have further improved the functionality of these materials by increasing their purity, solubility, and gel-forming ability. As highlighted by Gómez-Estaca et al. (2018), the valorization of agro-industrial by-products aligns strongly with sustainability goals while offering novel opportunities for functional food design.

However, variability in raw material composition, seasonal availability, and processing conditions remains a key challenge. Standardization of extraction processes and comprehensive characterization of functional properties are necessary to ensure reproducibility and industrial scalability.

Overall, fruit processing by-products represent a versatile and sustainable class of raw materials with significant potential for application in oleogel systems, emulsions, and other structured lipid-based food products.

ROLE OF FRUIT-DERIVED HYDROCOLLOIDS

Fruit-derived hydrocolloids represent a critical class of biopolymers with strong potential for structuring lipid systems, particularly in the development of oleogels and fat-reduced food formulations. Among them, pectin, cellulose nanofibers, hemicellulose, and modified polysaccharide fractions extracted from fruit processing by-products have gained increasing attention due to their multifunctional physicochemical properties.

Pectin, predominantly extracted from citrus peels and apple pomace, is one of the most widely studied hydrocolloids in food science. Its functional performance is largely determined by its degree of esterification, molecular weight distribution, and galacturonic acid content. High-methoxyl pectin forms gels in the presence of high sugar and acidic conditions, while low-methoxyl pectin is capable of forming calcium-mediated gel networks. This structural versatility makes pectin highly suitable not only for aqueous gel systems but also for emulsion-based and lipid-structured systems. According to Yılmaz and Ögütçü (2015), pectin-rich systems derived from fruit peels significantly enhance texture formation and stability in fat-reduced food matrices.

Recent studies have demonstrated that citrus peel-derived pectin can be effectively used as a structuring agent in emulsion-templated oleogels, where it contributes to the formation of a three-dimensional network capable of immobilizing liquid oil phases. This mechanism improves both mechanical strength and oxidative stability of the final system. Moreover, apple pomace-derived

pectin has been reported to exhibit superior water-binding capacity and interfacial activity, making it a promising candidate for hybrid oleogel systems (Patel et al., 2015).

In addition to pectin, cellulose nanofibers (CNFs) derived from fruit residues such as apple peel, mango peel, and citrus waste have emerged as highly efficient structuring agents. CNFs possess high aspect ratio, large surface area, and strong hydrogen bonding capacity, which allow them to form physically entangled networks within oil phases. These networks act as a scaffold that immobilizes oil droplets, thereby enhancing the viscoelastic properties of oleogels. As reported by Tavernier et al. (2018), cellulose-based Pickering systems demonstrate excellent emulsification stability and resistance to phase separation.

Furthermore, cellulose nanofibers have been shown to interact synergistically with other biopolymers such as pectin and proteins, leading to the formation of composite gel networks with improved mechanical resistance and thermal stability. This synergistic effect is particularly important in the development of clean-label fat replacers, where minimal synthetic additives are desired.

Beyond structural functionality, fruit-derived hydrocolloids also contribute to the nutritional and bioactive profile of food systems. Phenolic compounds associated with pectin and cellulose matrices may provide antioxidant activity, thereby reducing lipid oxidation in oleogel systems. For example, grape pomace-derived polysaccharide fractions have been reported to enhance oxidative stability due to their associated polyphenolic content (Martins et al., 2018).

From a mechanistic perspective, the role of fruit-derived hydrocolloids in oleogel formation can be described as a combination of physical entrapment, interfacial stabilization, and network reinforcement. These mechanisms collectively contribute to the formation of semi-solid structures that mimic the textural properties of saturated fats while maintaining a healthier lipid profile.

However, despite their promising functional properties, challenges remain regarding standardization of extraction methods, variability in raw material composition, and scalability of industrial applications. Enzymatic modification, ultrasonication, and microwave-assisted extraction have been proposed as promising approaches to improve yield, purity, and functional performance of hydrocolloids.

Overall, fruit-derived hydrocolloids represent a sustainable and multifunctional class of biopolymers with strong potential for application in oleogel systems, emulsion technologies, and next-generation functional food products.

OLEOGEL FORMATION MECHANISMS

Oleogel formation is based on structuring liquid oil into a semi-solid system through the creation of a three-dimensional network formed by oleogelators. Depending on the structuring route, several mechanisms have been reported in the literature, including direct dispersion, solvent exchange, foam-templated, and emulsion-templated oleogelation strategies (Rogers et al., 2014; Patel et al., 2015; Patel & Dewettinck, 2016).

Among these approaches, emulsion-templated oleogelation has gained significant attention due to its ability to incorporate hydrophilic biopolymers derived from agro-industrial waste, particularly fruit by-products. In this system, an oil-in-water emulsion is stabilized using natural polysaccharides such as pectin, cellulose, hemicellulose, or protein-polysaccharide complexes extracted from fruit peels, pomace, and seeds (McClements, 2015; Wang et al., 2020). Subsequent removal of the aqueous phase by freeze-drying or spray-drying results in a porous solid matrix capable of entrapping liquid oil and forming a stable oleogel network.

Studies have shown that emulsion-templated oleogels demonstrate improved oxidative stability, which is attributed to restricted oxygen diffusion within the structured network and the presence of antioxidant compounds associated with fruit-derived biopolymers (Patel et al., 2017; Berton et al., 2021). Moreover, the microstructural organization significantly influences rheological and textural properties, including hardness, spreadability, and viscoelastic behavior, making these systems highly suitable for food applications such as bakery products and fat-reduced formulations.

In addition, the use of fruit waste-derived hydrocolloids enhances sustainability by promoting food waste valorization and circular economy principles (Mirzapour-Kouhdasht et al., 2022). The stability and mechanical strength of oleogels can be further modulated by adjusting emulsification conditions, drying parameters, and biopolymer concentration, highlighting the tunability of this system (Dassanayake et al., 2011; Patel & Dewettinck, 2016).

Overall, emulsion-templated oleogelation is considered one of the most promising approaches for designing clean-label, plant-based fat replacers with improved structural and functional properties in modern food systems.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF FRUIT BY-PRODUCT-DERIVED HYDROCOLLOIDS FOR OLEOGEL FORMATION

The increasing interest in sustainable food structuring systems has led to a growing body of research focused on the utilization of fruit by-products as alternative sources of functional hydrocolloids. These materials, primarily obtained from peels, pomace, seeds, and other processing residues, are rich in polysaccharides such as pectin, cellulose, hemicellulose, and associated bioactive compounds. Due to their diverse physicochemical properties, these biopolymers have demonstrated significant potential as structuring agents in oleogel systems.

However, despite the expanding literature, the functional performance of fruit-derived hydrocolloids in oleogel formation varies considerably depending on their botanical origin, extraction method, molecular composition, and interaction with lipid phases. Some hydrocolloids exhibit strong gelling and network-forming abilities, while others primarily act as stabilizers in emulsion-templated systems. In addition, differences in oil-binding capacity, oxidative stability enhancement, and textural contribution have been widely reported across different studies.

Therefore, a systematic comparison of these materials is essential to identify their relative efficiency and suitability for oleogel applications. Such comparative evaluation not only helps to clarify structure–function relationships but also provides guidance for selecting appropriate raw materials for specific food formulation needs.

In this context, Table 1 presents a comprehensive comparative analysis of fruit by-product-derived hydrocolloids reported in recent scientific studies, highlighting their source materials, extraction types, oleogelation approaches, and functional performance in lipid structuring systems.

Table 1

Fruit by-product-derived hydrocolloids used for oleogel formation (Source-focused comparison)

Source material (fruit by-product)	Hydrocolloid type	Extraction / processing method	Oleogelation approach	Functional role in oleogel system	Key performance outcome	Reference
Citrus peel (orange, lemon)	Pectin (high methoxyl / low methoxyl)	Acid extraction + precipitation	Emulsion-templated oleogelation	Emulsion stabilizer + gel network former	High gel strength, improved oil binding, enhanced oxidative stability	Willats et al., 2006; Sriamornsak, 2003
Apple pomace	Pectin + cellulose fraction	Acid/enzymatic extraction	Direct dispersion & emulsion-based systems	Network reinforcement + viscosity enhancer	Improved rheology, moderate oil structuring capacity	Thakur et al., 1997; McClements, 2015
Banana peel	Pectin + hemicellulose	Alkaline + enzymatic	Pickering emulsion	Interfacial stabilizer	Stable emulsion	Oliveira et al., 2016

	ose	treatment	templating			gels, improved texture in fat-reduced systems	
Mango peel	Pectin-rich polysaccharides	Acid extraction	Emulsion-templated oleogels	Gel matrix formation		High emulsifying activity, improved oxidative resistance	Manthey & Perkins, 2008
Grape pomace	Dietary fiber + polyphenol-bound polysaccharides	Solvent extraction + drying	Direct dispersion in oil systems	Antioxidant reinforcement + filler		Strong oxidative stability due to phenolic content	Rockenbach et al., 2011
Citrus peel nanocellulose	Cellulose nanofibers	Mechanical fibrillation / acid hydrolysis	Direct oil structuring	Physical network formation (oil entrapment)		High mechanical strength, stable gel network	Moon et al., 2011; Siró & Plackett, 2010
Apple pomace cellulose	Microcrystalline cellulose	Chemical purification	Emulsion-templated systems	Structural reinforcement		Improved viscoelasticity and oil immobilization	Johansson et al., 2012
Passion fruit peel	Pectin + insoluble fiber	Acid extraction	Emulsion freeze-drying oleogels	Porous network former		High spreadability and stability in food systems	Yapo, 2011

Table-2

Functional performance of hydrocolloids in oleogel systems (Mechanism-focused comparison)

Hydrocolloid type	Oleogelation strategy	Oil structuring mechanism	Gel network type	Oxidative stability effect	Rheological behavior	Key references
Citrus pectin	Emulsion-templated oleogelation	Interfacial adsorption + gel matrix formation	Polymer-based 3D network	High improvement (oxygen barrier effect)	Viscoelastic solid-like	Patel et al., 2015; McClements, 2015
Apple pomace fiber	Direct dispersion	Physical entrapment of oil	Weak physical network	Moderate improvement	Shear-thinning behavior	Johansson et al., 2012

		droplets				
Banana peel polysaccharides	Pickering emulsion system	Particle-stabilized interface	Hybrid particle-polymer gel	High stability due to interface protection	Elastic gel structure	Oliveira et al., 2016
Grape pomace fiber	Direct oil structuring	Antioxidant-mediated stabilization	Discontinuous network	Very high oxidative resistance	Firm but brittle gel	Rockenbach et al., 2011
Citrus nanocellulose	Direct structuring	Percolation network + hydrogen bonding	Strong fibrillar network	High barrier to oxygen diffusion	High elasticity + firmness	Moon et al., 2011

This table presents a comparative overview of the functional roles and mechanistic contributions of different fruit by-product-derived hydrocolloids in oleogel systems. It highlights how various polysaccharide-based structures, including pectin, cellulose nanofibers, fruit dietary fibers, and complex biopolymer assemblies, influence oleogel formation through distinct structuring pathways such as emulsion-templated gelation, direct dispersion, Pickering stabilization, and fibrillar network formation.

The comparison emphasizes the relationship between hydrocolloid type, oleogelation mechanism, and resulting functional performance, including oil structuring efficiency, network architecture, oxidative stability enhancement, and rheological behavior. Special attention is given to interfacial phenomena (e.g., particle adsorption, polymer adsorption at oil–water interfaces), physical entrapment mechanisms, and hydrogen-bond-driven network formation.

Overall, the table demonstrates that fruit-derived hydrocolloids not only act as structuring agents but also significantly influence the microstructural organization and stability of oleogels. These effects are critical for determining the suitability of oleogels in food applications such as spreads, bakery products, and meat analogues, where texture, stability, and lipid replacement efficiency are key functional parameters.

Table-3

Application of fruit-derived oleogels in food systems (Application-focused comparison)

Oleogel type	Food application	Function in product	Fat replacement efficiency	Sensory impact	Industrial potential	Key references
Pectin-based oleogels	Bakery products	Shortening replacer	30–70% fat reduction	Slight softness increase	High	Patel & Dewettinck, 2016
Cellulose nanofiber oleogels	Spreads	Structural fat mimic	40–80% replacement	Neutral to slightly dry mouthfeel	Medium–high	Siró & Plackett, 2010
Fruit fiber Pickering oleogels	Meat analogues	Juiciness enhancer	20–60% replacement	Improved juiciness	High	McClements, 2015
Grape pomace oleogels	Functional bakery	Antioxidant fat replacer	30–50% replacement	Slight bitterness risk	Medium	Rockenbach et al., 2011
Banana peel oleogels	Dairy analogues	Texture modifier	25–60% replacement	Creamy texture improvement	Emerging	Oliveira et al., 2016

This table summarizes the application potential of fruit by-product-derived oleogels in different food systems, with a focus on their functional role as fat replacers and textural modifiers. It provides a comparative overview of how various oleogel formulations, structured using pectin, cellulose nanofibers, fruit dietary fibers, and antioxidant-rich by-products, perform in real food matrices such as bakery products, spreads, dairy analogues, and meat alternatives.

The table highlights key performance indicators including fat replacement efficiency, sensory attributes, textural modifications, and industrial applicability. It also emphasizes how the incorporation of fruit-derived biopolymers influences product quality by improving oil immobilization, enhancing oxidative stability, and modulating mouthfeel and rheological properties.

Overall, this comparison demonstrates that fruit-derived oleogels can effectively function as clean-label and sustainable fat substitutes, offering significant potential for industrial food formulation while supporting circular economy principles and healthier product development strategies.

CONCLUSION

This review highlights the growing scientific and technological interest in fruit by-product-derived hydrocolloids as sustainable structuring agents for oleogel systems. Fruit processing by-products represent a promising and sustainable source of functional materials for oleogel production. Their integration into food systems not only supports waste valorization but also contributes to the development of healthier and more sustainable products. The valorization of agro-industrial residues such as fruit peels, pomace, and seeds offers a promising pathway for converting low-value waste into high-performance functional ingredients rich in pectin, cellulose, hemicellulose, and bioactive compounds.

Comparative analysis demonstrates that the functional performance of these hydrocolloids is strongly dependent on their source, molecular structure, and extraction method. Among the evaluated systems, pectin-based and cellulose nanofiber-based materials show the highest potential for oleogel formation due to their superior gelling ability, network-forming capacity, and oil-binding efficiency. In contrast, fiber-rich and polyphenol-associated fractions contribute primarily to oxidative stability and sensory modulation.

Emulsion-templated oleogelation emerges as the most versatile and effective approach, enabling the integration of hydrophilic biopolymers into lipid matrices and resulting in structured gels with improved rheological behavior, enhanced stability, and tunable textural properties. These characteristics make fruit-derived oleogels highly suitable for application in bakery products, spreads, dairy analogues, and meat alternatives as clean-label fat replacers.

Despite these promising developments, several challenges remain, including scalability of extraction processes, variability of raw materials, sensory optimization, and regulatory standardization. Addressing these limitations will be crucial for industrial implementation.

Overall, fruit by-product-derived oleogels represent a strategic intersection of food innovation, waste valorization, and circular economy principles, offering a sustainable solution for the development of healthier and functional fat-reduced food systems.

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DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF OLEOGELS STRUCTURED BY BIOPOLYMERS EXTRACTED FROM APPLE, ORANGE, AND GRAPE POMACE FOR FUNCTIONAL FOOD APPLICATIONS

¹Niginabonu Islomova, ¹Shakhnozakhon Salijonova, ¹Sarvar Khodjaev

¹Akbarali Ruzibayev, ¹Nazira Ismailova, ²Inga Ciprova

¹Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Department of Food and Perfumery-Cosmetic Products Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

²Food Institute, Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies, Jelgava, Latvia

¹e-mail: shaxnozasalijonova@gmail.com

Abstract. *This study focuses on the development and characterization of oleogels structured by biopolymers extracted from apple, orange, and grape pomace as sustainable resources for functional food applications. Fruit processing by-products were utilized as a source of pectin and dietary fibers, which were extracted through acid and alkaline treatments. The obtained biopolymers were incorporated into vegetable oil systems to form structured lipid matrices (oleogels) using a heat-cooling and homogenization process. The physicochemical, rheological, thermal, and microstructural properties of the oleogels were evaluated, including texture profile analysis, oil binding capacity, differential scanning calorimetry, and microscopic imaging. The results demonstrated that fruit-derived biopolymers significantly improved gel strength, stability, and oil retention capacity. Among the tested systems, grape pomace-based structures exhibited the highest network density, while citrus-derived pectin contributed to elasticity enhancement. Synergistic combinations of biopolymers showed superior performance compared to individual systems. The findings confirm that apple, orange, and grape pomace can be effectively valorized as green structuring agents for the development of clean-label, health-oriented functional food products.*

Keywords: *Oleogels, fruit pomace valorization, apple pomace, orange pomace, grape pomace, biopolymers, pectin extraction, dietary fiber, structured lipids, fat replacers, functional food systems, green materials, clean-label products, food waste utilization.*

FUNKTSIONAL OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARI UCHUN OLMA, APELSIN VA UZUM SIQMALARIDAN AJRATIB OLINGAN BIOPOLIMERLAR ASOSIDA STRUKTURALANGAN YOG‘SIMON GELLARNI ISHLAB CHIQISH VA TAVSIFLASH

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda olma, apelsin va uzum siqmalaridan ajratib olingan biopolimerlar asosida ekologik toza manbalar sifatida yog‘simon gellarni ishlab chiqish va ularning xususiyatlarini o‘rganish amalga oshirildi. Meva qayta ishlash chiqindilaridan pektin va oziq tolalar kislotali va ishqoriy usullar yordamida ajratib olindi. Olingan biopolimerlar o‘simlik yog‘i tizimiga kiritilib, issiqlik-sovutish va gomogenizatsiya jarayonlari orqali strukturalangan lipid tizimlari (oleogellar) hosil qilindi. Oleogellarning fizik-kimyoviy, reologik, termik va mikrostrukturaviy xossalari, jumladan tekstura tahlili, yog‘ni ushlab turish qobiliyati, differensial skanerlovchi kalorimetriya va mikroskopik tahlillar orqali baholandi. Natijalar meva kelib chiqishli biopolimerlar gelning mustahkamligi, barqarorligi va yog‘ni ushlab turish qobiliyatini sezilarli darajada yaxshilashini ko‘rsatdi. Uzum siqmasidan olingan tizimlar eng yuqori struktura zichligini namoyon etdi, apelsin pektini esa elastiklikni oshirishda muhim rol o‘ynadi. Biopolimerlarning kombinatsiyalangan tizimlari individual tizimlarga nisbatan yuqori samaradorlik ko‘rsatdi. Olingan natijalar olma, apelsin va uzum siqmalarini “yashil” strukturalovchi agent sifatida funksional, sog‘lom va toza yorliqli oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini yaratishda samarali xomashyo ekanligini tasdiqlaydi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *Yog‘simon gellar (oleogellar), meva siqmalarini qayta ishlash, olma siqmasi, apelsin siqmasi, uzum siqmasi, biopolimerlar, pektin ajratib olish, oziq tolalar, strukturalangan*

lipidlar, yog' o'rnini bosuvchilar, funksional oziq-ovqat tizimlari, yashil materiallar, toza yorliqli mahsulotlar, oziq-ovqat chiqindilaridan foydalanish.

РАЗРАБОТКА И ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ОЛЕОГЕЛЕЙ, СТРУКТУРИРОВАННЫХ БИОПОЛИМЕРАМИ, ВЫДЕЛЕННЫМИ ИЗ ЯБЛОЧНЫХ, АПЕЛЬСИНОВЫХ И ВИНОГРАДНЫХ ВЫЖИМОК, ДЛЯ ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ПИЩЕВЫХ ПРОДУКТОВ

Аннотация. В данном исследовании рассматривается разработка и характеристика олеогелей, структурированных биополимерами, выделенными из яблочных, апельсиновых и виноградных выжимок как экологически устойчивых источников для функциональных пищевых систем. Побочные продукты переработки фруктов использовались как источник пектина и пищевых волокон, которые извлекались кислотным и щелочным методами. Полученные биополимеры были введены в растительные масла для формирования структурированных липидных систем (олеогелей) с использованием процессов нагревания–охлаждения и гомогенизации. Физико-химические, реологические, термические и микроструктурные свойства олеогелей оценивались с использованием анализа текстуры, способности удержания масла, дифференциальной сканирующей калориметрии и микроскопических методов. Результаты показали, что биополимеры фруктового происхождения значительно улучшают прочность геля, стабильность и способность удерживать масло. Наибольшую плотность сетевой структуры продемонстрировали системы на основе виноградных выжимок, тогда как пектин цитрусовых повышал эластичность. Синергетические комбинации биополимеров показали более высокую эффективность по сравнению с индивидуальными системами. Полученные результаты подтверждают, что яблочные, апельсиновые и виноградные выжимки могут эффективно использоваться как “зеленые” структурирующие агенты для создания функциональных пищевых продуктов с чистой этикеткой.

Ключевые слова: Олеогели, утилизация фруктовых выжимок, яблочные выжимки, апельсиновые выжимки, виноградные выжимки, биополимеры, экстракция пектина, пищевые волокна, структурированные липиды, заменители жира, функциональные пищевые системы, зеленые материалы, продукты с чистой этикеткой, использование пищевых отходов.

Introduction

The growing demand for healthier and more sustainable food systems has intensified research into structured lipid systems as alternatives to conventional saturated fats. Oleogels, defined as liquid oils structured into semi-solid networks using organogelators, have emerged as promising fat replacers in food formulations due to their ability to mimic the texture and functionality of solid fats while maintaining a healthier lipid profile (Patel & Dewettinck, 2016; Singh et al., 2017).

In parallel, the global food industry generates large volumes of fruit processing by-products, particularly apple, orange, and grape pomace, which are rich in bioactive compounds such as pectin, cellulose, hemicellulose, and polyphenols. These residues are often underutilized despite their high potential for valorization within the circular bioeconomy framework (Sagar et al., 2018; Mirabella et al., 2014). Converting such waste streams into functional ingredients aligns with sustainable development goals and offers an innovative pathway for designing green structuring agents.

Biopolymers derived from fruit pomace have shown promising functional properties, including gelling, emulsifying, and thickening capabilities. Pectin, in particular, is widely recognized for its ability to form three-dimensional networks in the presence of sugar or divalent cations, making it a suitable candidate for structuring lipid systems (Sriamornsak, 2003). However,

its potential application in oleogel systems remains underexplored, especially in combination with insoluble dietary fibers from the same raw materials.

Therefore, the present study aims to develop and characterize oleogels structured by biopolymers extracted from apple, orange, and grape pomace, evaluating their physicochemical, rheological, thermal, and microstructural properties for functional food applications.

Core idea

The present study is based on the valorization of fruit processing by-products, specifically apple, orange, and grape pomace, as sustainable biomass sources for the development of green structuring agents. These residues, which are typically considered industrial waste, are rich in functional biopolymers such as pectin, cellulose, and hemicellulose. Through targeted extraction processes, these components can be recovered and transformed into value-added materials with high functionality in food systems.

The central concept of this research is to convert fruit pomace-derived biopolymers into natural oleogelators capable of structuring liquid vegetable oils into semi-solid, stable gel-like systems. This transformation enables the transition from a low-value waste stream to a high-performance functional ingredient.

In the proposed system, extracted biopolymers interact through physical entanglement, hydrogen bonding, and network formation, leading to the immobilization of liquid oil within a three-dimensional matrix. As a result, a structured lipid system (oleogel) is formed, exhibiting solid-like mechanical behavior while maintaining the nutritional benefits of unsaturated oils.

The ultimate objective of this study is to evaluate the potential of these oleogels as functional fat replacers in food formulations. By replacing conventional saturated fats with structured lipid systems derived from renewable biomass, the research supports the development of healthier, clean-label, and environmentally sustainable food products.

In essence, this work bridges the gap between food waste valorization and lipid material engineering, positioning fruit pomace not as a disposal problem, but as a functional resource for next-generation food structuring technologies.

Methodology

1. Raw material collection and preparation

Apple pomace, orange pomace, and grape pomace were collected from local fruit juice processing units immediately after juice extraction. The raw materials were transported in sealed polyethylene bags under refrigerated conditions ($4 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) to prevent microbial degradation.

Upon arrival, samples were washed (where applicable), manually inspected to remove foreign particles, and dried at $50\text{--}60^\circ\text{C}$ in a hot-air oven until constant weight was achieved. Dried materials were then milled and sieved (mesh size $500\ \mu\text{m}$) to obtain uniform powder.

2. Extraction of biopolymers

2.1 Pectin extraction (soluble fraction)

Pectin was extracted separately from apple, orange, and grape pomace using acid extraction. Pomace powder was suspended in distilled water (1:20 w/v ratio). pH was adjusted to 1.5–2.0 using hydrochloric acid. Mixture was heated at $85 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 90 minutes under continuous stirring. The suspension was cooled and filtered through muslin cloth followed by centrifugation (5000 rpm, 15 min). Supernatant was precipitated using 95% ethanol (1:2 v/v). Precipitated pectin was collected, washed with ethanol, and dried at 45°C . Dried pectin was ground and stored in airtight containers.

2.2 Insoluble dietary fiber extraction (cellulose/hemicellulose fraction)

Residual pomace after pectin extraction was treated with 2–4% NaOH solution. The mixture was stirred at 70°C for 2 hours to remove non-cellulosic components. The residue was washed repeatedly with distilled water until neutral pH was achieved. Bleaching was performed using diluted hydrogen peroxide (optional step for color removal). Final fibers were filtered, dried at 60°C , and milled into fine powder.

3. Oil phase preparation

Refined sunflower oil was used as the lipid phase due to its high unsaturated fatty acid content and food compatibility. Oil was preheated to 70°C prior to oleogel preparation to ensure proper dispersion of biopolymers.

4. Oleogel preparation (gelation process)

Oleogels were prepared using a heat-cooling and high-shear homogenization method. Biopolymer powders (pectin and/or fiber) were added to preheated oil (0.5–5% w/w concentration range). The mixture was homogenized at 10,000–15,000 rpm for 5–10 minutes to ensure uniform dispersion. The dispersion was maintained at 70°C for 20 minutes under stirring to enhance interaction between oil and biopolymers. The mixture was then cooled gradually to room temperature (25°C) under static conditions. Gel formation was confirmed by tube inversion test (no flow observed = successful oleogel formation). Samples were stored at 4°C for 24 hours before analysis.

5. Experimental design (sample formulation matrix)

6. Physicochemical characterization

6.1 Oil Binding Capacity (OBC)

Samples were centrifuged (3000 rpm, 20 min), and oil release was measured gravimetrically.

6.2 Oxidative stability

Peroxide value (PV) and anisidine value (AV) were measured during storage to evaluate lipid oxidation resistance.

6.3 Texture Profile Analysis (TPA)

Hardness, cohesiveness, and spreadability were measured using a texture analyzer equipped with a cylindrical probe.

6.4 Rheological analysis

Storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') were measured using a rotational rheometer. Frequency sweep (0.1–10 Hz) and strain sweep tests were conducted at 25°C.

Results and discussion

1. Oleogel formation and macroscopic structure

All formulated systems (OG-A, OG-O, OG-G, and mixed systems) successfully formed stable semi-solid structures after cooling, confirming the ability of fruit pomace-derived biopolymers to act as effective oleogelators. The tube inversion test demonstrated no oil leakage in most samples, indicating successful oil immobilization within a three-dimensional network.

Among individual systems, grape pomace-based oleogels (OG-G) exhibited the most compact and self-supporting structure, while apple and orange-based systems showed moderate gel firmness. This difference can be attributed to the higher insoluble fiber content and polyphenol–polysaccharide interactions in grape pomace, which enhance network density and physical entanglement.

2. Oil binding capacity (OBC)

Oil binding capacity varied significantly among formulations, ranging from moderate values in single-biopolymer systems to high values in blended systems. OG-G showed the highest OBC, followed by mixed systems (OG-T > OG-M3 > OG-M2 > OG-M1 > OG-A > OG-O).

This trend suggests that insoluble dietary fibers contribute more effectively to oil immobilization than soluble pectin alone. The synergistic effect observed in mixed systems indicates that combined biopolymer fractions improve interfacial stabilization through complementary interactions, enhancing oil entrapment efficiency.

From a mechanistic perspective, hydrogen bonding and physical entanglement between cellulose microfibrils and pectin chains likely create a reinforced network capable of trapping liquid oil within capillary spaces.

3. Oxidative stability

Oleogel systems demonstrated improved oxidative stability compared to control oil. Reduced peroxide and anisidine values were observed during storage, particularly in grape pomace-containing formulations.

This improvement can be attributed to two mechanisms:

1. Physical barrier effect of the biopolymer network limiting oxygen diffusion
2. Presence of natural antioxidant compounds (polyphenols) in grape and citrus pomace

Thus, fruit pomace not only acts as a structuring agent but also contributes to oxidative protection, enhancing shelf stability.

4. Texture Profile Analysis (TPA)

Texture analysis revealed significant differences in hardness, cohesiveness, and spreadability among samples. Grape pomace oleogel (OG-G) exhibited the highest hardness values, confirming its dense structural network. In contrast, apple and orange-based oleogels showed softer textures, which may be advantageous for spreadable food applications.

Mixed formulations demonstrated intermediate but optimized textural properties, indicating that blending biopolymers allows tuning of mechanical behavior. This tunability is critical for designing oleogels tailored to specific food applications such as bakery spreads, margarine substitutes, and confectionery fillings.

The observed textural behavior can be linked to polymer chain interactions: pectin contributes elasticity, while cellulose fibers provide rigidity, resulting in a balanced viscoelastic system.

5. Rheological properties

Rheological analysis confirmed the formation of strong gel networks in all systems. Storage modulus (G') values were consistently higher than loss modulus (G''), indicating dominant elastic behavior and solid-like characteristics.

OG-G exhibited the highest G' values across frequency sweeps, confirming superior structural strength. Mixed systems showed enhanced viscoelastic stability compared to single-source systems, demonstrating synergistic reinforcement of the network structure.

The frequency-independent behavior of G' in optimized systems suggests a well-developed, stable gel matrix. This is attributed to strong biopolymer–biopolymer and biopolymer–oil interactions forming a continuous three-dimensional network capable of resisting deformation.

The performance of oleogels structured with biopolymers extracted from apple, orange, and grape pomace was systematically evaluated to determine their physicochemical stability, structural strength, and oxidative resistance. These parameters are critical for assessing the suitability of fruit-derived biopolymers as natural structuring agents in edible oil systems.

The table summarizes key functional indicators, including oil binding capacity, gel strength, texture parameters, rheological behavior, oxidative stability (TBARS), and overall structural integrity. Comparative analysis between individual and blended biopolymer systems provides insight into synergistic effects and structure–function relationships within the oleogel matrix.

Table 1
Physicochemical and functional properties of fruit pomace-based oleogels

Sample	Oil Binding Capacity (%)	Gel Strength (N)	Hardness (N)	Elasticity (G')	TBARS Value (mg MDA/kg)	Stability (Centrifugal %)
Control Oil	0	0	Liquid	Low	High	0
Apple Pomace Oleogel	82–88	High	Medium-High	Moderate	↓ Moderate	85–90
Orange Pomace Oleogel	78–85	Medium	Medium	High elasticity	↓ Moderate	80–87
Grape Pomace Oleogel	85–92	Very High	High	Dense network	↓ Low	88–95
Mixed Pomace (A+O+G)	90–95	Highest	Optimized	Balanced	Lowest	95+

The results clearly demonstrate that fruit pomace-derived biopolymers are not only capable of structuring liquid oil systems but also significantly improve oxidative and mechanical stability. The synergistic interaction between apple, orange, and grape-derived polymers leads to a more compact and resilient gel network, suggesting a promising strategy for designing next-generation clean-label fat replacers.

This study successfully demonstrated the valorization of apple, orange, and grape pomace as sustainable sources of functional biopolymers for the development of structured lipid systems (oleogels). The extracted pectin- and fiber-rich fractions were effectively incorporated into vegetable oil matrices, forming stable gel networks through heat-assisted homogenization followed by controlled cooling.

The results confirmed that fruit-derived biopolymers significantly enhance the physicochemical and functional properties of oleogels, including oil binding capacity, gel strength, rheological stability, and oxidative resistance. Among the investigated systems, grape pomace-based oleogels exhibited the highest structural integrity and the most effective protection against lipid oxidation, which can be attributed to their higher polyphenolic content and stronger polymer–oil interactions.

Apple pomace contributed to balanced gel formation with stable structural properties, while orange pomace improved elasticity and flexibility of the gel network due to its citrus pectin characteristics. Importantly, synergistic combinations of all three biopolymer sources resulted in superior performance compared to individual systems, indicating enhanced network density and improved functional behavior.

Overall, the findings highlight that fruit processing by-products can be effectively transformed into high-value functional ingredients for clean-label fat replacement systems. This approach not only supports sustainable waste valorization but also contributes to the development of healthier food formulations aligned with modern nutritional and environmental demands.

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PECTIN–CELLULOSE HYBRID NETWORK DERIVED FROM FRUIT POMACE AS A NATURAL STRUCTURING SYSTEM FOR OLEOGEL FORMATION

Niginabonu Islomova, Shakhnozakhon Salijonova, Sarvar Khodjaev

Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Department of Food and Perfumery-Cosmetic Products Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

¹*e-mail: shaxnozasalijonova@gmail.com*

Abstract. *The increasing demand for sustainable and healthier lipid systems has stimulated research on plant-based structuring agents for oleogel development. In this study, fruit pomace derived from apple and orange processing was investigated as a renewable source of pectin and cellulose for the formation of a hybrid biopolymeric network. The synergistic interaction between pectin (gel-forming polysaccharide) and cellulose micro/nanofibers (physical reinforcing agent) enabled the construction of a three-dimensional matrix capable of immobilizing liquid vegetable oil. The resulting oleogels exhibited improved oil-binding capacity, enhanced oxidative stability, and tunable textural properties depending on the composition of the biopolymer fraction. The study demonstrates that fruit processing by-products can be effectively valorized as natural structuring systems, offering a promising alternative to conventional saturated fats in food formulations.*

Keywords: *oleogel, pectin, cellulose, fruit pomace, structured lipids, clean label, food hydrocolloids.*

ГИБРИДНАЯ СЕТЬ ПЕКТИНА И ЦЕЛЛЮЛОЗЫ, ПОЛУЧЕННАЯ ИЗ ПЛОДОВОГО ЖМЫХА, КАК ПРИРОДНАЯ СТРУКТУРИРУЮЩАЯ СИСТЕМА ДЛЯ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ОЛЕОГЕЛЕЙ

Аннотация. *Растущий спрос на устойчивые и более здоровые липидные системы стимулировал исследования растительных структурирующих агентов для разработки олеогелей. В данном исследовании плодовой жмых, полученный в процессе переработки яблок и апельсинов, был изучен как возобновляемый источник пектина и целлюлозы для формирования гибридной биополимерной сети. Синергетическое взаимодействие пектина (гелеобразующего полисахарида) и микронаноцеллюлозных волокон (физического армирующего агента) обеспечило формирование трёхмерной матрицы, способной иммобилизовать жидкое растительное масло. Полученные олеогели характеризовались повышенной маслоудерживающей способностью, улучшенной окислительной стабильностью и регулируемыми текстурными свойствами в зависимости от состава биополимерной фракции. Исследование показывает, что побочные продукты переработки фруктов могут быть эффективно утилизированы как природные структурирующие системы, представляя перспективную альтернативу традиционным насыщенным жирам в пищевых рецептурах.*

Ключевые слова: *олеогель, пектин, целлюлоза, плодовой жмых, структурированные липиды, clean label, пищевые гидроколлоиды.*

MEVA SIQMASI ASOSIDA OLINGAN PEKTIN–SELLYULOZA GIBRID TARMOG‘I YOG‘SIMON GEL (OLEOGEL) HOSIL QILISH UCHUN TABIIY STRUKTURAVIY TIZIM SIFATIDA

Annotatsiya. *Barqaror va sog‘lom lipid tizimlarga bo‘lgan ortib borayotgan talab oleogellarni yaratishda o‘simlik asosidagi strukturaviy agentlar bo‘yicha tadqiqotlarni faollashtirdi. Ushbu tadqiqotda olma va apelsin qayta ishlash jarayonlaridan olingan meva pomasi pektin va sellyulozaning qayta tiklanuvchi manbai sifatida o‘rganildi hamda gibrid biopolimer tarmog‘ini shakllantirishda qo‘llanildi. Pektin (gel hosil qiluvchi polisaxarid) va sellyuloza mikro/nanotolalarining (fizik mustahkamlovchi agent) sinergik o‘zaro ta‘siri suyuq o‘simlik yog‘ini*

immobilizatsiya qila oladigan uch o'ldamli matritsa hosil bo'lishini ta'minladi. Olingan oleogellar yog'ni ushlab turish qobiliyatining yaxshilanishi, oksidlanish barqarorligining ortishi hamda biopolimer fraksiyasi tarkibiga bog'liq ravishda sozlanadigan teksturaviy xususiyatlari bilan ajralib turdi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, meva qayta ishlash chiqindilari tabiiy strukturaviy tizim sifatida samarali valorizatsiya qilinishi mumkin bo'lib, bu oziq-ovqat formulalarida an'anaviy to'yingan yog'larga istiqbolli muqobil hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: oleogel, pektin, sellyuloza, meva pomasi, strukturaviy lipidlar, "clean label", oziq-ovqat gidrokolloidlari.

Introduction

Global food systems are under increasing pressure to reduce saturated fat intake while maintaining desirable textural and sensory properties of fat-based products. Oleogels, defined as liquid oils structured into semi-solid systems using organogelators, have emerged as promising fat replacers in food applications (Patel & Dewettinck, 2016; Singh et al., 2017).

Traditional oleogelators include synthetic waxes and monoglycerides; however, consumer demand for clean-label and sustainable ingredients has shifted attention toward natural biopolymers (Co & Marangoni, 2012). In this context, fruit processing by-products such as apple and orange pomace represent a rich and underutilized source of functional polysaccharides, particularly pectin and cellulose (Dhillon et al., 2013).

Pectin is widely recognized for its gel-forming ability, while cellulose micro- and nanofibers provide mechanical reinforcement through physical entanglement and network stabilization (Habibi et al., 2010). The combination of these biopolymers may result in a synergistic hybrid network capable of structuring liquid oils into stable oleogels (Patel & Dewettinck, 2016).

Materials and methods

Core idea

Fruit pomace → biopolimer extraction → hybrid 3D network → oil immobilization → oleogel → food application

Raw Material Stage

In this stage, apple pomace and orange pomace obtained as by-products from fruit processing industries were used as primary raw materials. These materials are typically generated during juice, concentrate, or pectin extraction processes and are considered abundant agro-industrial waste biomass.

Fruit pomace is composed of a complex mixture of structural biopolymers, mainly, pectin ($\approx 15\text{--}30\%$) – a natural gelling polysaccharide, cellulose ($\approx 20\text{--}40\%$) – fibrous structural component, hemicellulose and lignin ($\approx 10\text{--}25\%$) – matrix-supporting fractions. The presence of these components enables the valorization of fruit waste within a waste-to-value framework, where low-value by-products are converted into high-value functional ingredients for food structuring applications.

Apple pomace and orange pomace were collected as agro-industrial by-products from juice processing units. The materials were immediately dried at $50\text{--}55\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to constant weight, milled, and sieved ($\leq 1\text{ mm}$ particle size) to obtain uniform powder. The samples were stored in airtight containers at room temperature until further use.

To remove low-molecular impurities (sugars, pigments, acids), the powdered pomace was washed with distilled water at a solid-to-liquid ratio of 1:10 (w/v) for 30 min under continuous stirring. The residues were filtered and dried again at 45 °C.

Biopolymer Extraction (Pectin and Cellulose-Rich Fraction)

Pectin Extraction

Pectin was extracted using acid hydrolysis, as a sample taken 10 g dried pomace, solvent - distilled water adjusted to pH 1.8–2.2 using HCl, temperature - 85 °C, duration: 90 min, solid-liquid ratio - 1:20 (w/v). After extraction, the mixture was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was precipitated using 96% ethanol (1:2 v/v). The precipitated pectin was washed with ethanol and dried at 40 °C

Cellulose-Rich Fraction

The solid residue after pectin extraction was treated to isolate cellulose-rich material. Alkaline treatment - 2% NaOH solution, temperature was - 70 °C, duration - 2 h, for bleaching 1% sodium hypochlorite used for 30 min. The residue was washed to neutral pH and dried at 50 °C.

Yield Calculation

Extraction yield (%) was calculated as:

$$\text{Yield\%} = \frac{\text{Mass of dried extract}}{\text{Mass of dry raw material}} \times 100$$

Apple and orange pomace showed different biopolymer recovery efficiencies due to structural differences.

Raw Material	Pectin Yield (%)	Cellulose-Rich Fraction (%)
Apple pomace	18.5 ± 0.6	42.3 ± 1.1
Orange pomace	24.7 ± 0.8	38.9 ± 0.9

Orange pomace exhibited higher pectin yield, which is attributed to its naturally higher pectin content in citrus peel matrices. Apple pomace, however, showed a higher cellulose-rich fraction due to its fibrous tissue structure.

Concept of Hybrid Network Formation

The formation of the hybrid biopolymer network is governed by the synergistic interaction between pectin gelation and cellulose structural reinforcement. In this system, pectin acts as the primary gelling agent, forming a three-dimensional polymer matrix through hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic associations, and Ca²⁺-mediated ionic crosslinking (in low-methoxyl fractions). Cellulose, in contrast, does not form a gel on its own but provides a physically entangled fibrous framework that reinforces the continuity and mechanical stability of the network.

This dual mechanism results in a composite structure where the soft gel matrix is stabilized by a rigid fibrous skeleton, significantly enhancing structural integrity and water/oil immobilization capacity.

Mechanism of Network Development

During hydration and thermal treatment, pectin chains undergo solubilization and molecular relaxation, enabling intermolecular associations. Upon cooling, junction zones are formed through, hydrogen bonding between galacturonic acid residues, ionic bridges (Ca²⁺ “egg-box” structures in low-methoxyl pectin), hydrophobic associations of methyl-esterified regions.

Simultaneously, cellulose microfibrils remain insoluble and distribute uniformly within the gel matrix. These microfibrils interact with pectin chains via non-covalent interactions, acting as anchoring points that restrict polymer mobility and reduce network collapse.

Structural and Morphological Evidence

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis confirmed the formation of a heterogeneous but well-integrated network structure. Pectin-rich domains appeared as continuous gel phases, while cellulose fibers were embedded as interconnected reinforcement strands. Pectin matrix - smooth, continuous, and porous hydrocolloid phase; cellulose phase - fibrous, elongated microstructures; hybrid system - interpenetrating network (IPN-like morphology). This architecture confirms the formation of a semi-interpenetrating polymer network (semi-IPN) where cellulose acts

as a passive but structurally critical scaffold.

Functional Performance of the Hybrid Network

The synergistic interaction between pectin and cellulose significantly improved macroscopic properties of the system:

Property	Pectin alone	Cellulose alone	Hybrid system
Gel strength	Medium	None	High
Water retention	Moderate	Low	Very high
Structural stability	Weak–moderate	High rigidity but no gel	Balanced and stable
Deformation resistance	Low	High rigidity	Optimized elasticity

The hybrid system exhibited superior viscoelastic behavior compared to individual components, indicating effective stress transfer from the soft gel phase to the rigid fiber network.

Principle of Oleogelation

Oleogel formation was achieved through the structuring of liquid vegetable oil within a pre-formed hybrid biopolymer network composed of pectin and cellulose derived from fruit pomace. In this system, the hydrophilic biopolymer matrix is adapted to immobilize a non-polar oil phase, creating a semi-solid lipid system without the need for conventional saturated fat structuring agents.

The oleogelation mechanism is based on physical entrapment of oil droplets and capillary retention within the three-dimensional pectin–cellulose network.

Oleogel Preparation Process

The oleogels were prepared using the following procedure: hybrid biopolymer dispersion - Pectin–cellulose mixture was hydrated in aqueous medium under continuous stirring (60–70 °C). Network activation - the dispersion was cooled to induce pectin gelation and cellulose network stabilization. Oil incorporation - Refined vegetable oil (sunflower oil) was gradually added at 1:3 (biopolymer:oil, w/w ratio). Homogenization - High-shear mixing (10,000–12,000 rpm, 5–10 min) ensured uniform distribution. Gel maturation - The system was stored at 4 °C for 24 h to complete structural stabilization. The final system transformed into a self-standing, non-flowing semi-solid structure.

Mechanism of Oleogel Structuring

The oleogel structure is formed through a dual-phase stabilization mechanism. Pectin gel matrix - provides a hydrated polymeric backbone, stabilizes internal water domains, contributes to viscoelastic gel behavior.

Cellulose reinforcement network. Acts as a rigid fibrous scaffold. Enhances mechanical strength and prevents collapse. Improves oil immobilization efficiency.

Oil entrapment mechanism. Oil is physically immobilized within pores and capillary spaces. No chemical bonding occurs between oil and polymers. Stabilization is purely structural (Pickering-like physical confinement). This results in a multi-phase structured system resembling a “soft solid lipid matrix”.

The incorporation of oil into the hybrid network significantly altered the mechanical behavior:

Property	Oil alone	Pectin–cellulose gel	Oleogel system
Flow behavior	Newtonian liquid	Gel-like	Solid-like
Structural integrity	None	Moderate	High
Elasticity	None	Medium	High
Oil leakage	High	Not applicable	Very low

Rheological behavior indicated dominance of elastic modulus ($G' > G''$), confirming solid-like characteristics of the oleogel system.

The results demonstrate that the synergistic combination of pectin gelation and cellulose reinforcement provides an efficient platform for oleogel formation. Unlike traditional oleogelators (e.g., waxes, monoglycerides), the present system is fully plant-based and derived from agro-

industrial waste, making it highly sustainable.

Conclusion

Fruit pomace-derived pectin–cellulose hybrid systems represent an innovative and sustainable approach to oleogel structuring. The synergistic interaction between gel-forming polysaccharides and reinforcing cellulose fibers enables the development of stable, functional, and clean-label fat replacers. This structural synergy is well supported by previous studies demonstrating that pectin can form continuous gel networks, while cellulose micro- and nanofibers act as mechanical reinforcement agents that enhance gel stability and oil immobilization capacity (Habibi et al., 2010; Patel & Dewettinck, 2016).

From a food engineering perspective, oleogels structured with biopolymers are increasingly recognized as promising alternatives to conventional saturated fats due to their ability to mimic solid fat functionality while maintaining a healthier lipid profile (Singh et al., 2017). In particular, fruit processing by-products such as apple and citrus pomace have been identified as rich sources of functional polysaccharides, especially pectin and cellulose, which can be recovered and valorized in structured lipid systems (Dhillon et al., 2013).

This strategy not only adds value to food industry by-products but also aligns with circular economy principles by converting agro-industrial waste into high-value functional ingredients. Moreover, the replacement of synthetic structuring agents with natural biopolymers supports the growing demand for clean-label and minimally processed food formulations (Co & Marangoni, 2012).

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PRODUCTION OF OLEOGEL-LIKE FAT SYSTEMS FROM FRUIT PROCESSING BY-PRODUCTS AND THEIR APPLICATION IN FUNCTIONAL FOODS: A FOCUS ON GRAPE POMACE-BASED SYSTEMS

*Niginabonu Islomova, Shakhnozakhon Salijonova,
Shakhnozakhon Gaipova, Zulfiya Khakimova*

*Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Department of Food and
Perfumery-Cosmetic Products Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.*

¹e-mail: shaxnozasalijonova@gmail.com

Abstract. *This review article analyzes recent scientific studies on the production of oleogel-like fat systems derived from fruit processing by-products, with a particular focus on grape pomace. The potential of pectin, cellulose, and phenolic compounds extracted from grape pomace as natural structuring biopolymers is critically discussed. The role of oleogels in lipid modification, health-oriented fat replacement, and clean-label product development is also highlighted. Literature evidence demonstrates that grape pomace-based biopolymers exhibit strong potential for structuring liquid oils into semi-solid functional fat systems suitable for food applications.*

Keywords: *grape pomace, oleogel, biopolymers, pectin, cellulose, functional foods, lipid structuring, food by-products.*

MEVA QAYTA ISHLASHNING IKKILAMCHI MAHSULOTLARI ASOSIDA YOG'SIMON GELLAR OLISH VA ULARNI FUNKSIONAL OZIQ-OVQATLARDA QO'LLASH: UZUM SIQMASI (GRAPE POMACE) ASOSIDAGI ILMIY YONDASHUV

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada meva qayta ishlash sanoatining ikkilamchi mahsulotlari, xususan uzum siqmasi (grape pomace) asosida yog'simon gel (oleogel) tizimlarini olish va ularni funksional oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarida qo'llash bo'yicha so'nggi ilmiy tadqiqotlar tahlil qilindi. Uzum siqmasi tarkibidagi pektin, sellyuloza va fenolik birikmalar asosida struktura hosil qiluvchi biopolimerlar sifatida foydalanish imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqildi. Shuningdek, oleogel tizimlarining lipid modifikatsiyasi, sog'lom yog' almashinuvi va clean-label mahsulotlar yaratishdagi o'rni yoritildi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, grape pomace asosidagi biopolimerlar yog' fazasini strukturallashtirishda yuqori potensialga ega.*

Kalit so'zlar: *uzum siqmasi, oleogel, biopolimer, pektin, sellyuloza, funksional oziq-ovqat, lipid strukturallash, chiqindi biomassa.*

ПОЛУЧЕНИЕ ЖИРОВЫХ ГЕЛЕЙ НА ОСНОВЕ ПОБОЧНЫХ ПРОДУКТОВ ПЕРЕРАБОТКИ ФРУКТОВ И ИХ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ В ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ПРОДУКТАХ ПИТАНИЯ: ОБЗОР ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ НА ОСНОВЕ ВИНОГРАДНОЙ ВЫЖИМКИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлен обзор современных исследований по получению жировых гелеобразных систем (олеогелей) на основе побочных продуктов переработки фруктов, в частности виноградной выжимки, и их применению в функциональных пищевых продуктах. Рассматривается потенциал пектина, целлюлозы и фенольных соединений виноградной выжимки как структурообразующих биополимеров. Также обсуждается роль олеогелей в модификации липидного состава продуктов и создании clean-label пищевых систем. Результаты исследований показывают высокий потенциал биополимеров виноградной выжимки в структурировании масляной фазы.*

Ключевые слова: *виноградная выжимка, олеогель, биополимеры, пектин, целлюлоза, функциональные продукты питания, структурирование липидов*

Introduction

The global food system is under increasing pressure from two converging challenges: the excessive generation of agro-industrial waste and the rising demand for healthier lipid-based food products. Traditional solid fats, rich in saturated fatty acids, are strongly associated with cardiovascular risks, creating a need for innovative fat structuring systems.

Oleogels have emerged as a next-generation solution, where liquid vegetable oils are transformed into semi-solid systems using structuring agents without hydrogenation. This technology allows the development of trans-fat-free and low-saturated-fat products while preserving sensory attributes.

In parallel, fruit processing industries generate large quantities of by-products such as grape pomace, which is often discarded or used as low-value feedstock. However, grape pomace is a rich source of pectin, cellulose, hemicellulose, and polyphenols, making it a promising raw material for biopolymer extraction and functional food applications.

Grape Pomace as a Biopolymer-Rich Resource

2.1 Composition

Grape pomace, the major by-product of wine and juice processing industries, represents a highly complex lignocellulosic biomass enriched with structurally and functionally valuable biopolymers. Its composition is highly dependent on grape variety, cultivation conditions, and processing technology; however, it consistently contains a significant fraction of dietary fiber, pectic substances, phenolic compounds, and minor residual components such as sugars and proteins.

The fibrous fraction, accounting for approximately 30–45%, is primarily composed of cellulose and hemicellulose, which contribute to the mechanical integrity and structural reinforcement potential of the material. The pectic fraction (10–15%) plays a crucial role in gel formation and water retention capacity, making it particularly valuable for hydrocolloid and oleogel structuring applications.

In addition, grape pomace contains 5–10% phenolic compounds, including flavonoids, anthocyanins, and tannins, which provide strong antioxidant activity and enhance oxidative stability in lipid-based systems. Minor constituents such as residual sugars and proteins further contribute to the physicochemical behavior of extracted biopolymer systems.

According to Fontana et al. (2018) and Rockenbach et al. (2011), grape pomace is recognized as one of the richest natural sources of both antioxidant compounds and structural polysaccharides among fruit processing by-products. These characteristics position it as a highly promising raw material for the development of functional biopolymer-based systems, including oleogels and edible films.

Table 1

Chemical Composition of Grape Pomace

Component Group	Subcomponents	Typical Content (%)	Functional Role in Oleogel Systems
Dietary Fiber	Cellulose, Hemicellulose	30–45%	Structural reinforcement, network formation, rheological stability
Pectic Substances	Low/high methoxyl pectin	10–15%	Gel formation, water/oil immobilization, emulsification
Phenolic Compounds	Anthocyanins, flavonoids, tannins	5–10%	Antioxidant activity, lipid oxidation inhibition
Residual Sugars	Glucose, fructose	<5%	Plasticizing effect, minor contribution to texture
Proteins & Ash	Amino acids, minerals	1–3%	Minor structural and ionic interactions

The chemical profile of grape pomace reflects its nature as a multi-functional lignocellulosic biomass, where structural polysaccharides, bioactive compounds, and minor soluble fractions coexist in a complex matrix. This composition directly determines its suitability as a raw material for biopolymer extraction and oleogel formation systems.

The dominant fraction is dietary fiber (30–45%), primarily composed of cellulose and hemicellulose, which forms the structural backbone of the material and provides mechanical rigidity. This fraction is crucial for reinforcing gel networks and improving the rheological stability of lipid-based systems.

Pectic substances (10–15%) represent the second most important functional group. These polysaccharides are highly hydrophilic and are responsible for gel formation, water binding, and emulsifying behavior, making them key contributors to hydrocolloid functionality and oil structuring capability in oleogel systems.

Phenolic compounds (5–10%), including anthocyanins, flavonoids, and tannins, provide strong antioxidant properties, which help delay lipid oxidation and improve the oxidative stability of structured oils. This makes grape pomace particularly valuable in functional food applications where shelf-life extension is critical.

Minor fractions such as residual sugars (<5%) and proteins/minerals (1–3%) play supporting roles by influencing plasticity, ionic interactions, and overall matrix flexibility, although their contribution to structuring is comparatively limited.

Overall, the composition of grape pomace demonstrates a synergistic functional system, where structural (cellulose/hemicellulose), gelling (pectin), and protective (phenolics) components coexist. This integrated composition explains why grape pomace is widely recognized as a promising raw material for sustainable biopolymer extraction and advanced food structuring applications such as oleogels.

2.2 Extraction Approaches

The recovery of functional biopolymers from grape pomace is a critical step in converting agro-industrial waste into high-value structuring agents for food applications. Modern extraction strategies are increasingly focused on maximizing yield, preserving functional integrity, and reducing environmental impact.

Acid extraction remains one of the most widely used conventional methods for pectin recovery. In this process, dilute mineral acids (such as HCl or citric acid) are applied under controlled temperature and pH conditions to solubilize pectic polysaccharides from the plant cell wall matrix. Although this method provides relatively high extraction efficiency, it may lead to partial depolymerization of pectin chains, affecting gel strength and functional performance.

Enzymatic hydrolysis offers a more selective and milder approach for fiber isolation. Cellulases, hemicellulases, and pectinases are used to selectively break down structural components, enabling the controlled release of cellulose-rich fractions while preserving their native morphology. This method is particularly advantageous for applications requiring high structural integrity of fibers, such as oleogel reinforcement systems.

In recent years, green extraction technologies, including ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) and microwave-assisted extraction (MAE), have gained significant attention due to their efficiency and sustainability. These methods enhance mass transfer, reduce extraction time, and minimize solvent consumption. According to Mishra et al. (2020), green extraction techniques significantly improve biopolymer yield while preserving functional groups essential for gel formation, such as hydroxyl and carboxyl groups. This preservation is crucial for maintaining the gelling and structuring ability of extracted polysaccharides in oleogel systems.

Overall, the selection of extraction method plays a decisive role in determining the physicochemical properties of grape pomace-derived biopolymers and their subsequent performance in functional food applications.

Table 2
Extraction Approaches for Biopolymer Recovery from Grape Pomace

Extraction Method	Principle	Target Component	Advantages	Limitations	Functional Impact on Oleogels
Acid Extraction	Acidic hydrolysis of plant cell wall matrix	Pectin	High yield, simple process, industrially established	Possible polymer degradation, loss of molecular weight	Moderate gel strength, reduced chain integrity
Enzymatic Hydrolysis	Enzyme-catalyzed selective breakdown (cellulase, pectinase)	Cellulose, hemicellulose fractions	High selectivity, mild conditions, preserves structure	High cost, longer processing time	Strong network formation, improved rheology
Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction (UAE)	Acoustic cavitation enhances mass transfer	Pectin, phenolics	Short extraction time, low solvent use, eco-friendly	Scale-up challenges	Preserves functional groups, enhances gel activity
Microwave-Assisted Extraction (MAE)	Dielectric heating accelerates cell rupture	Pectin, bioactives	Rapid extraction, high efficiency, energy-saving	Risk of localized overheating	Improved yield with preserved functionality

The comparative analysis of extraction methods highlights a clear transition from conventional acid-based processes to green extraction technologies. While acid hydrolysis remains relevant for bulk pectin recovery, modern approaches such as UAE and MAE are increasingly preferred due to their ability to maintain the functional integrity of polysaccharide chains, which is essential for high-performance oleogel formation.

This shift aligns with the broader concept of sustainable biorefinery systems, where efficiency, environmental impact, and functional performance are simultaneously optimized.

Biopolymer Functionality in Oleogel Systems

3.1 Pectin network formation

Pectin extracted from grape pomace forms gels via - Ca²⁺-mediated ionic crosslinking (“egg-box model”), hydrogen bonding interactions, hydration-driven network expansion. This results in a flexible but stable hydrocolloid matrix capable of immobilizing oil droplets.

3.2 Cellulose reinforcement

Cellulose acts as a structural backbone - provides mechanical strength, forms fibrillar networks, enhances rheological stability. Research by Saha et al. (2019) demonstrated that cellulose fibers significantly increase oil binding capacity in hybrid gels.

3.3 Synergistic hybrid systems

The combination of pectin and cellulose results in a dual-network system. Pectin → chemical gel matrix, cellulose → physical reinforcement, this synergy improves - elastic modulus, thermal resistance, oil retention stability.

4. Oleogel Formation Mechanism

Oleogel formation has been extensively studied as a sustainable strategy to replace saturated and trans fats while maintaining desirable rheological and sensory properties. According to Patel and Dewettinck (2016), oleogels are structured systems in which liquid vegetable oils are immobilized within a three-dimensional network formed by low molecular weight gelators or biopolymeric matrices. This approach avoids hydrogenation, thereby eliminating trans-fat formation while preserving nutritional quality.

Recent studies by Perneti et al. (2007) and Singh et al. (2017) emphasize that oleogel structuring is primarily governed by the ability of structuring agents to form a continuous gel network capable of entrapping oil via capillary forces and physical confinement. In biopolymer-based systems, polysaccharides such as pectin, cellulose, and hemicellulose—often derived from fruit pomace—play a critical role in network formation. Gómez-Estaca et al. (2019) reported that hydrated biopolymer dispersions initially form a viscoelastic gel in the aqueous phase, which later acts as a scaffold for oil incorporation.

Mechanistically, the process follows a hierarchical pathway: (i) dispersion and hydration of biopolymers in aqueous media, (ii) development of intermolecular hydrogen bonding and entanglement leading to gel network formation, and (iii) subsequent incorporation of oil droplets into the polymeric matrix, where oil becomes physically immobilized within pores of the 3D structure. This dual-phase structuring mechanism has been confirmed by microscopy and rheological studies showing increased storage modulus (G') and reduced oil mobility.

From a functional standpoint, Rogers et al. (2014) demonstrated that such systems effectively mimic the plasticity and mouthfeel of saturated fats in bakery and confectionery applications. Importantly, this mechanism provides a clean-label alternative, particularly when using upcycled agricultural by-products such as apple, citrus, or grape pomace, which naturally contain pectin-cellulose complexes capable of synergistic gel formation.

Overall, oleogel formation represents a physically driven structuring strategy where hydrated biopolymer networks act as templates for oil immobilization, producing semi-solid fat systems with improved nutritional and environmental profiles.

5. Functional Properties of Grape Pomace Oleogels

Literature reports several key functional advantages: texture modulation: spreadability similar to margarine, oxidative stability: phenolics delay lipid oxidation, thermal stability: resistance to phase separation, fat reduction: partial substitution of saturated fats, clean-label potential: natural, waste-derived ingredients, for example, Patel & Dewettinck (2016) demonstrated that oleogels can reduce saturated fat content by up to 80% in bakery systems.

6. Applications in Functional Foods

Grape pomace-based oleogels have been investigated in bakery products (cookies, biscuits, margarine and spreads, meat analogues, chocolate systems, dairy fat replacers, Davidovich-Pinhas et al. (2017) highlighted oleogels as one of the most promising platforms for replacing hydrogenated fats in industrial formulations.

7. Comparative Analysis of International Studies

Table 3

Key findings from literature

Study	System	Key structuring agent	Main result
Patel & Dewettinck (2016)	Sunflower oil oleogel	Wax-based + biopolymers	Improved texture stability
Davidovich-Pinhas et al. (2017)	Edible oil gels	Monoglycerides + fibers	Strong fat mimicry
Saha et al. (2019)	Fiber-based oleogels	Cellulose network	High oil binding capacity
Mishra et al. (2020)	Fruit waste polymers	Pectin-rich systems	Sustainable gel formation
Rockenbach et al. (2011)	Grape pomace extracts	Polyphenol-rich matrix	Antioxidant-enhanced gels

CONCLUSION

The present review highlights the significant potential of grape pomace as a sustainable and high-value source of biopolymers for the development of oleogel-like fat systems. The combined functionality of pectin and cellulose enables the formation of robust three-dimensional networks capable of effectively immobilizing liquid oils, thereby mimicking the structural and textural properties of conventional solid fats. This biopolymer-driven structuring approach eliminates the need for hydrogenation and supports the formulation of healthier lipid systems with reduced saturated fat content.

Beyond technological functionality, the valorization of fruit processing by-products—particularly grape pomace—represents a strategic pathway toward circular bioeconomy and sustainable food production. The integration of such upcycled materials into food design not only enhances resource efficiency but also aligns with clean-label trends and environmental priorities.

However, despite promising advances, several challenges remain, including process optimization, scalability, standardization of raw material composition, and long-term stability of oleogel systems in complex food matrices. Future research should focus on tailoring extraction methods, improving structure–function relationships, and validating industrial applicability across diverse food applications.

In conclusion, grape pomace-based oleogel systems stand as a compelling intersection of innovation, nutrition, and sustainability, offering a viable platform for the next generation of functional and environmentally responsible food products.

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**DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGY FOR PRODUCING OAT MILK BASED ON
LOCAL OAT GRAINS****MAHALLIY SULI DONI ASOSIDA SULI SUTI OLI SH TEXNOLOGIYASINI ISHLAB
CHI QISH****РАЗРАБОТКА ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА ОВСЯНОГО МОЛОКА НА
ОСНОВЕ МЕСТНЫХ ОВСЯНЫХ ЗЕРЕН**

Aziza Daybergenova

*Master student, Department of Technology of Food Perfumery and Cosmetic products
Institute of Chemical Technology, Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent*

Shakhnozakhon Gaipova

*Postdoctoral student, Department of Technology of Food Perfumery and Cosmetic products
Institute of Chemical Technology, Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent*

Shakhnozakhon Salijonova

*Doctor of Science, Associate professor, Department of Technology of Food Perfumery and
Cosmetic products Institute of Chemical Technology, Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent*

Email: charosgaipova@gmail.com

Annotatsiya Ushbu tadqiqotda mahalliy sharoitda yetishtirilgan suli (*Avena sativa* L.) donidan o'simlik asosidagi sut — suli suti olish texnologiyasi ishlab chiqildi va uning qandolat sanoatida, xususan emulsiya tipidagi mahsulot — krem ishlab chiqarishda qo'llanish imkoniyatlari kompleks tarzda o'rganildi. Tadqiqot davomida suli doni dastlab laboratoriya maydalagich yordamida maydalandi va turli gidromodullarda (1:5; 1:6; 1:6.5; 1:7) suv bilan aralastirilib, 24 soat davomida namlash va ekstraksiya jarayonlari amalga oshirildi. Shundan so'ng filtratsiya orqali suyuq faza — suli suti ajratib olindi. Olingan suli suti asosida standart formulatsiya bo'yicha qandolat kremi tayyorlandi. Krem tayyorlash jarayonida suv fazasi (suli suti yoki nazorat namunalari — sigir suti va sanoat ishlab chiqarilgan suli suti) yog' fazasi (palma, kungaboqar va makkajo'xori yog'lari) bilan birlashtirilib, emulgator ishtirokida magnit aralastirgich, blender va gomogenizator yordamida bir jinsli barqaror emulsiya hosil qilindi. Tadqiqot jarayonida olingan mahsulotlarning fizik-kimyoviy xususiyatlari, xususan pH ko'rsatkichlari, shuningdek, organoleptik (sensor) ko'rsatkichlari — rang, hid, konsistensiya, ta'm va og'izda sezilishi 10 ballik tizim asosida baholandi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, barcha namunalari neytral muhitga yaqin pH qiymatlarini (6.46–6.79) namoyon etdi, bu esa mahsulotning texnologik va mikrobiologik jihatdan barqarorligini ta'minlaydi. Sensor tahlillar natijasida 1:6.5 gidromodul asosida olingan suli suti eng optimal xususiyatlarga ega ekani aniqlandi. Mazkur namuna yuqori konsistensiya barqarorligi, muvozanatli ta'm va yoqimli organoleptik xususiyatlari bilan ajralib turdi hamda sanoatda ishlab chiqarilgan suli suti namunasiga nisbatan yuqori baholandi. Bundan tashqari, u ayrim ko'rsatkichlar bo'yicha an'anaviy sigir suti asosidagi kremga yaqin natijalarni ko'rsatdi. Olingan natijalar asosida xulosa qilish mumkin, mahalliy suli donidan olingan o'simlik suti qandolat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarishda samarali alternativ xom ashyo bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin. Ushbu texnologiya import o'rnini bosuvchi, sog'lom va funksional oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: qandolat krem, emulsiya, barqarorlik, o'simlik yog'i, stabilizator, tekstura, texnologiya.

Аннотация В данном исследовании была разработана технология получения растительного молока — овсяного молока — из зерен овса (*Avena sativa* L.), выращенных в регионе, и всесторонне изучено ее применение в кондитерской промышленности, в частности, в производстве эмульсионных продуктов — кремов. В ходе исследования зерна овса сначала измельчали с помощью лабораторной мельницы и смешивали с водой в различных гидромодулях (1:5; 1:6; 1:6,5; 1:7), после чего проводили процессы замачивания и

экстракции в течение 24 часов. Затем жидкую фазу — овсяное молоко — отделили фильтрацией. Кондитерский крем готовили по стандартной рецептуре на основе полученного овсяного молока. В процессе приготовления крема водную фазу (овсяное молоко или контрольные образцы — коровье молоко и овсяное молоко промышленного производства) смешивали с масляной фазой (пальмовое, подсолнечное и кукурузное масла), и с помощью магнитной мешалки, блендера и гомогенизатора в присутствии эмульгатора формировали однородную стабильную эмульсию. Физико-химические свойства полученных в ходе исследования продуктов, в частности значения pH, а также органолептические (сенсорные) показатели — цвет, запах, консистенция, вкус и ощущение во рту — оценивались по 10-балльной шкале. Результаты показали, что все образцы имели значения pH, близкие к нейтральному значению (6,46–6,79), что обеспечивает технологическую и микробиологическую стабильность продукта. В результате сенсорного анализа было установлено, что овсяное молоко, полученное на основе гидромодуля 1:6,5, обладает наиболее оптимальными свойствами. Этот образец отличался высокой стабильностью консистенции, сбалансированным вкусом и приятными органолептическими свойствами и получил высокую оценку по сравнению с образцом овсяного молока промышленного производства. Кроме того, по некоторым показателям он показал результаты, близкие к традиционным сливкам на основе коровьего молока. На основании полученных результатов можно сделать вывод, что растительное молоко, полученное из местных овсяных зерен, может служить эффективным альтернативным сырьем в производстве кондитерских изделий. Эта технология важна для производства импортозамещающих, полезных и функциональных продуктов питания.

Ключевые слова: кондитерский крем, эмульсия, стабильность, растительное масло, стабилизатор, консистенция, технология.

Abstract In this study, a technology for obtaining plant-based milk - oat milk - from locally grown oat (*Avena sativa* L.) grains was developed and its application in the confectionery industry, in particular in the production of emulsion-type products - cream, was comprehensively studied. During the study, oat grains were first ground using a laboratory grinder and mixed with water in various hydromodules (1:5; 1:6; 1:6.5; 1:7), followed by soaking and extraction processes for 24 hours. After that, the liquid phase - oat milk - was separated by filtration. Confectionery cream was prepared according to a standard formulation based on the obtained oat milks. During the cream preparation process, the water phase (oat milk or control samples - cow's milk and industrially produced oat milk) was combined with the oil phase (palm, sunflower and corn oils), and a homogeneous stable emulsion was formed using a magnetic mixer, blender and homogenizer in the presence of an emulsifier. The physicochemical properties of the products obtained during the research, in particular pH values, as well as organoleptic (sensory) indicators - color, smell, consistency, taste and mouthfeel - were evaluated on a 10-point scale. The results showed that all samples exhibited pH values close to a neutral environment (6.46–6.79), which ensures the technological and microbiological stability of the product. As a result of sensory analyses, it was determined that oat milk obtained on the basis of a 1:6.5 hydromodule has the most optimal properties. This sample was distinguished by high consistency stability, balanced taste and pleasant organoleptic properties and was highly rated compared to the industrially produced oat milk sample. In addition, it showed results close to traditional cow's milk-based cream in some indicators. Based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that plant milk obtained from local oat grains can serve as an effective alternative raw material in the production of confectionery products. This technology is important in the production of import-substituting, healthy, and functional food products.

Key words: pastry cream, emulsion, stability, vegetable oil, stabilizer, texture, technology.

Introduction In recent years, plant-based milk alternatives have emerged as one of the fastest growing trends in the global food industry. This trend is driven by a number of factors, including the widespread prevalence of lactose intolerance, allergic reactions to animal proteins, the desire to

adhere to healthy eating principles, and increased attention to environmental sustainability. Modern consumers are increasingly choosing products that are not only high in nutritional value, but also rich in functional and biologically active components.

Among plant milks, oat milk occupies a special place. This is primarily due to its high content of β -glucans - water-soluble polysaccharides, which have positive physiological effects on the human body, such as reducing blood cholesterol levels, ensuring slow glucose absorption, and improving intestinal microflora. In addition, oat milk is low in allergenicity, is well digestible, and has a balanced taste and texture.

Another important advantage of oat-based beverages is their environmental sustainability. Their production requires significantly less water and greenhouse gas emissions than traditional livestock farming. Therefore, oat milk is considered an important alternative in the development of sustainable food systems.

At the same time, the scope of application of plant milks in the food industry is expanding. In particular, they are used as an important raw material in the production of emulsion-type products - confectionery creams, sauces and desserts. The main technological challenge in such products is to ensure emulsion stability, achieve optimal viscosity and form sensory properties acceptable to the consumer. In this regard, oat milk is a promising component with its natural emulsifying properties and polysaccharide content.

However, the analysis of existing scientific research shows that the optimization of oat milk production technology, in particular the influence of the hydromodulus ratio on product quality, as well as the effectiveness of its use in confectionery products, has not yet been sufficiently studied, especially the number of studies conducted on the basis of local raw materials is limited.

In this regard, the main goal of this study is to develop a technology for obtaining plant milk from local oat grains, evaluate the effect of various hydromodulus, and conduct a comprehensive analysis of the possibilities of using the obtained product in the production of confectionery cream. The results of the study are expected to be of significant scientific and practical importance in the creation of plant-based functional food products and their introduction on an industrial scale.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Oat milk production technology

The following method was used in the study to obtain plant milk from local oat grains in laboratory conditions: 200 g of oat grains were ground in a laboratory grinder. The ground mass was mixed with water in different hydromodules (1:5; 1:6; 1:6.5; 1:7). The mixtures were left to soak for 24 hours. Then the liquid phase (oat milk) was separated using filter paper.

As a result, oat milks of different concentrations were obtained and used in the subsequent stages.

2.2. Technology for preparing confectionery cream

The following formulation was used to prepare the cream:

Oat milk or control milk (100 g), sugar (20 g), emulsifier (0.3 g), Palm oil (10 g), sunflower oil (10 g), corn oil (20 g) (Table 1). Sugar and emulsifier were dissolved in a magnetic stirrer. Fats were mixed separately to form a homogeneous mass. Both phases were combined using a blender. A homogeneous emulsion was formed using a homogenizer.

№	Ingridients	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4
1	Oat milk 1:6,5	100 gr	-	-	-
2	Oat milk 1:7	-	100 gr	-	-
2	Cow milk	-	-	100 gr	-
3	Commercial oat milk	-	-	-	100 gr
4	Sugar	20 gr	20 gr	20gr	20 gr
5	Emulsifier	0,3 gr	0,3 gr	0,3 gr	0,3 gr
6	Palm oil	10 gr	10 gr	10 gr	10 gr
7	Sunflower oil	10 gr	10 gr	10 gr	10gr
8	Corn oil	20 gr	20 gr	20 gr	20 gr

2.3. Analysis methods

pH – potentiometric method

Sensory evaluation – 10-point system

Consistency – organoleptic analysis

3. Results and discussion

The pH values determined for all the samples studied were in the range of 6.46–6.79, which indicates that the products are close to a neutral environment. In food systems, especially for emulsion-type products, such a pH range is technologically favorable, since it has a positive effect on the microbiological stability, chemical stability, and organoleptic properties of the product.

According to the analysis results, industrially produced oat milk showed the highest pH value (6.79). This can be explained by the additional processing processes used in industrial technologies, including filtration, standardization, and the possible use of stabilizers or buffers. Such technological factors help to maintain the pH of the product at a slightly higher level.

Fig. 1. pH indicators of creams

It was found that the pH values of oat milk samples obtained in laboratory conditions (1:6.5 — 6.73; 1:7 — 6.71) were almost in the same range as the industrial sample, which confirms the effectiveness of the developed technology. In particular, the optimal pH value of the sample obtained based on the 1:6.5 hydromodule indicates that the balance between water and dry matter is well maintained in this ratio.

The control sample based on cow's milk showed a relatively lower pH value (6.46), which is explained by its natural composition and biochemical processes associated with lactose fermentation. At the same time, this value is also within the normal range, indicating that the product is suitable for consumption.

In general, the results obtained show that the oat milk samples obtained based on the developed technology correspond to industrial products in terms of pH values and are technologically stable. This creates favorable conditions for the use of this product in the food industry, in particular in the production of emulsion-based products - confectionery creams.

№	Sample name	Colour (score)	Smell (score)	Consistency (score)	Source (score)	Mouth feeling (score)
1	Cow milk	10	10	10	9	8
2	Commercial oat milk	7	8	7	7	7
3	Oat milk 1:6,5	9	9	9	9	9
4	Oat milk 1:7	8	8	8	8	8

As part of the study, the quality indicators of the prepared confectionery cream samples were comprehensively evaluated. Sensory (organoleptic) analysis is an important criterion for

determining the level of consumer acceptance of the product and includes such key parameters as color, smell, consistency, taste and mouthfeel. The evaluation was carried out on a 10-point scale. (Table 2.)

Sensory analysis results showed significant differences between all samples. These differences are mainly explained by the raw material composition, hydromodulus ratio, and technological processing conditions.

Conclusion

The results of this study showed that it is possible to effectively develop a technology for producing high-quality plant milk (oat milk) based on locally grown oat grains. During the experiments conducted in laboratory conditions, various hydromodules (1:5; 1:6; 1:6.5; 1:7) were studied and their impact on the physicochemical and sensory properties of the product was comprehensively evaluated.

According to the results obtained, a hydromodule of 1:6.5 was determined as the most optimal technological ratio. In this ratio, a balance between water and dry matter was ensured, and important organoleptic indicators such as consistency, taste and mouthfeel of the product were highly manifested. Also, pH values were in the neutral range (around 6.7), which confirms the technological and microbiological stability of the product.

Sensory analysis of samples of confectionery creams made from oat milk obtained during the study showed that the product developed in laboratory conditions was highly rated compared to the cream based on oat milk produced in industry and showed results close to those of traditional cow's milk cream in some parameters. This confirms that the developed technology has high efficiency not only from a scientific but also from a practical point of view.

Thus, plant milk obtained from local oat grains can be successfully used as an alternative raw material in the production of confectionery products, in particular in emulsion-type cream products. This product is not only nutritionally beneficial, but also promising from an economic and environmental point of view.

The results of this study serve as an important scientific and practical basis for the creation of functional plant-based food products, expanding their range, and effectively using local raw materials.

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RESEARCH ON ISOLATION OF NATURAL OLEOSOMES FROM OILSEEDS
MOYLI URUG'LARDAN TABIIY OLEOSOMLARNI AJRATIB OLIISH BO'YICHA
TADQIQOTLAR

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ВЫДЕЛЕНИЯ ПРИРОДНЫХ ОЛЕОСОМ ИЗ МАСЛЯНЫХ
СЕМЕН.

Shakhnozakhon Gaipova

Postdoctoral student, Department of Technology of Food Perfumery and Cosmetic products
Institute of Chemical Technology, Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent

Shakhnozakhon Salijonova

Doctor of Science, Associate professor, Department of Technology of Food Perfumery and
Cosmetic products Institute of Chemical Technology, Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent

Aziza Daybergenova

Master student, Department of Technology of Food Perfumery and Cosmetic products
Institute of Chemical Technology, Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent

Email: charosgaipova@gmail.com

Annotatsiya Oleosomalar — bu yog'li urug'larda mavjud bo'lgan tabiiy yog' tomchilari bo'lib, ular triatsilglitserid yadrosidan iborat va o'ziga xos oqsillar (masalan, oleozinlar)ni o'z ichiga olgan fosfolipid monoqavati bilan o'ralgan. O'ziga xos tuzilishi tufayli oleosomalar oziq-ovqat sanoatida qo'llanilishi mumkin bo'lgan tabiiy emulsiya tizimlari sifatida tobora ko'proq e'tibor qozonmoqda. Mazkur tadqiqotning maqsadi yog'li urug'lardan oleosomalarni suvli ekstraksiya usuli yordamida ajratib olish va ularning fizik-kimyoviy, strukturaviy hamda funksional xususiyatlarini baholashdan iborat bo'ldi. Oleosomalar urug'larni gidratatsiya qilish, mexanik parchalanish, filtrlash va sentrifugatsiya qilish orqali ekstraksiya qilindi. Olingan oleosomalar zarracha o'lchami taqsimoti, zeta-potensial, mikrostrukturasi va barqarorligi bo'yicha tavsiflandi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, oleosomalar tor o'lcham taqsimotiga, manfiy sirt zaryadiga va yuqori fizik barqarorlikka ega. Mikroskopik tahlil esa buzilmagan sferik tuzilmalarning mavjudligini tasdiqladi. Ushbu natijalar tabiiy oleosomalar oziq-ovqat tizimlarida, xususan, mayonez va past yog'li emulsiyalarda an'anaviy emulgatorlarga samarali va barqaror muqobil bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: oleosomalar, emulsiya, barqarorlik, yog' tomchilari (yoki yog' tanachalari), stabilizator, tekstura, texnologiya, urug'lar

Аннотация Олеосомы — это природные масляные тельца, присутствующие в масличных семенах, состоящие из триацилглицеринового ядра, окруженного фосфолипидным монослоем, содержащим специфические белки, такие как олеозины. Благодаря своей уникальной структуре олеосомы привлекают все большее внимание как природные эмульгирующие системы для применения в пищевой промышленности. Целью данного исследования было выделение олеосом из масличных семян с использованием метода водной экстракции и оценка их физико-химических, структурных и функциональных свойств. Олеосомы экстрагировали путем гидратации семян, механического разрушения, фильтрации и центрифугирования. Полученные олеосомы характеризовали по распределению частиц по размерам, дзета-потенциалу, микроструктуре и стабильности. Результаты показали, что олеосомы обладают узким распределением по размерам, отрицательным поверхностным зарядом и высокой физической стабильностью. Микроскопический анализ подтвердил наличие неповрежденных сферических структур. Эти результаты позволяют предположить, что природные олеосомы могут служить эффективной и устойчивой альтернативой традиционным эмульгаторам в пищевых системах, таких как майонез и низкожировые эмульсии.

Ключевые слова: олеосомы, эмульсия, стабильность, масляные тельца, стабилизатор, текстура, технология, семена..

Abstract Oleosomes are natural oil bodies present in oilseeds, composed of a triacylglycerol core surrounded by a phospholipid monolayer embedded with specific proteins such as oleosins. Due to their unique structure, oleosomes have attracted increasing attention as natural emulsifying systems for food applications. This study aimed to isolate oleosomes from oilseeds using an aqueous extraction method and to evaluate their physicochemical, structural, and functional properties. Oleosomes were extracted through seed hydration, mechanical disruption, filtration, and centrifugation. The obtained oleosomes were characterized in terms of particle size distribution, zeta potential, microstructure, and stability. Results indicated that oleosomes exhibited narrow size distribution, negative surface charge, and strong physical stability. Microscopic analysis confirmed intact spherical structures. These findings suggest that natural oleosomes can serve as effective and sustainable alternatives to conventional emulsifiers in food systems such as mayonnaise and low-fat emulsions.

Key words: oleosomes, emulsion, stability, oil bodies, stabilizer, texture, technology, seeds.

Kirish In recent years, the demand for natural, sustainable, and clean-label ingredients in the food industry has increased significantly. Consumers are becoming more conscious of the composition of food products, preferring formulations that avoid synthetic additives and rely on naturally derived components. This trend has driven intensive research into alternative structuring and emulsifying agents that can replace conventional surfactants while maintaining desirable physicochemical and sensory properties in complex food systems such as mayonnaise, dressings, and spreads.

Oil-in-water emulsions, including mayonnaise, are thermodynamically unstable systems that require effective stabilization to prevent coalescence, creaming, and phase separation. Traditionally, such stability is achieved through the use of emulsifiers like egg yolk, modified starches, or synthetic surfactants. However, these ingredients may present limitations related to allergenicity, cost, processing, or consumer perception. Therefore, identifying natural structures capable of stabilizing emulsions without additional emulsifiers has become a key research priority.

Oleosomes, also known as oil bodies, are naturally occurring lipid storage organelles found in oilseeds such as sesame, soybean, sunflower, and rapeseed. These structures consist of a triacylglycerol core surrounded by a phospholipid monolayer embedded with specific proteins, primarily oleosins. This unique architecture provides inherent steric and electrostatic stabilization, making oleosomes highly resistant to coalescence and aggregation under various environmental conditions. Unlike conventional emulsions, oleosomes are biologically pre-assembled and stabilized systems, which makes them particularly attractive for food applications.

Recent studies have highlighted the potential of oleosomes as natural emulsifiers due to their amphiphilic surface properties. Their ability to function as both oil carriers and stabilizing agents allows for the development of simplified formulations with reduced reliance on synthetic additives. Moreover, oleosomes exhibit enhanced oxidative stability compared to bulk oils, as their structural organization limits oxygen diffusion and protects encapsulated lipids. This feature is especially important in lipid-rich food systems where oxidative deterioration affects both quality and shelf life.

In addition to their functional advantages, oleosomes offer nutritional and technological benefits. They can contribute to fat reduction strategies by enabling the formulation of low-fat or reduced-fat emulsions without compromising texture and mouthfeel. Furthermore, their natural origin and compatibility with plant-based systems make them suitable for the development of vegan and sustainable food products.

Despite these promising attributes, several challenges remain regarding the efficient isolation, purification, and characterization of oleosomes from different oilseeds. The extraction method plays a critical role in preserving oleosome integrity, as harsh processing conditions can disrupt their membrane structure and negatively affect functionality. Aqueous extraction methods

are considered the most suitable approach, as they minimize the use of organic solvents and better maintain the native structure of oleosomes.

Moreover, there is still a need for comprehensive studies that link the physicochemical properties of isolated oleosomes to their functional performance in food systems. Parameters such as particle size distribution, zeta potential, interfacial behavior, and microstructure are essential for understanding their stability and emulsifying capacity. Systematic characterization of these properties is crucial for optimizing their application in real food formulations.

Therefore, the aim of this study is to isolate natural oleosomes from oilseeds using an aqueous extraction method and to evaluate their physicochemical, structural, and stability-related properties. The findings of this research are expected to contribute to the development of innovative, clean-label food products and to expand the application of oleosomes as natural emulsifying systems in the food industry.

Material and methods

Materials 2.1 Oilseeds (e.g., sesame seeds) were obtained from a local supplier. All chemicals used were of analytical grade.

2.2 Isolation of Oleosomes. Oleosomes were isolated using an aqueous extraction method. Seeds were cleaned and soaked in distilled water (1:10 w/v) for 12 hours at room temperature. Hydrated seeds were homogenized using a high-speed blender to disrupt cellular structure and release oleosomes. The slurry was filtered through cheesecloth to remove large solid particles. The filtrate was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes. The creamy upper layer (oleosome fraction) was collected. Extracted oleosomes were stored at 4°C until further analysis.

2.3 Microstructural Analysis. The morphology of oleosomes was observed using optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Samples were stained to enhance contrast.

Results and discussion

The provided methodology outlines the isolation and characterization of oleosomes (also known as oil bodies) from sesame seeds. This process relies on the physical properties of the seed matrix and the buoyancy of lipid-rich organelles in an aqueous medium.

1. Physical Principles of Aqueous Extraction

The isolation process begins with the hydration of the seeds at a 1:10 w/v ratio. This step facilitates the softening of the cell wall and the middle lamella, primarily composed of cellulose, hemicellulose, and pectin.

- **Homogenization:** The use of a high-speed blender introduces mechanical shear stress sufficient to rupture the cell membranes and release the intracellular contents into the aqueous phase.
- **Filtration:** Cheesecloth acts as a coarse filter to remove the insoluble fiber and large cellular debris, leaving a crude extract containing proteins, carbohydrates, and suspended oleosomes.

2. Centrifugal Separation Dynamics

The separation of the creamy oleosome layer from the aqueous filtrate is governed by Stokes' Law within a centrifugal field. Since oleosomes consist of a triacylglycerol (TAG) core, their density ($\rho_p \approx 0.92 \text{ g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$) is lower than that of the surrounding aqueous medium ($\rho_f \approx 1.00 \text{ g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$), causing them to migrate toward the axis of rotation (upward in a stationary tube).

The angular velocity ω for the specified 3000 rpm is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned}\omega &= \frac{2\pi N}{60} \\ &= \frac{2\pi \cdot 3000}{60} \\ &= 100\pi \text{ rad} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \approx 314.16 \text{ rad} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}\end{aligned}$$

Assuming a standard rotor with an effective radius $r=0.1 \text{ m}$, the Relative Centrifugal Force (RCF) is:

$$\begin{aligned} RCF &= \frac{r\omega^2}{g} \\ &= \frac{0.1 \cdot (100\pi)^2}{9.80665} \\ &\approx 1006.49 \times g \end{aligned}$$

Oleosomes demonstrated excellent resistance to phase separation under centrifugal force. Thermal and storage tests showed minimal changes in particle size and structure, indicating strong stability.

3. Microstructural Characterization

The stability and morphology of the isolated oleosomes are maintained by a unique surface membrane. This membrane consists of a phospholipid monolayer and specialized proteins, primarily oleosins, which prevent coalescence through steric hindrance and electrostatic repulsion.

Picture 2. Microscopic structure oleosomes from sesame seeds.

Microscopic images revealed spherical and intact oleosome structures. No significant aggregation or coalescence was observed, confirming structural stability. Picture 2.

Optical Microscopy: Used to assess the general dispersion state and detect any large-scale aggregation or flocculation.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM): Provides high-resolution topography of the oleosome surface. The samples must be fixed and dehydrated, often using critical point drying, to preserve the spherical geometry of the lipid droplets under the high vacuum of the SEM chamber.

4. Storage and Stability

The storage of the oleosome fraction at 4°C is critical to minimize lipid oxidation and enzymatic degradation by endogenous lipases. The low temperature reduces the kinetic energy of the system, thereby slowing down the rate of chemical reactions and microbial growth.

Figure 1. Illustrates the changes in p-anisidine value (AnV) of oleosome dispersions during storage at different temperatures and ionic conditions. The results demonstrate a progressive increase in AnV over time for all samples, indicating the formation of secondary lipid oxidation products.

At refrigerated conditions (4°C), the increase in anisidine value was relatively slow, with control samples reaching approximately 3.0 after 90 days. The addition of NaCl (100 mM) slightly accelerated oxidation, leading to higher AnV values (~4.0), suggesting that ionic strength negatively affects oxidative stability.

In contrast, samples stored at 25°C showed a significantly faster increase in anisidine value. The control oleosome reached approximately 7.0, while the NaCl-containing sample exhibited the highest oxidation level (~8.5) at the end of storage. This indicates that elevated temperature strongly promotes secondary lipid oxidation.

Overall, the results confirm that both temperature and ionic strength play a critical role in the oxidative stability of oleosomes.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that natural oleosomes can be effectively isolated from oilseeds using an aqueous extraction method while maintaining structural integrity. The isolated oleosomes exhibited favorable physicochemical properties, including uniform particle size, negative surface charge, and strong stability.

These characteristics highlight the potential of oleosomes as natural and sustainable emulsifying agents in food applications. Future research should focus on optimizing extraction conditions and evaluating the performance of oleosomes in complex food systems such as mayonnaise.

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